

OPUSCULA ZOOLOGICA

INSTITUTI ZOOSYSTEMATICI
ET OECOLOGICI UNIVERSITATIS
BUDAPESTINENSIS

Redacta ab

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TOMUS LVI, FASCICULUS I

**A Catalogue of Oribatida Types of the “Balogh Collection” in
the Hungarian Natural History Museum (Arachnida,
Acariformes)**

by

E. HORVÁTH & Cs. CSUZDI

Monograph

<https://doi.org/10.18348/opzool.2025.1.3>
<https://zoobank.org/References/3A6338FE-028C-4ACF-87CC-9D030CDCE957>

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BUDAPEST, 2025

Opusc. Zool. Budapest, 56 (1), 2025

Launched in 1956

by

DR. ISTVÁN ANDRÁSSY, DR. ÁRPÁD BERCZIK and DR. GYÖRGY KERTÉSZ

The publication is supported by
the Hungarian Academy of Sciences

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eISSN 2063-1588

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Published: 24 March 2025.

A catalogue of Oribatida types of the “Balogh collection” in the Hungarian Natural History Museum (Arachnida, Acariformes)

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Abstract. Academician János Balogh was one of the most outstanding acarologists of his time. During his collecting expeditions around the world, he amassed an internationally significant collection of mites and described more than 1,000 species of oribatid mites. This outstanding collection is now housed in the Hungarian Museum of Natural History. In this article, we summarise the results of the revision of his collection and adapt the nomenclature of the species to the current taxonomy. A total of 1142 Oribatida species names are reported that can be attributed to the work of János Balogh, Judith Csizsár or Péter Balogh. Of these, we found the holotypes of 674 species in the collection, and the holotypes of 289 species that should be in the collection according to the literature appear to be missing. In addition, we also report names described by J. Balogh and P. Balogh in 2002 that do not meet the current ICZN requirements and should be considered nomina nuda, as follows: *Acroppia papuana* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002; *Cavernocephus obliquus* P. Balogh, 2002; *Cavernocephus undulatus* P. Balogh, 2002; *Dimidiogalumna walworki* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002; *Dolichereмаeus berlesei* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002; *Flagroscutobelba simillima* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002; *Galumna engelbrechti* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002; *Malaconothrus valeriae* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002; *Paulinacarus sarkari* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002; *Pedrocortezella pletzenae* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002; *Pulchroppia mahunkarum* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002; *Rhysotritia niedbalai* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002; *Scapheremaeus hammerae* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002; *Scutobelbella permixta* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002; *Trimalaconothrus multipilosus* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002. In addition, three other replacement names have been synonymised because the secondary homonymy no longer exists, namely *Megaschelorbates pajaki* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002 (= *Schelorbates (Schelorbates) microsetosus* (Lee & Pajak, 1990)); *Pedrocortezella pletzenae* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002 (= *Pheroliodes africaus* (Balogh, 1966)) and *Unguizetes hammeri* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002 (= *Chamobates (Chamobates) javensis* (Hammer, 1979)).

Keywords. Acari, Oribatida, moss mites, species list, nomen nudum, secondary homonym.

INTRODUCTION

János Balogh (1913–2002) a full member of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences was one of the leading acarologists of his time. After graduating from Pázmány Péter University, Budapest in 1935, he was appointed to the Department of Zoology and Zoogeography where he continued to work after his retirement (1984) until his death in 2002 (Dózsa-Farkas 2003).

It is worth noting that János Balogh started his career studying spiders, and by the time he got to the university he was practically a well-trained a-

carologist. This group was also the subject of his first and still influential study, "A Sas-hegy pókfaunája (Spider fauna of the Sas Hill)", published as a small booklet in 1935, and was also the basis of his doctoral thesis (Balogh 1935, Szinetár *et al.* 2012).

After joining the Department of Systematic Zoology and Zoogeography of Pázmány Péter University as an unpaid assistant professor in 1935, his interest turned to the soil mesofauna, especially mites (Acari), perhaps at the suggestion of the then head of the department, Professor Endre Dudich. (Mahunka 2003).

János Balogh promptly realized that the Hungarian mite fauna is largely unexplored and it is true for the entire Carpathian Basin. From the second half of the 1930s, he threw himself into the study of mites with great enthusiasm, and between 1937 and 1939 he published several new species to science and new data on the Hungarian fauna (*e.g.* Balogh 1937, 1938, 1939). As a result of his diligent research work, in 1943 he published a review of the Hungarian oribatid mites (Balogh 1943, "*Conspectus Oribateorum Hungariae*"), which also served as his habilitation thesis (Mahunka 2003).

With the support of UNESCO, professor Balogh made his first trip to the tropics of Africa in 1963. After that, he went on more than 30 expeditions and collecting trips to South America, New Guinea, Australia, Oceania and New Caledonia. Of course, he collected in all regions mainly soil animals, but he also tried to collect other groups as well. His last expedition was to the tropical island of São Tomé in 2000 (Mahunka 2003, Horváth & Kontschán 2013).

János Balogh was a very prolific scientist. He published 7 scientific monographs, several book chapters and about 150 scientific articles and described (with co-authors) more than 1000 oribatid species, representing about one tenth of the world's known species (Subias 2023). However, his collection of Oribatida mites is much richer, containing more than 5000 vials (mostly unidentified) from different regions of the world (*e.g.* South America, Fiji Islands, Australia, New Guinea, Hawaii, *etc.*) and is now deposited in the Soil Zoology Collections of the Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest.

In the present paper we list the oribatid mite species described by the late Professor János Balogh (and his co-authors), his wife Judith Csiszár and his son Péter Balogh, and present the data resulting from a thorough revision of his material now housed in the Natural History Museum, Budapest.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

All publications by J. Balogh (and co-authors) were thoroughly checked for new nomina and the data in the publication were compared with those in the collection files and also with the labels on the vials found. Where discrepancies are found, they are noted in the remarks for each entry.

For each species, we list the valid combination according to Subias (2004 and updates), except in a few cases where the late Sándor Mahunka strongly disagreed. Also in the synonymy section, we list the primary combination of the name together with important synonyms and a reference to the last valid combination. We also list the depository of the type material given in the original publication and, if it is in the Hungarian Natural History Museum, the number of type specimens found during the revision.

In the book "Identification Keys to the Oribatid Mites of the extra-Holarctic Regions. vols. I–II." (J. Balogh & P. Balogh 2002) the authors presented seven "new species" and several nomina nova. Unfortunately, some of the new species and most of the published nomina nova represent nomina nuda and thus unavailable names, because they do not fulfil ICZN (2000) Art. 16.4.1., 16.4.2. However, in order to make the list complete, we also present these names. In addition, for each replacement name for secondary homonyms, we checked that the secondary homonymy still existed and corrected the valid name where necessary.

Abbreviations of depositories used in the text are as follows:

BMNH, British Museum of Natural History
HNHM, Hungarian Natural History Museum
MHNG, Muséum d'histoire naturelle, Genève
NM, KwaZulu-Natal Museum, Pietermaritzburg
NMT, National Museum, Tokyo (Coll. Aoki)
NSMT, National Science Museum, Tokyo
ZIL, Zoological Institute of Academy of Sciences, Leningrad

TAXONOMY

ORIBATIDA van der Hammen, 1968

PALAEOSOMATA Grandjean, 1969

ACARONYCHOIDEA Grandjean, 1932

ACARONYCHIDAE Grandjean, 1932

Loftacarus Lee, 1980

Loftacarus longicaudatus (Balogh & Csiszár, 1963)

Stomacarus longicaudatus Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 467, fig. 1.

Loftacarus longicaudatus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1988b: 13.

Stomacarus longicaudatus: Fredes 2018: 15.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

ENARTHRONOTA Grandjean, 1969

BRACHYCHTHONIOIDEA Thor, 1934

BRACHYCHTHONIIDAE Thor, 1934

Brachychthonius Berlese, 1910

Brachychthonius africanus Balogh, 1958

Brachychthonius africanus Balogh, 1958: 4.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Brachychthonius impressus Moritz, 1976

Brachychochthonius subcrucoides Balogh & Mahunka, 1979b: 283, figs 4–6.

Sellnickochthonius subcrucoides: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 65.

Sellnickochthonius subcrucoides: Miko 2016: 18.

Brachychochthonius impressus: Behan-Pelletier & Lindo 2019: 13.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG (*S. subcrucoides*).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype (*S. subcrucoides*).

Brachychthonius pauliani Balogh & Mahunka, 1966

Brachychthonius pauliani Balogh & Mahunka, 1966b: 26, fig. 1.

Brachychthonius pauliani: Ermilov, Stanchaeva & Subías 2022: 379.

Type material in the literature: Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-103-67/Afr).

Eobrachychthonius Jacot, 1936

Eobrachychthonius longisetosus Csiszár, 1961

Eobrachychthonius longisetosus Csiszár, 1961b: 447, fig. 1.

Eobrachychthonius longisetosus: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 49.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes ELTE Állatrendszertani Intézet (Department of Systematic Zoology, Eötvös Loránd University).

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Liochthonius Hammen, 1959

Liochthonius (Liochthonius) szemmelveiszi J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983

Liochthonius szemmelveiszi J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 303, fig. 1.

Type material in the literature. Holotype in the Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Poecilochthonius Balogh, 1943

Poecilochthonius spiciger (Berlese, 1910)

Brachychthonius rapoportii Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 318, fig 1.

Poecilochthonius rapoportii: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 148.
Poecilochthonius spiciger: Behan-Pelletier & Lindo 2019: 17.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fourteen paratypes. Holotype and the majority of paratypes are deposited in HNHM, some paratypes also in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Sellickochthonius* Krivolutsky, 1964**

***Sellickochthonius heterotrichus* (Balogh, 1963)**

Brachyochthonius heterotrichus Balogh, 1963: 35, fig. 1.

Sellickochthonius heterotrichus Subías 2004: 32.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. In the original description it is stated that the Holotype is deposited in Tervuren however, we have found it in the collection of the HNHM.

***Sellickochthonius hungaricus* (Balogh, 1943)**

Poecilochthonius hungaricus Balogh, 1943: 23, tab. IV, fig. 9.

Brachyochthonius hungaricus: Moritz 1976: 310.

Sellickochthonius hungaricus: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 61.

Brachyochthonius hungaricus: Starý 2006: 22.

Brachyochthonius hungaricus: Starý 2007: 13.

Sellickochthonius hungaricus: Miko 2016: 17.

Sellickochthonius hungaricus: Schatz 2018: 10.

Sellickochthonius rostratus hungaricus: Subías 2020: 24.

Type material in the literature. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Two microscope slides of doubtful status.

Remarks. In HNHM we have found two slides one with a hand-written label "*Brachyochthonius hungaricus* Prep. Balogh, Holotyp" Ócsa, 1950.

XI. 10 cm², No. 1, Loksa & Balogh (HNHM Oribpr-155). This seems to be a later sample near to the type locality Pótharasz (= Csévharasz). The other is a typical Frosslund preparation labelled as *Brachyochthonius hungaricus* Balogh, Neotypus, Ungarn, Ócsa, 1950, J. Balogh Leg. (HNHM Oribpr-5). It seems that this Neotypus designation was never published.

***Sellickochthonius oesziae* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1979)**

Brachyochthonius oesziae Balogh & Mahunka, 1979b: 283, figs 1–3.

Sellickochthonius oesziae: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 235.

Sellickochthonius oesziae: Miko 2016: 18.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype?

Remarks. The vial labelled as Holotype seems to be empty.

HYPOCHTHONIOIDEA Berlese, 1910

HYPOCHTHONIDAE Berlese, 1910

***Eohypochthonius* Jacot, 1938**

***Eohypochthonius (Eohypochthonius) becki* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

Eohypochthonius becki Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 35, fig. 1.

Eohypochthonius (Eohypochthonius) becki: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 7.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and forty seven paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG, three paratypes NMT.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and fifty two paratypes.

***Eohypochthonius (Eohypochthonius) vilhenarum* (Balogh, 1958)**

Afrhypochthonius vilhenarum Balogh, 1958: 4.

Eohypochthonius vilhenarum: Wallwork 1960: 374, figs: 4–5.

Eohypochthonius vilhenarum: Norton & Ermilov 2014: 14.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, á Tervuren.
Deposited in HNHM: Three paratypes.

Notrolohmanna Balogh, 1968

Nothrolohmanna calcarata Balogh, 1968

Nothrolohmanna calcarata Balogh, 1968: 260, pl. I, figs 1–2.
Nothrolohmanna calcarata: Norton & Ermilov 2014: 14.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), one paratype in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

LOHMANNIIDAE Berlese, 1916

Annectacus Grandjean, 1950

Annectacus africanus Balogh, 1961

Annectacus africanus Balogh, 1961b: 517, fig. 1.
Annectacus africanus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 347, fig. 36B.
Annectacus africanus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 14.
Annectacus africanus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 15.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, and one paratype.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Cryptacus Grandjean, 1950

Cryptacus tuberculatus Csiszár, 1961

Cryptacus tuberculatus Csiszár, 1961a: 346, figs 3–4.
Cryptacus tuberculatus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 337, 13D.
Cryptacus tuberculatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 14.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Dendracarus Balogh, 1961

Dendracarus pulchellus Balogh, 1961

Dendracarus pulchellus Balogh, 1961d: 16, figs 13–14.
Dendracarus pulchellus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: figs 346, 34A–B.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Javacarus (Javacarus) Balogh, 1961

Javacarus (Javacarus) granulatus Csiszár, 1961

Javacarus granulatus Csiszár, 1961a: 348, fig. 8.
Javacarus granulatus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 345, fig. 32A.
Javacarus granulatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 16.

Type material in the literature. Holotype in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Javacarus (Javacarus) inexpectatus Balogh, 1962

Javacarus inexpectatus Balogh, 1962c: 61.
Javacarus inexpectatus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 345.
Javacarus (Javacarus) inexpectatus: Subías 2004: 32.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Remarks. In the original description only a holotype is mentioned. The specimen labelled as “paratype” has the same locality and collector as of the holotype however, it was not published in the original description therefore its “paratype” status is invalid.

Javacarus (Javacarus) kuehnelti Balogh, 1961

Javacarus kuehnelti Balogh, 1961e: 31, figs 39–40.

Javacarus kuehnelti: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1986b: 269.

Javacarus kuehnelti: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 345, fig. 32C.

Javacarus kuehnelti: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 16.

Javacarus kuehnelti: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 16.

Type material in the literature. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Lepidacarus Csiszár, 1961

Lepidacarus ornatissimus Csiszár, 1961

Lepidacarus ornatissimus Csiszár, 1961a: 347, figs 5–6.

Lepidacarus ornatissimus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 335, figs 8C–D.

Lepidacarus ornatissimus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 16.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one tritonympha paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. According to the original description (Csiszár 1961) the type material was deposited in HNHM however, we did not find them in the collection. It appears to be lost.

Lohmannia (Lohmannia) Michael, 1898

Lohmannia (Lohmannia) javana Balogh, 1961

Lohmannia javana Balogh, 1961e: 26, figs 5–6.

Lohmannia javana javana: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 333, fig. 5B.

Lohmannia javana: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 16.

Lohmannia javana: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 17.

Type material in the literature. No data on deposition

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Lohmannia (Lohmannia) similis Balogh, 1962

Lohmannia similis Balogh, 1962c: 60, fig. 2.

Lohmannia similis: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 333, 4C.

Lohmannia similis: Norton & Ermilov 2014: 16.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fourteen, partly juvenile paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Meristacarus Grandjean, 1934

Meristacarus africanus africanus Balogh, 1958

Meristacarus africanus Balogh, 1958: 3.

Meristacarus africanus Balogh 1961a: 67, fig. 4.

Meristacarus africanus africanus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 340, fig. 20D.

Meristacarus africanus: Ermilov & Mary 2019: 634.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes according to (Balogh 1961a). Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. There is no holotype and no paratypes mentioned in the original description, the later designations (Balogh 1961a) are invalid and therefore all specimens are syntypes.

Meristacarus biroi Balogh, 1961

Meristacarus biroi Balogh, 1961e: 28, figs 22–22a.

Meristacarus biroi: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 340, fig. 20A.

Type material in the literature. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Meristacarus douhereti J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983

Meristacarus douhereti J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 304, fig. 2.

Meristacarus douhereti: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: fig. 340, 20C.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes, Balogh collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Two types.

Remarks. Although in the original description it is clearly stated that the species is described on

a holotype and two paratypes, in the collection we have found a vial with the label of "types" containing two specimens. It seems that the holotype was lost.

***Meristacarus heterotrichus heterotrichus*
Csiszár, 1961**

Meristacarus heterotrichus Csiszár, 1961a: 348, fig. 7.
Meristacarus heterotrichus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 340, fig. 20B.
Meristacarus heterotrichus heterotrichus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 17.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and six paratypes.

Remarks. In the vial labelled as paratypes there are six specimens with locality Java, Leg. Hamman. It should be checked by an expert to decide whether all the six specimens belong to the same species.

***Meristacarus madagascarensis madagascarensis*
Balogh, 1962**

Meristacarus madagascarensis Balogh, 1962e: 122, figs 1–3.
Meristacarus madagascarensis madagascarensis: Balogh & Balogh 1987: 340, pl. 23: B.
Meristacarus madagascarensis: Mahunka 1997a: 118.
Meristacarus madagascarensis: Mahunka 2002b: 9.
Meristacarus madagascarensis madagascarensis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 69, pl. 122: 2.
Meristacarus madagascarensis madagascarensis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 18.

Type material in the literature. Holotype l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar, and twenty paratypes without indication of deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and twelve paratypes.

***Meristolohmannia* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

***Meristolohmannia meristacaroides* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Meristolohmannia meristacaroides Balogh & Mahunka, 1966c: 555, figs 1–2.

Meristolohmannia meristacaroides: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 332, figs 3B–C.

Meristolohmannia meristacaroides: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 60.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. Type specimens are in the Austral Museum and the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Six syntypes.

Remarks. The species was described on a holotype and five paratypes. In the vial found in HNHM there are six specimens. It seems that the holotype and paratypes were not separated by the original authors therefore, they represent syntypes.

Mixacarus (Mixacarus) Balogh, 1958

***Mixacarus (Mixacarus) integer* Balogh, 1958**

Mixacarus integer Balogh, 1958: 4.

Mixacarus integer: Balogh 1960b: 90, figs 1–2.

Mixacarus integer: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 341, fig. 24C.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Nine paratypes (0-1127-68/Afr), twelve paratypes (0-348-68/Afr).

Remarks. There is no mention of the number of specimens examined in the original description. Later Balogh (1960b) reports on a holotype and eight paratypes. However, we found two vials of paratypes containing nine and twelve specimens. The vial with nine specimens (0-1127-68/Afr) has a label with only 'Angola' written on it and matches the 1+8 specimens reported by Balogh (1960b) as type material, so they are syntypes of *M. integer*. The other vial containing 12 specimens has a more detailed locality (Angola Riv. Camipopo26.II.1954. Ang.4067-47) and is labelled as *Mixacarus integer* Balogh (and not sp. n. or sp. nov.), which clearly indicates that these specimens were identified later and are therefore not part of the type material.

***Mixacarus (Mixacarus) neotropicus* Balogh, 1962**

Mixacarus neotropicus Balogh, 1962c: 61.

Mixacarus neotropicus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 341.

Mixacarus (Mixacarus) neotropicus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 8.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty five, partly juvenile paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remark. According to the museum files the type material was lent to Dr. L. Beck in 1997.

Mixacarus (Phyllolohmannia) J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1987

Mixacarus (Phyllolohmannia) hamanni Balogh, 1961

Mixacarus hamanni Balogh, 1961e: 27, figs 17–18.

Mixacarus hamanni[sic!]: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 342, figs 25C–D.

Mixacarus (Phyllolohmannia) hamanni: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 18.

Type material in the literature. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Nesiacarus Csiszár, 1961

Nesiacarus australis Balogh & Mahunka, 1981

Nesiacarus australis Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 56, figs 7–11.

Nesiacarus australis: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 339, figs 18C–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

Nesiacarus reticulatus Csiszár, 1961

Nesiacarus reticulatus Csiszár, 1961a: 346, figs 1–2.

Nesiacarus reticulatus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 339, fig. 18B.

Nesiacarus reticulatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 19.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Ozacarus Colloff & Halliday, 1998

Ozacarus reductus (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983)

Austracarus reductus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983b: 290, fig. 5.

Austracarus reductus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 339, figs pl. 19B–C.

Ozacarus reductus Colloff & Halliday 1998: 61. comb. nov.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. The holotype is deposited in the CSIRO Canberra, the paratypes partly in the above institute and partly in the Balogh collection.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. According to the documentation in HNHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO in 1994. The paratypes remained at HNHM where they were lost due to the broken vial.

Papillacarus (Vepracarus) Aoki, 1965

Papillacarus (Vepracarus) ramosus Balogh, 1961

Papillacarus ramosus Balogh, 1961e: 26, figs 11–12.

Vepracarus ramosus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 336, fig. 13B.

Papillacarus ramosus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 20.

Papillacarus (Vepracarus) ramosus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 23.

Type material in the literature No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Paulianacarus (Millotacarus) Balogh, 1961

Paulianacarus (Millotacarus) granulatus (Balogh, 1961)

Millotacarus granulatus Balogh, 1961d: 12, figs 10–12.

Millotacarus granulatus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 344, figs 31A–B.

Paulianacarus (Millotacarus) granulatus: Subías 2004: 41.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Paulianacarus (Millotacarus) sabrias* Coetzee, 2001**

Paulianacarus (Millotacarus) sarbias Coetzee, 2001: 58.

Paulianacarus sarkarae P. Balogh, 2002: 72.

Remarks. This species was originally described as *Paulianacarus foliatus* Sarkar & Subías, 1984. However, this name was preoccupied by *Paulianacarus foliatus* Mondal & Chakrabarti, 1983 therefore Coetzee (2001) provided the replacement name *Paulianacarus (Millotacarus) sarbias* Coetzee, 2001. Paralelly P. Balogh (2002) has also provided a replacement name *Paulianacarus sarkarae* P. Balogh, 2002 which represents a junior synonym of *P. (M.) sabrias*.

Paulianacarus (Paulianacarus) Balogh, 1961

***Paulianacarus (Paulianacarus) laevis* Balogh, 1961**

Paulianacarus laevis Balogh, 1961d: 10, figs 3–4.

Paulianacarus levis [sic!]: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 344, fig. 31C.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Paulianacarus (Paulianacarus) nodosus* Balogh, 1961**

Paulianacarus nodosus Balogh, 1961d: 10, figs 5–7.

Paulianacarus nodosus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 344, figs 30B–C.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Paulianacarus (Paulianacarus) rugosus* Balogh, 1961**

Paulianacarus rugosus Balogh, 1961d: 12, figs 8–9.

Paulianacarus rugosus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 344, fig. 29D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Torpacarus* Grandjean, 1950**

***Torpacarus omittens paraguayensis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

Torpacarus omittens paraguayensis Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 56, figs 12–16.

Torpacarus omittens paraguayensis: Mahunka 1984b: 111.

Torpacarus omittens paraguayensis: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 343, fig. 27C.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nineteen paratypes HNHM, four paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and twenty two paratypes.

***Xenolohmannia* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Xenolohmannia capillata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Xenolohmannia capillata Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 274, figs 3A–C.

Xenolohmannia capillata: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 339, figs 17B–C.

Xenolohmannia capillata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 9.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

***Xenolohmannia comosa* P. Balogh, 1984**

Xenolohmannia comosa P. Balogh, 1984a: 35, figs 4A–B.

Xenolohmannia comosa: J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1987: 355, fig. 17A.

Type material in the literature: Holotype and eight paratypes. No data on deposition

Deposited in HNHM: Nine types.

Remarks. It seems that the holotype and paratypes were not separated and are now indistinguishable, therefore we propose to consider all these specimens as syntypes.

***Xenolohmannia discrepans* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Xenolohmannia discrepans Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 2, figs 1–5.

Xenolohmannia discrepans: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1987: 339, fig. 18A.

Xenolohmannia discrepans: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 9.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-508-68/D-Am).

MESOPLOPHORIDAE Ewing, 1917

***Mesoplophora (Mesoplophora)* Berlese, 1904**

***Mesoplophora (Mesoplophora) africana* Balogh, 1958**

Mesoplophora africana Balogh, 1958: 32.

Mesoplophora (Mesoplophora) africana: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 17.

Mesoplophora africana: Ermilov & Mary 2019: 634.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Eleven paratypes.

Remarks. In the museum we found eleven specimens labelled as paratypes. However, in the original description no holotype was designated therefore these specimens should be part of the syntype series.

PROTOPLOPHOROIDEA Ewing, 1917

SPHAEROCHTHONIIDAE Grandjean, 1947

***Sphaerochthonius* Berlese, 1910**

***Sphaerochthonius phyllophorus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Sphaerochthonius phyllophorus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 32, fig. 4.

Sphaerochthonius phyllophorus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 11.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. Holotype and the majority of paratypes in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of: J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. According to the HNHM registry, a vial of paratypes should also be in the HNHM, but we did not find it in the collection.

PARHYPOSOMATA Grandjean, 1969

PARHYPOCHTHONIOIDEA Grandjean, 1932

PARHYPOCHTHONIIDAE Grandjean, 1932

***Parhypochthonius* Berlese, 1904**

***Parhypochthonius africanus* Balogh, 1958**

Parhypochthonius africanus Balogh, 1958: 2.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

MIXONOMATA Grandjean, 1969

EPILOHMANNIOIDEA Oudemans, 1923

EPILOHMANNIIDAE Oudemans, 1923

***Epilohmannia (Epilohmannia)* Berlese, 1910**

***Epilohmannia (Epilohmannia) barbatula* Balogh, 1958**

Epilohmannia barbatula Balogh, 1958: 3.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Epilohmannia (Epilohmannia) insignipes*
Balogh, 1962**

Epilohmannia insignipes Balogh, 1962e: 123, figs 4–6.

Type material in the literature. Holotype l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Epilohmannia (Epilohmannia) minuta minuta*
Berlese, 1920**

Epilohmannia minuta Berlese, 1920: 149.

Epilohmannia pallida americana Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 59, figs 22–25.

Epilohmannia pallida americana: Mahunka 1998: 842.

Epilohmannia miunuta: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 12.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fifty two paratypes in HNHM, eight paratypes in MHNG (*E. pallida americana*).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and thirty four paratypes (*E. pallida americana*).

***Epilohmannia (Epilohmannia) sculpturata*
Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Epilohmannia sculpturata Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 24, figs 2A–C.

Epilohmannia sculpturata: Fredo 2018: 30.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and ten paratypes.

Epilohmannia (Neoepilohmannia) McDaniell & Bolen, 1989

***Epilohmannia (Neoepilohmannia) guarani*
Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

Epilohmannia guarani Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 5, fig. 4.

Epilohmannia guarani: Balogh & Mahunka 1981: 58, figs 17–21.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Epilohmannia (Neoepilohmannia) lenkoi*
Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

Epilohmannia lenkoi Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 6, fig. 5.

Epilohmannia lenkoi: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 12.

Epilohmannia (Neoepilohmannia) lenkoi: Subías 2017: 51.

Epilohmannia lenkoi: Fredes 2018: 29.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype ZIL.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

EUPHTHRACAROIDEA Jacot, 1930

EUPHTHRACARIDAE Jacot, 1930

***Acrotrititia* Jacot, 1923**

***Acrotrititia vestita* (Berlese, 1913)**

Eremella vestita Berlese, 1913: 96, fig. 7: 78.

Rhysotrititia comteae Mahunka, 1983b: 273, figs. 4–7.

Rhysotrititia anchistea Niedbała, 1998: 62, figs. 127–134.

Rhysotrititia niedbalai Balogh & Balogh, 2002: 46, figs: 98: 4–5. **nomen nudum.**

Acrotrititia vestita: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 202.

Type material in the literature. No mention.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found (*Rh. niedbalai*).

Remarks. Balogh & Balogh (2002) separated the oriental populations of *Acrotrititia anchistea* Niedbała, 1998 to a new species *Rhysotrititia niedbalai* which is a nomen nudum because fails to meet ICZN Art. 16. It was synonymized with *Acrotrititia comteae* Mahunka, 1983 by Niedbała (2006) and later all the three names with *Acrotrititia vestita* (Berlese, 1913) (Niedbała 2011).

ORIBOTRITIIDAE Grandjean, 1954

Indotritia (Zeaotritia) Mahunka, 1988

Indotritia (Zeaotritia) brevisetosa Niedbala, 2000

- Indotritia brevisetosa* Niedbala & Colloff, 1997: 494, figs 6–13.
Indotritia (Zeaotritia) brevisetosa Niedbala, 2000: 340. "nom. nov."
Indotritia coloffi[!] J. Balogh & P. Balogh 2002: 43. nom. nov.
Indotritia (Zeaotritia) brevisetosa: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 38.

Type material in the literature. N/A.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. Balogh & Balogh (2002) provided a replacement name for *Indotritia brevisetosa* Niedbala & Colloff, 1997 non *Indotritia brevisetosa* (Berlese, 1923). However, the name has been replaced by *Indotritia (Z.) brevisetosa* Niedbala, 2000, nom. nov.

PHTHIRACAROIDEA PERTY, 1841

PHTHIRACARIDAE PERTY, 1841

Atropacarus Ewing, 1917

Atropacarus (Atropacarus) csiszarae (Balogh & Mahunka, 1979)

- Steganacarus csiszarae* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979b: 284, figs 7–9.
Atropacarus (Atropacarus) csiszarae: Niedbala 1992: 236. pl. 255a-i.
Atropacarus csiszarae: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 68.
Atropacarus (Atropacarus) csiszarae: Niedbala 2011: 203, figs 174O–T.
Steganacarus (Atropacarus) csiszarae [sic!]: Murvanidze & Mumladze 2016: 18.
Steganacarus (Atropacarus) csiszarae: Miko 2016: 26.
Atropacarus (Atropacarus) csiszarae: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 56.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) Berlese, 1923

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) andrei (Balogh, 1958)

- Steganacarus andrei* Balogh, 1958: 33.
Hoplophorella andrei: Mahunka 1984a: 130, figs 4–8. comb. nov.
Hoplophorella andrei: Mahunka 1992: 165, figs 18–19.
Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) andrei: Liu & O'Connor 2015: 67, figs 11–23.
Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) vitrinus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 18.
Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) andrei: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 20.
Hoplophorella (Hoplophorella) andrei: Subías 2018: 69.
Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) andrei: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 40.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description there is no Holotype designated. Therefore, all specimens should be considered as syntypes.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) brevipilis (Balogh, 1958)

- Steganacarus brevipilis* Balogh, 1958: 34.
Steganacarus brevipilis: Balogh 1962d: 93.
Hoplophorella (Hoplophorella) brevipilis: Subías 2004: 48.
Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) brevipilis: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 37.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) collaris (Balogh, 1958)

- Steganacarus collaris* Balogh, 1958: 34.
Hoplophorella collaris: Mahunka 1984a: 133, figs 19–23.
Hoplophorella (Hoplophorella) collaris: Subías 2004: 48.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) collaris: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 48.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) collaris: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 40.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren (Mahunka 1984a).

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) lanceosetus*
(Balogh & Mahunka, 1981)**

Steganacarus lanceoseta Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 53, figs 1–6.

Hoplophorella lanceoseta: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 148.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) lanceosetus: Niedbała 1994: 38, figs 250–256.

Hoplophorella (Hoplophorella) lanceoseta: Subías 2004: 49.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) lanceosetus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 18.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) lanceosetus: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 108.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) singularis*
Sellnick, 1959**

Hoplophorella queenslandica Balogh & Mahunka, 1978a: 33, figs 5–8.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) singularis: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 35.

Hoplophorella (Hoplophorella) singularis: Subías 2004: 49.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) singularis: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 181.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. The holotype and several paratypes are deposited in CSIRO, Canberra; another part of paratypes are deposited in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Three paratypes (*H. queenslandica*).

Remarks. According to the documentation in HNHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO Canberra

in 1977.11.28. There is an other vial in the jar of *H. queenslandica* labelled as sp. n. but without further type material marking. Its location is only given as Australia. It may not be part of the type material.

Hoplophthiracarus Jacot, 1933

***Hoplophthiracarus frater* (Balogh, 1958)**

Steganacarus frater Balogh, 1958: 33.

Hoplophthiracarus frater: Mahunka 1984a: 139, figs 23–40. comb. nov.

Hoplophthiracarus (Plonaphacarus) frater: Mahunka 1992: 166. fig. 26.

Hoplophthiracarus frater: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 77.

Hoplophorella (Rhacaplacarus) frater: Subías 2019: 66.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

Remarks. No holotype was designated in the original description. Therefore, all the specimens should be regarded as syntypes.

Notophthiracarus (Notophthiracarus) Ramsay, 1966

***Notophthiracarus (Notophthiracarus) echinus*
(Balogh, 1962)**

Hoplophorella echinus Balogh, 1962e: 146, figs 41–43.

Notophthiracarus (Notophthiracarus) echinus: Mahunka 1990: 204, figs 15–17. comb. nov.

Notophthiracarus echinus: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 37.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Notophthiracarus (Notophthiracarus) pauliani*
(Balogh, 1962)**

Hoplophorella pauliani Balogh, 1962e: 148, figs 44–45.

Notophthiracarus (Notophthiracarus) pauliani: Subías 2004: 52.

Notophthiracarus (?) pauliani: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 150.

Type material in the literature. Holotype l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Notophthiracarus (Notophthiracarus) quietus*
Niedbala, 1989**

Notophthiracarus quietus Niedbala 1989: 24, figs 52–57.

Notophthiracarus gressitti Balogh & Mahunka, 1997: 23, figs 7–11.

Notophthiracarus quietus: Niedbala 2000: 490. syn nov.

Notophthiracarus quietus: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 164.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype in the collection of W. Niedbala.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and six paratypes.

***Notophthiracarus (Notophthiracarus) sinuosus*
Niedbala, 1982**

Phthiracarus sinuosus: Niedbala, 1982: 192, figs 36–54.

Notophthiracarus alpinus Balogh & Mahunka, 1997: 19, figs 1–6.

Notophthiracarus sinuosus: Niedbala 2000: 490. *N. alpinus* syn. nov.

Notophthiracarus sinuosus: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 182.

Hoplophthiracarus (Notophthiracarus) sinuosus: Subías 2020: 77.

Type material in the literature: Holotype and twenty four paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype in the collection of W. Niedbala.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and twenty paratypes (*N. alpinus*).

***Notophthiracarus (Notophthiracarus) zebra*
(Balogh, 1962)**

Hoplophorella zebra Balogh, 1962e: 144, figs 36–40.

Notophthiracarus (Notophthiracarus) zebra: Subías 2004: 52.

Notophthiracarus zebrus: Mahunka 2009a: 92 figs 1–5.

Notophthiracarus zebrus: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 207.

Type material in the literature. Holotype l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. "zebra" is a noun in apposition which does not change with changing gender of its genus (ICZN 31.2.1.)

***Notophthiracarus (Steganacarellus) Mahunka*,
1986**

***Notophthiracarus (Steganacarellus) multituberculatus*
(Balogh & Mahunka, 1966)**

Steganacarus multituberculatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 1, fig. 1.

Notophthiracarus (Steganacarellus) multituberculatus: Subías 2018: 86.

Notophthiracarus multituberculatus: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 128.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes NM, four paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Phthiracarus (Phthiracarus) Perty, 1841

***Phthiracarus (Phthiracarus) baloghorum*
(Mahunka, 1997)**

Phthiracarus insularis Balogh, 1962e: 149, figs 46–49.

Archiphthiracarella insularis: Mahunka 1996a: 20, figs 6–11. comb. nov.

Archiphthiracarella baloghorum Mahunka, 1997b: 86. nom. nov.

Phthiracarus minor Niedbala, 2001: 15, figs 33–39. nom. nov.

Phthiracarus baloghorum: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 30.

Type material in the literature. Holotype l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar.

Deposited in HNHM: Neotype (NO-1533-96).

Remarks. Mahunka (1996b) designated a neotype for the species because the type specimen was destroyed. Also he recognized that *Phthiracarus insularis* Balogh, 1962 is a junior homonym of *Phthiracarus insularis* Jacot, 1934 and

proposed a replacement name *Archiphthiracarella baloghorum* Mahunka, 1997. Later Niedbała (2001) has also provided a replacement name *Phthiracarus minor* Niedbała, 2001 which is therefore a junior synonym of *Ph. baloghorum*.

***Phthiracarus (Phthiracarus) benoiti* Balogh, 1958**

Phthiracarus benoiti Balogh, 1958: 33.
Phthiracarus benoiti: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 31. nomen dubium.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Phthiracarus (Phthiracarus) bryobius* Jacot, 1931**

Archiphthiracarus hungaricus Balogh & Mahunka, 1979b: 288, figs 20–22.
Phthiracarus (Archiphthiracarus) bryobius: Subías 2004: 55.
Phthiracarus hungaricus: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 76.
Phthiracarus bryobius: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 39.
Phthiracarus bryobius: Behan-Pelletier & Lindo 2019: 35.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM (*A. hungaricus*).
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Phthiracarus (Phthiracarus) machadoi* Balogh, 1958**

Phthiracarus machadoi Balogh, 1958: 32.
Phthiracarus machadoi: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 115. nomen dubium
Phthiracarus (Phthiracarus) machadoi: Subías 2020: 82.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Phthiracarus (Phthiracarus) zicmani* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

Phthiracarus feideri Balogh & Mahunka, 1979b: 286, figs 12–14.

Phthiracarus zicmani Balogh & Mahunka, 1983: 152, pl. 82: f–h. nom. nov.
Phthiracarus zicmani: Miko 2016: 26.
Phthiracarus zicmani: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 72.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Phthiracarus (Archiphthiracarus) Balogh & Mahunka, 1979

***Phthiracarus (Archiphthiracarus) peristomaticus* Willmann, 1951**

Phthiracarus peristomaticus Willmann, 1951: 173, fig. 39.
Archiphthiracarus hammeni Balogh & Mahunka, 1979b: 287, figs 18–19.
Archiphthiracarus peristomaticus: Niedbała 1986: 314, (syn. nov. *A. hammeni*).
Phthiracarus peristomaticus: Niedbała 2008: 152.
Phthiracarus peristomaticus: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 86.
Archiphthiracarus variabilis Balogh & Mahunka, 1979b: 287, figs 15–17.
Archiphthiracarus peristomaticus: Niedbała 1986: 314, (syn. nov. *A. variabilis*).
Phthiracarus (Archiphthiracarus) peristomaticus: Subías 2004: 55.
Phthiracarus peristomaticus: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 152.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG (*Archiphthiracarus hammeni*). Holotype and five paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG (*Archiphthiracarus variabilis*).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes (*Archiphthiracarus hammeni*). Holotype and four paratypes (*Archiphthiracarus variabilis*).

***Phthiracarus (Archiphthiracarus) pygmaeus* Balogh, 1958**

Phthiracarus pygmaeus Balogh, 1958: 32.
Archiphthiracarus minutissimus Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 23, figs 1A–B.
Phthiracarus serrula Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 4, fig. 3.
Phthiracarus pygmaeus: Niedbała 1994: 16, figs 37–39. (syn. nov. *Ph. serrula*)

- Archiphthiracarus pygmaeus*: Mahunka 1984a: 127, figs 1–3. comb. nov.
Phthiracarus passimpunctatus P. Balogh, 1988b: 174, figs 7–9.
Phthiracarus pygmaeus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 20.
Phthiracarus (Archiphthiracarus) pygmaeus: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 124.
Phthiracarus pygmaeus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 38.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren (*Phthiracarus pygmaeus*) (Mahunka 1984a). Holotype and thirty five paratypes HNHM, five paratypes MHNG (*Archiphthiracarus minutissimus*). Holotype and one paratype HNHM (*Phthiracarus serrula*). Holotype, no data on deposition (*Phthiracarus passimpunctatus*).

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found (*Phthiracarus pygmaeus*). Holotype and twenty five paratypes (*Archiphthiracarus minutissimus*). Holotype and one paratype (*Phthiracarus serrula*). Holotype (*Phthiracarus passimpunctatus*).

Remarks. For *Phthiracarus pygmaeus* Balogh, 1958 Mahunka (1984a) reports a holotype deposited in the Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren, two paratypes in HNHM and one paratype in MHNG. However, the original description does not mention a holotype, so all specimens should be considered as syntypes. We did not find the two syntypes that should be in HNHM.

***Plonaphacarus* Niedbała, 1986**

***Plonaphacarus insignis* (Balogh & Csiszár, 1963)**

- Neophthiracarus insignis* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 467, figs 3–4.
Plonaphacarus insignis: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 97.
Phthiracarus insignis: Fredes 2018: 40.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

***Plonaphacarus kaszabi* (P. Balogh, 1988)**

- Hoplophthiracarus kaszabi* P. Balogh, 1988b: 172, figs 1–6.

- Plonaphacarus kaszabi*: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 102.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Plonaphacarus machadoi* (Balogh, 1958)**

- Steganacarus machadoi* Balogh, 1958: 33.
Hoplophthiracarus machadoi: Mahunka 1984a: 139, figs 41–46.
Hoplophthiracarus (Plonaphacarus) machadoi: Mahunka 1992: 166, fig. 27.
Rhacaplacarus (Rhacaplacarus) machadoi: Subías 2004: 57.
Rhacaplacarus machadoi: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2009: 742, fig. 3.
Hoplophorella (Rhacaplacarus) machadoi: Subías 2020: 68.
Plonaphacarus machadoi: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 115.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren (Mahunka 1984a).

Deposited in HNHM: Six paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description there is no holotype designated therefore, all the specimens should be considered as syntypes.

***Protophthiracarus* Balogh, 1972**

***Protophthiracarus ephippiger* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1978)**

- Steganacarus ephippiger* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 271, figs 1A–E.
Hoplophorella ephippiger: Mahunka 1984a: 136. comb. nov.
Hoplophorella ephippiger: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1988: 30.
Protophthiracarus ephippiger[!]: Niedbała 1994: 31, figs 167–175.
Notophthiracarus (Besuchetacarus) ephippiger: Subías 2008: 72.
Protophthiracarus ephippiger: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 21.
Protophthiracarus ephippiger: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 69.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Protophthiracarus prominens* (Balogh, 1958)**

Steganacarus prominens Balogh, 1958: 34.

Hoplophorella prominens: Mahunka 1984a: 136, figs 31–35. comb. nov.

Hoplophorella (*Hoplophorella*) *prominens*: Subías 2004: 49.

Protophthiracarus prominens: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 159.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren (Mahunka 1984a).

Deposited in HNHM: Thirty four paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description there is no holotype designated therefore, all specimens should be considered as syntypes.

***Protophthiracarus subsellatus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1977)**

Hoplophorella subsellata Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 1, fig. 1.

Steganacarus galeatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 273, figs 2A–D.

Protophthiracarus subsellatus: Niedbała 1986: 323. (syn. nov. *P. galeatus*)

Hoplophorella galeata: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 148.

Atropacarus (*Hoplophorella*) *galeatus*: Niedbała 1994: 38, figs 243–249.

Protophthiracarus subsellatus: Niedbała 1992: 206, 209A–H.

Protophthiracarus subsellatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 22.

Protophthiracarus subsellatus: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 189.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype ZIL (*Hoplophorella subsellata*). Holotype HNHM (*Steganacarus galeatus*).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes (*Hoplophorella subsellata*). Holotype (*Steganacarus galeatus*).

STEGANACARIDAE NIEDBAŁA, 1986

***Austrophthiracarus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

***Austrophthiracarus andinus* (P. Balogh, 1984)**

Phthirarica andina P. Balogh, 1984a: 31, figs 2A–F.

Neoprotophthiracarus andinus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 148.

Austrophthiracarus andinus: Niedbała 1994: 22, figs 82–91.

Austrophthiracarus andinus: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 20.

Hoplophthiracarus (*Protophthiracarus*) *andinus*: Subías 2020: 78.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and Paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Types, seven specimens.

Remarks. In the original description there is no mention of the number of specimens studied just holotype and paratypes, from the same locality. It appears that no holotype was actually selected and all the material was placed in a vial labelled 'Types', therefore they are syntypes.

***Austrophthiracarus caudatus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1977)**

Phthiracarus caudatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 2, fig. 2.

Notophthiracarus (*Notophthiracarus*) *caudatus*: Subías 2004: 51

Austrophthiracarus caudatus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 148.

Austrophthiracarus caudatus: Niedbała 1994: 23, figs 92–95.

Phthiracarus caudatus: Woas 2002: 283.

Austrophthiracarus caudatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 18.

Austrophthiracarus caudatus: Niedbała *et al.* 2018: 44.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Austrophthiracarus espeletiae* (P. Balogh, 1984)**

Sturmacarus espeletiae P. Balogh, 1984a: 33, figs 3A–F.

Neoprotophthiracarus espeletiae: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 148.

Austrophthiracarus espeletius: Niedbała 1994: 25, figs 106–115.

Hoplophthiracarus (Protophthiracarus) espeletiae: Subías 2020: 79.

Austrophthiracarus espeletiae: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 70.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty seven paratypes, no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Twenty eight types.

Remarks. A holotype is mentioned in the original description, but was not actually selected from the 28 specimens available. Therefore, all the type material represents syntypes.

***Austrophthiracarus feideri* (Balogh & Csiszár, 1963)**

Phthiracarus feideri Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 467, figs 5–6.

Notophthiracarus feideri: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 149.

Austrophthiracarus feideri: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 69.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. There is a note among the museum's files by J. Balogh, written at 1984.05.18. "*I borrowed the holotype of Ph. reideri[feideri] (Balogh & Csiszár, 1963) for revision. As usual, I first examined the vial without opening it. The specimen was not included. Then, with great care, I searched further, piece by piece, all the labels, without success. The vial did not contain the specimen. It must be assumed that it had previously got lost.*"

***Austrophthiracarus hirtus* (P. Balogh, 1984)**

Sturmacarus hirtus P. Balogh, 1984a: 33, figs 4A–F.

Neoprotophthiracarus hirtus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 148.

Austrophthiracarus hirtus: Niedbała 1994: 27, figs 125–129.

Phthiracarus (Neophthiracarus) hirtus: Subías 2020: 87.

Austrophthiracarus hirtus: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 91.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Austrophthiracarus multisetosus* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Austrophthiracarus multisetosus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 286, fig. 3.

Austrophthiracarus multisetosus: Niedbała 1994: 27, figs 130–131.

Austrophthiracarus multisetosus: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 38.

Phthiracarus (Neophthiracarus) multisetosus Subías 2004: 57.

Austrophthiracarus multisetosus: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 128.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype is deposited in the CSIRO Canberra, the paratypes partly in the above institute and partly in the Balogh collection, later to be transferred to the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. According to Colloff & Halliday (1998) the holotype is not in the CSIRO.

***Austrophthiracarus radiatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Austrophthiracarus radiatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1978a: 32, figs 1–4.

Austrophthiracarus similis J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983b: 283, fig. 1.

Austrophthiracarus radiatus: Niedbała 1994: 28. (*A. similis* syn. nov.).

Austrophthiracarus radiatus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1983b: 288, fig. 4.

Austrophthiracarus radiatus: Niedbała 1994: 28, figs 139–157.

Austrophthiracarus radiatus: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 43.

Notophthiracarus (Protophthiracarus) radiatus: Subías 2018: 85.

Austrophthiracarus radiatus: Niedbała & Liu 2018: 164.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and one paratype are

deposited in CSIRO, Canberra; one paratype in HNHM (*Austrophthiracarus radiatus*). Holotype, CSIRO Canberra and two paratypes, Balogh collection, later to be transferred to the HNHM (*Austrophthiracarus similis*).

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype and one vial without any typus marking (*Austrophthiracarus radiatus*). Two paratypes (*Austrophthiracarus similis*).

Remarks. According to Colloff & Halliday (1998) the holotype of *A. radiatus* is not in the CSIRO collection.

***Austrophthiracarus wallworki* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Austrophthiracarus wallworki J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983b: 285, fig. 2.

Austrophthiracarus wallworki: Niedbala 1994: 30, figs 157–166.

Austrophthiracarus wallworki: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 45.

Phthiracarus (Neophthiracarus) wallworki: Subías 2004: 57.

Austrophthiracarus wallworki: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 205.

Type material in the literature. Holotype CSIRO Canberra and two Paratypes Balogh collection.

Deposited in HNHM: One specimen (paratype?)

Remarks. According to Colloff & Halliday (1998) the holotype is not in the CSIRO collection.

***Protophthiracarus* Balogh, 1972**

***Protophthiracarus chilensis* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)**

Notophthiracarus chilensis Balogh & Mahunka, 1967c: 43, figs 1–7.

Protophthiracarus chilensis: Niedbala 1994: 31, figs 167–175.

Notophthiracarus (Protophthiracarus) chilensis: Subías 2004: 53.

Protophthiracarus chilensis: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 45.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype BMNH.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Steganacarus (Rafacarus) Niedbala, 1981

***Steganacarus (Rafacarus) rafalskii* (Niedbala, 1981)**

Neosteganacarus cataracta Balogh & Mahunka, 1992: 166, figs 18–21, 25–26.

Steganacarus (Rafacarus) rafalskii: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 24.

Steganacarus (Rafacarus) rafalskii: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 164.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and thirteen paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and nine paratypes (*N. cataracta*).

Steganacarus (Rhacaplacarus) Niedbala, 1986

***Steganacarus (Rhacaplacarus) baggioi* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1992)**

Mantigueracarus baggioi Balogh & Mahunka, 1992: 161, figs 1–6.

Steganacarus (Rhacaplacarus) baggioi: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 22.

Steganacarus (Rhacaplacarus) baggioi: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 28.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Steganacarus (Rhacaplacarus) perezinigoii* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1992)**

Mantigueracarus perezinigoii Balogh & Mahunka, 1992: 162, figs 7–14.

Steganacarus (Rhacaplacarus) perezinigoii: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 23.

Steganacarus (Rhacaplacarus) perezinigoii: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 152.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Remarks. In the original description there is only a holotype mentioned. Therefore, the specimen labelled "paratype" cannot belong to the type series, even though the locality data are exactly the same.

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) Ewing, 1917

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) angulatus (Balogh & Mahunka, 1992)

Neosteganacarus angulatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1992: 164, figs 15–17, 22–24.

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) angulatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 23.

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) angulatus: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 20.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) hirsutus Pérez-Íñigo, 1974

Steganacarus clavigerus (Berlese, 1904): Pérez-Íñigo 1968: 209, figs 24–25.

Steganacarus perezinigo Balogh & Mahunka, 1979b: 286: figs 10–11. nom. nov.

Steganacarus hirsutus Pérez-Íñigo, 1974: Balogh & Mahunka 1983: 146. (syn. nov. of *S. perezinigo*)

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) hirsutus: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 90.

Remarks. Balogh & Mahunka (1979) recognized that the specimen identified by Pérez-Íñigo (1968) as *S. clavigerus* (Berlese, 1904) represents a different species which they named *S. perezinigo* (erroneously stating that it is nom. nov. instead of sp. nov.). Later, they have synonymized it with *S. hirsutus* Pérez-Íñigo, 1974 (Balogh & Mahunka 1983).

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) relictus (Balogh & Mahunka, 1992)

Neosteganacarus relictus Balogh & Mahunka, 1992: 169, figs 27–30, 38–39.

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) relictus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 24.

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) relictus: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 167.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) sol Balogh, 1958

Steganacarus sol Balogh, 1958: 34.

Steganacarus sol: Balogh 1962d: 93.

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) sol: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 182.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Two vials, one specimen in each with writing "sp. n.", without any other marking.

Remarks. As the information on the holotype and number of paratypes (1 + 1 specimens) are given in a later publication (Balogh 1962d) the two specimens in the two vials should be considered as syntypes.

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) tenuiseta J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986

Steganacarus tenuiseta J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986b: 266, figs 1–5.

Notophthiracarus (Steganacarellus) tenuiseta: Subías 2008: 75.

Steganacarus (?) tenuiseta: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 192.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one (broken) paratype.

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) valeriae (Balogh & Mahunka, 1992)

Nortonacarus valeriae Balogh & Mahunka, 1992: 171, figs 31–37.

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) valeriae: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 24.

Steganacarus (Steganacarus) valeriae: Niedbala & Liu 2018: 200.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Remarks. In the original description there is only a holotype mentioned. Therefore, the specimen labelled as "paratype" does not belong to the type series.

DESMONOMATA WOOLLEY, 1973

NOTHRINA VAN DER HAMMEN, 1982

CROTONIOIDEA THORELL, 1876

CROTONIIDAE THORELL, 1876

***Crotonia* Thorell, 1876**

***Crotonia flagella* (Balogh & Csiszár, 1963)**

Acronothrus flagellatus Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 469, fig. 7.

Crotonia flagellata: Norton & Ermilov 2014: 28.

Crotonia flagellata: Fredes 2018: 43.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Heminothrus* (*Heminothrus*) Berlese, 1913**

***Heminothrus* (*Heminothrus*) *papua* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986)**

Holonothrus papua J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986b: 269, figs 11–14.

Heminothrus (*Heminothrus*) *papua*: Subías 2017: 116.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Heminothrus* (*Platynothrus*) Berlese, 1913**

***Heminothrus* (*Platynothrus*) *leleupi* (Balogh, 1958)**

Platynothrus leleupi Balogh, 1958: 7.

Platynothrus leleupi: Balogh 1962d: 94.

Heminothrus (*Platynothrus*) *leleupi*: Subías 2008: 103.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Heminothrus* (*Platynothrus*) *novaezealandicus* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 200)**

Platynothrus novaezealandicus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 85, pl. 141: 7. "nom. nov." pro *Platynothrus maior* Hammer, 1966 nec. Willmann, 1956.

Platynothrus maior Hammer, 1966, "nom. praeoc." por Willmann, 1956.

Heminothrus (*Platynothrus*) *novaezealandicus*: Subías 2004: 66.

***Heminothrus* (*Platynothrus*) *reductus* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986)**

Platynothrus reductus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 37, figs 7–9.

Heminothrus (*Platynothrus*) *reductus*: Subías 2008: 102.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fourteen paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and nine paratypes.

HERMANNIIDAE SELLNICK, 1928

***Baloghacarus* Mahunka, 1980**

***Baloghacarus australis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

Baloghacarus australis Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 61, figs 32–36.

Baloghacarus australis: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 29.

Baloghacarus australis: Fredes 2018: 52.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Galapagacarus* P. Balogh, 1985**

***Galapagacarus schatzi* P. Balogh, 1985**

Galapagacarus schatzi P. Balogh, 1985d: 31, figs 1A–F.

Galapagacarus schatzi: Baert 2018: 163.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

Remarks. As there is no mention of holotype or paratypes in the original publication therefore, the type material housed in the HNHM should be considered as syntypes.

***Phyllhermannia* Berlese, 1916**

***Phyllhermannia africana* Balogh, 1958**

Phyllhermannia africana Balogh, 1958: 7.

Phyllhermannia africana: Balogh 1962d: 94.

Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) africana: Subías 2004: 70.

Phyllhermannia africana: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 47.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Phyllhermannia angulata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Phyllhermannia angulata Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 2, figs 2–3.

Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) angulata: Subías 2004: 70.

Phyllhermannia angulata: Ermilov, Hugo-Coetzee, Khaustov & Khaustov 2020: 2128.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and thirty five paratypes NM, thirty five paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Twenty nine paratypes (0-105-67/Afr).

***Phyllhermannia exornata* Balogh, 1962**

Phyllhermannia exornata Balogh, 1962e: 127, figs 9–11.

Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) exornata: Subías 2004: 70.

Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) exornata: Mahunka 2009c: 48.

Type material in the literature. Holotype l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Phyllhermannia forsteri* P. Balogh, 1985**

Phyllhermannia forsteri P. Balogh, 1985e: 36, figs 4A–D.

Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) forsteri: Subías 2020: 112.

Phyllhermannia forsteri: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 48.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

***Phyllhermannia falklandica* P. Balogh, 1988**

Phyllhermannia falklandica P. Balogh, 1988a: 111, figs 1–4.

Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) falklandica: Subías 2004: 69.

Phyllhermannia falklandica: Fredes 2018: 45.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Phyllhermannia pauliani* Balogh, 1962**

Phyllhermannia pauliani Balogh, 1962e: 128, figs 12–13.

Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) pauliani: Subías 2004: 70.

Type material in the literature. L'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Phyllhermannia serrata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Phyllhermannia serrata Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 2, figs 4–5.

Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) serrata: Subías 2004: 70.

Phyllhermannia serrata: Ermilov, Hugo-Coetzee, Khaustov & Khaustov 2020: 2129.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, NM.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-109-67/Afr).

***Phyllhermannia similis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967**

Phyllhermannia similis Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 39, pl. I, figs 1–2.

Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) similis: Subías 2004: 70.

Phyllhermannia similis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 49.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-36-67/As).

***Phyllhermannia tenuiseta* P. Balogh, 1988**

Phyllhermannia tenuiseta P. Balogh, 1988b: 176, figs 10–12.

Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) tenuiseta: Subías 2004: 70.

Phyllhermannia tenuiseta: Ermilov, Khaustov & Johar-chi 2020: 880.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description only a holotype is mentioned however, in the collection we have found two vials labelled as "*Phyllhermannia tenuiseta* Paratypes" as well. As no paratypes are mentioned in the original description these specimens (if they belong to this species) cannot be regarded as paratypes.

MALACONOTHRIDAE BERLESE, 1916

***Malaconothrus (Malaconothrus)* Berlese, 1904**

***Malaconothrus (Malaconothrus) lineolatus* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986)**

Trimalaconothrus lineolatus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 37, figs 10–11.

Tyrphonostrus (Tyrphonostrus) lineolatus: Subías 2018: 107.

Malaconothrus lineolatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 49.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and nine paratypes.

***Malaconothrus (Malaconothrus) machadoi* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Malaconothrus punctulatus Balogh, 1958: 5.

Malaconothrus machadoi Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 257. nom. nov. pro *M. punctulatus* Balogh, 1958 not *M. punctulatus* Hammer, 1952.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Seven paratypes.

Remarks. There is no holotype designated in the original description and no details of the type material. The seven specimens found and labelled "Paratypes" are therefore syntypes.

***Malaconothrus (Malaconothrus) neoplumosus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Malaconothrus neoplumosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 256, fig. 3.

Tyrphonostrus (Cristonostrus) neoplumosus: Subías 2014: 102.

Tyrphonostrus (Cristonostrus) neoplumosus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 26.

Malaconothrus neoplumosus: Miko 2019: 354.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Malaconothrus (Malaconothrus) pilosellus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Malaconothrus pilosellus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 257, fig. 4.

Malaconothrus (Malaconothrus) pilosellus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 25.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Malaconothrus (Malaconothrus) rohri*
P. Balogh, 1997**

Malaconothrus rohri P. Balogh, 1997: 21, figs 1–2.

Malaconothrus rohri J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 77, pl. 133: 4–5. sp. n.

Tyrphonostrus (Cristonostrus) rohri: Subías 2014: 103.

Tyrpochthonius rohri: Ermilov & Smit 2017: 795.

Malaconothrus rohri: Miko 2020: 354.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and sixteen paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material found.

Remarks. In J. Balogh & P. Balogh (2002) it was mistakenly reported as a new species.

***Malaconothrus (Trimalaconothrus) Berlese,*
1916**

***Malaconothrus (Trimalaconothrus) africanus*
(Balogh, 1958)**

Trimalaconothrus africanus Balogh, 1958: 5.

Malaconothrus (Trimalaconothrus) africanus: Subías 2014: 98.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Eight paratypes (0-1129-68/Afr).

Remarks. There is no holotype designated in the original description and also no details of the type material. The eight specimens found and labelled "Paratypes" consequently represent syntypes.

***Malaconothrus (Trimalaconothrus) multipilosus*
J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002 *nomen nudum***

Trimalaconothrus multipilosus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 80, pl. 137: 6–7.

Trimalaconothrus multipilosus: Schatz 2006: 224.

Type material in the literature. No type material was specified and no deposition was mentioned in the original description.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. This name is not available under ICZN because it does not comply with Art. 16.4.1 ("explicit fixation of a holotype, or syntypes, for the nominal taxon") and 16.4.2 ("where the holotype or syntypes are extant specimens, by a statement of intent that they will be (or are) deposited in a collection and a statement indicating the name and location of that collection").

***Malaconothrus (Trimalaconothrus) oppositus*
(P. Balogh, 1997)**

Trimalaconothrus oppositus P. Balogh, 1997: 22, figs 3–4.

Trimalaconothrus oppositus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 80, pl. 137: 4–5.

Malaconothrus (Trimalaconothrus) oppositus: Oliveira et al. 2017: 26.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. In J. Balogh & P. Balogh (2002) it was erroneously reported as a new species.

***Malaconothrus (Trimalaconothrus) planus*
(Balogh, 1958)**

Trimalaconothrus planus Balogh, 1958: 6.

Malaconothrus (Trimalaconothrus) planatus: Subías 2014: 98.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Malaconothrus (Trimalaconothrus) reticulatus*
(Balogh, 1958)**

Trimalaconothrus reticulatus Balogh, 1958: 5.

Malaconothrus (Trimalaconothrus) reticulatus: Subías 2014: 98.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Five paratypes.

Remarks. There is no holotype in the original description and no details of the type material. The five specimens found and labelled "Paratypes" are therefore syntypes.

***Malaconothrus (Trimalaconothrus) similis*
(Balogh, 1958)**

Trimalaconothrus similis Balogh, 1958: 6.
Malaconothrus (Trimalaconothrus) similis: Subías
2014: 98.

Type material in the literature. Collections du
Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Malaconothrus (Trimalaconothrus) soror*
(Balogh, 1958)**

Trimalaconothrus soror Balogh, 1958: 6.
Malaconothrus (Trimalaconothrus) soror: Subías
2014: 98.

Type material in the literature. Collections du
Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Tyrphonothrus (Tyrphonothrus) Knülle, 1957*
Tyrphonothrus (Tyrphonothrus) humeratus
(P. Balogh, 1997)**

Trimalaconothrus humeratus P. Balogh, 1997: 24, figs
7–8.
Trimalaconothrus humeratus J. Balogh & P. Balogh,
2002: 78, pl. 135: 2–3.
Tyrphonothrus (Tyrphonothrus) humeratus: Oliveira *et*
al. 2017: 26.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No
data on deposition.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.
Remarks. In J. Balogh & P. Balogh (2002) it
was erroneously reported as a new species.

***Tyrphonothrus (Tyrphonothrus) itatiaiae*
(P. Balogh, 1997)**

Trimalaconothrus itatiaiae P. Balogh, 1997: 22, figs 5–
6.
Trimalaconothrus itatiaiae J. Balogh & P. Balogh,
2002: 78, pl. 134: 11–12.
Tyrphonothrus (Tyrphonothrus) itatiaiae: Oliveira *et*
al. 2017: 26.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and
three paratypes. No data on deposition.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.
Remarks. In J. Balogh & P. Balogh (2002) it
was erroneously reported as a new species.

***Tyrphonothrus (Cristonothrus) Subías, 2004*
Tyrphonothrus (Cristonothrus) subrasus
(Balogh, 1962)**

Malaconothrus subrasus Balogh, 1962e: 125, figs 7–8.
Tyrphonothrus (Cristonothrus) subrasus: Subías 2014:
103.

Type material in the literature. Holotype l’In-
stitut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar,
and two paratypes with no data on deposition.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Tyrphonothrus (Cristonothrus) valeriae* (J. Balogh
& P. Balogh, 2002) *nomen nudum***

Malaconothrus valeriae J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002:
76.
Malaconothrus valeriae: Schatz 2006: 224.
Tyrphonothrus (Cristonothrus) valeriae: Subías: 2014:
103.

Type material in the literature. No type ma-
terial and deposition is mentioned in the original
description.

Deposited in HNHM: No material found.
Remarks. This name is not available according
to ICZN because does not fulfill Art. 16.4.1
("explicit fixation of a holotype, or syntypes, for
the nominal taxon") and 16.4.2 ("where the holo-
type or syntypes are extant specimens, by a state-
ment of intent that they will be (or are) deposited
in a collection and a statement indicating the
name and location of that collection").

***Tyrphonothrus (Cristonothrus) vilhenarum*
(Balogh, 1958)**

Malaconothrus vilhenarum Balogh, 1958: 5.
Tyrphonothrus (Cristonothrus) vilhenarum: Subías
2014: 103.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

NANHERMANIIDAE SELLNICK, 1928

***Cyrthermannia* Balogh, 1958**

***Cyrthermannia florens* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Cyrthermannia florens Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 26, figs 2D–E.

Cyrthermannia florens: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 27.

Cyrthermannia florens: Miko 2019: 361.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and six paratypes.

***Cyrthermannia stellata* Balogh, 1970**

Cyrthermannia stellata Balogh, 1970b: 294, pl. I. figs 2–3.

Cyrthermannia stellata: P. Balogh 1988b: 172.

Cyrthermannia stellata: Miko 2019: 361.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. "The holotype and part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM."

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Cyrthermannia tuberculata* Balogh, 1958**

Cyrthermannia tuberculata Balogh, 1958: 3.

Cyrthermannia tuberculata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 215.

Cyrthermannia tuberculata: Miko 2019: 362.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Masthermannia* Berlese, 1913**

***Masthermannia extrema* (Balogh, 1958)**

Posthermannia extrema Balogh, 1958: 3.

Masthermannia extrema: Subías 2004: 68.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Masthermannia grandjeani* (Balogh, 1958)**

Posthermannia grandjeani Balogh, 1958: 2.

Masthermannia grandjeani: Subías 2004: 68. sp. inq.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Fourteen paratypes.

Remarks. There is no holotype in the original description and no details of the type material. The 14 specimens found and labelled "Paratypes" are therefore syntypes.

***Nanhermannia* Berlese, 1913**

***Nanhermannia* (*Nanhermannia*) *domrowi* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Nanhermannia domrowi Balogh & Mahunka, 1978a: 35, figs 9–11.

Nanhermannia domrowi: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 74.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and a part of paratypes are deposited in CSIRO, Canberra; another part of paratypes are deposited HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. According to the documents in HNHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO Canberra in 1977.11.28 however, Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it.

***Nanhermannia* (*Nanhermannia*) *fenneri* Balogh, 1970**

Nanhermannia fenneri Balogh, 1970b: 294, pl. I. fig. 1.

Nanhermannia (*Nanhermannia*) *fenneri*: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 61.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty three paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and twenty one paratypes.

***Nanhermannia (Nanhermannia) gladiata*
P. Balogh, 1985**

Nanhermannia galadiata[!] P. Balogh, 1985a: 83, figs 2A–B.

Nanhermannia gladiata: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 74.

Type material in the literature. Holotype CSIRO Canberra, and one paratype with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. According to Colloff & Halliday (1998) the holotype is in the collection of HNHM but, we did not find it. According to the museum's postal registry the holotype was sent to the CSIRO on 1994.12.05.

***Nanhermannia (Nanhermannia) milloti* Balogh,
1961**

Nanhermannia milloti Balogh, 1961d: 7, figs 1–2.

Nanhermannia milloti: Mahunka 1997a: 118.

Nanhermannia milloti: Mahunka 2002: 10.

Nanhermannia milloti: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 61.

Nanhermannia milloti: Mahunka 2009a: 96, figs 10–11.

Nanhermannia milloti: Mahunka 2009b: 339.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Seven paratypes (0-1125-68/Afr)

***Nanhermannia (Nanhermannia) quadridentata*
Balogh, 1958**

Nanhermannia quadridentata Balogh, 1958: 2.

Nanhermannia quadridentata: Balogh 1961a: 67, figs 1–3.

Type material in the literature. No data on the type material, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

Remarks. There is no holotype designated in the original publication and no information on the

number of specimens examined. The holotype and ten paratypes reported by Balogh (1961a) should be considered as syntypes.

***Nanhermannia (Nanhermannia) tenuisetosa*
P. Balogh, 1985**

Nanhermannia tenuisetosa P. Balogh, 1985a: 81, figs 1A–B.

Nanhermannia tenuisetosa: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 75.

Type material in the literature. Holotype CSIRO Canberra.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Notohermannia* P. Balogh, 1985**

***Notohermannia obtusa* P. Balogh, 1985**

Notohermannia obtusa P. Balogh, 1985a: 84, figs 3A–F.

Notohermannia obtusa: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 75.

Type material in the literature. Holotype CSIRO Canberra, and seven paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. We have found the holotype in the HNHM collection but not the seven paratypes.

NOTHRIDAE BERLESE, 1896

***Nothrus* Koch, 1835**

***Nothrus angolensis* Balogh, 1958**

Nothrus angolensis Balogh, 1958: 7.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Nothrus basilewskyi* Balogh, 1958**

Nothrus basilewskyi Balogh, 1958: 6.

Nothrus basilewskyi: Balogh 1962d: 94.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. Balogh (1962d) reported a holotype and a paratype, but these were not designated in the original publication, so both are syntypes.

***Nothrus becki* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

Nothrus becki Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 60, figs 26–31.

Nothrus becki: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 27.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Nothrus flagellum* Csiszár, 1961**

Nothrus flagellum Csiszár, 1961a: 349, fig. 9.

Nothrus flagellum: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 62.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Nothrus leleupi* Balogh, 1958**

Nothrus leleupi Balogh, 1958: 6.

Nothrus leleupi: Balogh 1962d: 94.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One vial labelled as sp. nov. but without type marking.

Remarks. Balogh (1962d) reported a holotype and three paratypes, but these were not designated in the original publication and are therefore syntypes.

TRHYPOCHTHONIIDAE WILLMANN, 1931

***Afronothrus* Wallwork, 1961**

***Afronothrus incisivus* Wallwork, 1961**

Afronothrus incisivus neotropicus Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 2, figs 1A–C.

Afronothrus incisivus neotropicus: Mahunka 1998: 841.

Afronothrus incisivus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 28.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fifty paratypes. The Holotype (except where no paratypes representing the species are available) are deposited in the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba, while the paratypes and the exceptions mentioned above are in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and twenty five paratypes.

***Allonothrus* (*Allonothrus*) Hammen, 1953**

***Allonothrus* (*Allonothrus*) *neotropicus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Allonothrus neotropicus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 256, figs 1–2.

Allonothrus (*Allonothrus*) *neotropicus*: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 28.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eleven Paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Allonothrus* (*Pseudonothrus*) Balogh, 1958**

***Allonothrus* (*Pseudonothrus*) *hirtus* (Balogh, 1958)**

Pseudonothrus hirtus Balogh, 1958: 7.

Allonothrus (*Pseudonothrus*) *hirtus*: Subías 2004: 59.

Allonothrus (*Pseudonothrus*) *hirtus*: Ermilov & Mary 2019: 634.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Nine paratypes.

Remarks. There is no holotype designated in the original publication therefore, the specimens in the HNHM are syntypes.

***Trhypochthonius* Berlese, 1904**

***Trhypochthonius africanus* Balogh, 1958**

Trhypochthonius africanus Balogh, 1958: 4.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Trhypochthonius javanus* Csiszár, 1961**

Trhypochthonius javanus Csiszár, 1961a: 349, fig. 10.
Trhypochthonius javanus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 65.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

BRACHYPYLINA HULL, 1918

HERMANNIELLOIDEA GRANDJEAN, 1934

HERMANNIELLIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1934

***Hermanniella* Berlese, 1908**

***Hermanniella madagascarensis* Balogh, 1962**

Hermanniella madagascarensis Balogh, 1962b: 419, figs 1–4.

Hermanniella madagascarensis: Mahunka 2002b: 10.
Hermanniella madagascarensis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 96, pl. 154, figs 9–11.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two Paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Hermanniella congoensis* Balogh, 1958**

Hermanniella congoensis Balogh, 1958: 23.
Hermanniella congoensis: Ermilov & Rybalov 2018: 1835.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. There is one specimen in HNHM labelled as sp. n. but without type marking.

***Hermanniella humilis* Balogh, 1962**

Hermanniella humilis Balogh, 1962d: 98, figs 8–11.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Musée Royal de l’Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Hermannobates* Hammer, 1961**

***Hermannobates flagelliseti* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

Hermannobates flagelliseti Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 63, figs 37–40.

Hermannobates flagelliseti: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 29.
Hermannobates flagelliseti: Fredes 2018: 52.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

PLASMOBATIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1961

***Orbiculobates* Grandjean, 1961**

***Orbiculobates australis* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963**

Orbiculobates australis Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 469, fig. 8.

Solenozetes australis: Subías 2004: 71.
Orbiculobates australis: Fredes 2018: 53.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three Paratypes. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Plasmobates* Grandjean, 1929**

***Plasmobates africanus* Balogh, 1958**

Plasmobates africanus Balogh, 1958: 23.
Plasmobates africanus: Fernandez & Theron 2016: 2. sp. inq.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Plasmobates machadoi* Balogh, 1958**

Plasmobates machadoi Balogh, 1958: 23.
Plasmobates machadoi: Fernandez & Theron 2016: 2. sp. inq.
Plasmobates machadoi: Subías 2020: 116. sp. inq.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, á Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Plasmobates minor* Balogh, 1958**

Plasmobates minor Balogh, 1958: 23.

Plasmobates africanus: Fernandez & Theron 2016: 1. sp. inq.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, á Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Solenozetes Grandjean*, 1931**

***Solenozetes flagellatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Solenozetes flagellatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 33, fig. 1.

Solenozetes flagellatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 30.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes Deposited in HNHM: Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of. J. Aoki, E. Piffil, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

PLATEREMAEOIDEA TRÄGÅRDH, 1926

GYMNODAMAEIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1954

***Austrodamaeus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

***Austrodamaeus elegantulus* (Hammer, 1958)**

Gymnodamaeus elegantulus Hammer, 1958: 39, fig. 40.

Allodamaeus trisetosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 259, figs 5–6.

Austrodamaeus rimosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 64, figs 41–44.

Aleurodamaeus elegantulus: Fredes 2018: 58.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG

(*Austrodamaeus rimosus*). No data on deposition (*Allodamaeus trisetosus*).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes (*Austrodamaeus rimosus*). Holotype (*Allodamaeus trisetosus*).

***Jacotella* Banks, 1947**

***Jacotella ornatus* (Balogh & Csiszár, 1963)**

Allodamaeus ornatus Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 471, figs 11–12.

Allodamaeus tuberculatus Aoki & Fujikawa, 1971: 113. nom. nov.

Allodameus ornatus: Paschoal 1987: 348.

Jacotella ornata: Fredes 2018: 58.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1124-68/D-Am).

LICNODAMAEIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1954

***Flammaeremaeus* Balogh, 1968**

***Flammaeremaeus gressitti* Balogh, 1968**

Flammaeremaeus gressitti Balogh, 1968: 261, pl. I. 3–4.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Hexachaetoniella* Paschoal, 1987**

***Hexachaetoniella dispersa* (P. Balogh, 1985)**

Pedrocortesella dispersa P. Balogh, 1985b: 55, figs 4A–D.

Hexachaetoniella dispersa: Hunt 1996b: 296, figs 6–7.

Hexachaetoniella dispersa: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 87.

Hexachaetoniella dispersa: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 58.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Licnodamaeus* Grandjean, 1931**

***Licnodamaeus fissurataus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1965)**

Pedrocortesella fissurata Balogh & Mahunka, 1965: 453, figs 3–4.

Licnodamaeus fissuratus: Bayartogtokh 2010: 44, 34A–B.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Licnodamaeus granulatus* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963**

Licnodamaeus granulatus Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 471, figs 9–10.

Licnodamaeus granulatus: Fredes 2018: 59.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five Paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1130-68/D-Am) and one paratype.

***Novazelandiella* Paschoal, 1989**

***Novazelandiella queenslandica* (P. Balogh, 1985)**

Pedrocortesella queenslandica P. Balogh, 1985b: 56, figs 5A–C.

Labiogena queenslandica: Hunt, 1996b: 311, figs 1A,B, 5–7.

Labiogena queenslandica: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 78.

Novazelandiella queenslandica: Subías 2004: 74.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Pedrocortesella* Hammer, 1961**

***Pedrocortesella hardyi* Balogh, 1968**

Pedrocortesella hardyi Balogh, 1968: 262, pl. II. figs 9–10.

Pedrocortesella hardyi: Aoki 1984: 133, fig. 3. comb. n.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Pedrocortesella inaequalis* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1965)**

Pedrocortesella inaequalis Balogh & Mahunka, 1965: 455, figs 5–6.

Licneremaeus inaequalis: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 225.

Pedrocortesella inaequalis: Bayartogtokh 2010: 43, figs 33A–B–B.

Pedrocortesella inaequalis: Ermilov *et al.* 2021c: 702.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-950-68/As) and four paratypes (0-951-68/As).

***Pedrocortesella propinqua* P. Balogh, 1985**

Pedrocortesella propinqua P. Balogh, 1985b: 51, figs 2A–D.

Pheroliodes propinqua: Woas 1992: 9: 144.

Pedrocortesella propinqua: Hunt 1996a: 272, figs 10A–C.

Pedrocortesella propinqua: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 93.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Pedrocortesella temperata* P. Balogh, 1985**

Pedrocortesella temperata P. Balogh, 1985b: 51, figs 3A–D.

Pedrocortesella propinqua: Hunt 1996a: 279, figs 1B, 43–45.

Pedrocortesella temperata: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 95.

Pedrocortesella temperata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 59.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Eleven specimens in one vial labelled as "Type material".

PHEROLIODIDAE PASCHOAL, 1987

Nooliodes Paschoal, 1989

Nooliodes franzi (Balogh, 1966)

Pedrocortesia franzi Balogh, 1966: 70, fig. 1.

Pedrocortesia franzi: Paschoal 1987: 371.

Nooliodes franzi: Subías 2004: 73.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Nooliodes glaber (Balogh, 1962)

Plateremaeus glaber Balogh, 1962b: 421, figs 7–8.

Nooliodes glaber: Paschoal 1989: 180.

Nooliodes glaber: Mahunka 1997a: 118.

Nooliodes glaber: Mahunka 2002b: 10.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nine paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Pheroliodes Grandjean, 1931

Pheroliodes africanus (Balogh, 1966)

Pedrocortesia africana Balogh, 1966: 70, fig. 2.

Pedrocortesella pletzenae J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 108, pl. 171: 7. nom. nov. pro *Pedrocortesella africana* (Balogh, 1966) nec. Pletzen, 1963.

Pheroliodes africanus: Subías 2004: 73.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. J. Balogh & P. Balogh (2002) provided a replacement *Pedrocortesella pletzenae* nom. nov. for *Pedrocortesia africana* Balogh, 1966 regarding congeneric with *Pedrocortesella africana* Pletzen, 1963. However, at present *Pe. africana* Balogh, 1966 belongs to the genus *Pheroloides* Grandjean, 1931 (Subías 2004) therefore *Pheroloides africanus* is the valid name (ICZN Art. 59.2, 4)

Pheroliodes longiceps Balogh & Mahunka, 1966

Pheroliodes[!] (?) *longiceps* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 4, figs 6–7.

Pheroliodes longiceps: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 59.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes NM, two paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Pheroliodes vermicularis (Balogh, 1970)

Pedrocortesia vermicularis Balogh, 1970b: 295, pl. I. Figs 4–5.

Pedrocortesia vermicularis: Paschoal 1987: 371.

Pheroliodes vermicularis: Subías 2004: 74.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

PLATEREMAEIDAE TRÄGÅRDH, 1926

Lopheremaeus Paschoal, 1988

Lopheremaeus mirabilis (Csiszár, 1962)

Plateremaeus mirabilis Csiszár, 1962b: 283, figs 1–3.

Lopheremaeus mirabilis: Paschoal 1987: 349.

Lopheremaeus mirabilis: Murvanidze & Mumladze 2016: 26.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, and one paratype with deposition not

exactly stated ("The paratypes are either in the collections of the authors or in the two museums indicated above" i.e. HNHM or NHM Sofia).

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Lopheremaeus tunicatus* (Balogh, 1958)**

Gymnodamaeus tunicatus Balogh, 1958: 9.

Plateremaeus tunicatus: Balogh 1962: 421.

Plateremaeus tunicatus: Paschoal 1987: 354.

Lopheremaeus tunicatus: Subías 2004: 73.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Three paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description no holotype is designated and no data on there type material is given. Therefore these three "Paratypes" should be considered as part of the syntype series.

Plateremaeus Berlese, 1908

***Plateremaeus berlesei* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Plateremaeus berlesei Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 275, figs 4A–B.

Plateremaeus berlesei: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 32.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

***Plateremaeus costulatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Plateremaeus costulatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 276, figs 5A–B.

Plateremaeus costulatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 32.

Plateremaeus costulatus: Fredes 2018: 60.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Plateremaeus latus* P. Balogh, 1988**

Plateremaeus latus P. Balogh, 1988b: 176, figs 13–15.

Plateremaeus latus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 880.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Plateremaeus novemsetosus* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Plateremaeus novemsetosus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 81, figs 1A–C.

Plateremaeus novemsetosus: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 81.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. The holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1994.

***Platyamerus peculiaris* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Platyamerus peculiaris J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983b: 299, fig. 12.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype is deposited in CSIRO Canberra, the paratypes partly in the above institute and partly in the Balogh Collection, later to be transferred to the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. The holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1994.

***Paralopheremaeus* Paschoal, 1987**

***Paralopheremaeus legendrei* (Balogh, 1962)**

Plateremaeus legendrei Balogh, 1962b: 421, figs 5–6.

Plateremaeus legendrei: P. Balogh 1988b: 172.

Paralopheremaeus legendrei: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 880.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

DAMAEOIDEA BERLESE, 1896

DAMAEIDAE BERLESE, 1896

Metabelba (Metabelba) Grandjean, 1936

Metabelba (Metabelba) angolensis Balogh, 1958

Metabelba angolensis Balogh, 1958: 8.

Non *Metabelba (Neobelba) glabriseta* Mahunka, 1982:

Subías 2004: 147.

Metabelba angolensis: Miko *et al.* 2014: 1. spec. inc. sed.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. Miko *et al.* (2014) reviewed the African *Metabelba* species and redescribed *M. (P.) glabriseta* on the basis of the type material. They have rejected the synonymy of *M. angolensis* Balogh, 1958 and *M. glabriseta* Mahunka, 1982 proposed by Subías (2004) because the descriptions of the five *Metabelba* species in Balogh (1958) are rather brief and the lack of figures makes it impossible to relate them to other *Metabelba* species. Therefore, they considered all the five species of Balogh (1958) *M. benoiti*, *M. tanganyikensis*, *M. heteropoda*, *M. horida* and *M. angolensis* as *species incertae sedis*.

Metabelba (Metabelba) benoiti Balogh, 1958ü

Metabelba benoiti Balogh, 1958: 9.

Metabelba benoiti: Balogh 1962d: 94.

Metabelba benoiti: Miko *et al.* 2014: 1. spec. inc. sed.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Metabelba (Metabelba) heteropoda Balogh, 1958

Metabelba heteropoda Balogh, 1958: 8.

Metabelba heteropoda: Miko *et al.* 2014: 1. spec. inc. sed.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Metabelba (Metabelba) horrida Balogh, 1958

Metabelba horrida Balogh, 1958: 8.

Metabelba horrida: Miko *et al.* 2014: 1. spec. inc. sed.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Metabelba (Metabelba) orientalis Balogh & Mahunka, 1967

Metabelba orientalis Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 40, pl. I. Figs 3–4.

Metabelba orientalis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 59.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Metabelba (Metabelba) tanganyikensis Balogh, 1958

Metabelba tanganyikensis Balogh, 1958: 8.

Metabelba tanganyikensis: Balogh 1962d: 94.

Metabelba tanganyikensis: Miko *et al.* 2014: 1. spec. inc. sed.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Parabelbella Bulanova-Zachvatkina, 1967

Parabelbella flagellata (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)

Metabelba flagellata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 33, fig. 2.

Parabelbella (Parabelbella) flagellata: Subías 2012: 141.

Allobelba (Parabelbella) flagellata: Subías 2020: 128.

Parabelbella flagellata: Ermilov & Ryabinin 2020: 373.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajsiki and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype

CEPHEOIDEA BERLESE, 1896

Reticulocephus Vasiliu & Čalugăr, 1977

Reticulocephus decoui Vasiliu & Čalugăr, 1977

Cepheus (Cubacephus) lobatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 37, fig. 2.

Reticulocephus decoui Vasiliu & Čalugăr, 1977: 241, figs 1–2.

Reticulocephus decoui: Subías 2004: 84.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype?

Remarks. In the collection we have found a vial labelled as *Cepheus ornatus* Holotype. There is no such species described and the locality data are the same as for *Cepheus lobatus*.

ANDEREMAEIDAE BALOGH, 1972

Anderemaeus Hammer, 1958

Anderemaeus australiensis J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983

Anderemaeus australiensis J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983b: 301 fig. 13.

Anderemaeus australiensis: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 97.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. The holotype is deposited in CSIRO Canberra, the paratypes partly in the above institute and partly in the Balogh Collection, later to be transferred to the HNHM.

HNHM: Five paratypes.

Remarks. The holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra on 05.12.1994.

Anderemaeus capitatus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985

Anderemaeus capitatus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985a: 44, figs 1A–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Anderemaeus hidasii P. Balogh, 1995

Anderemaeus hidasii P. Balogh, 1995: 4, figs 1–3.

Anderemaeus hidasii: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 36.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and forty five paratypes Balogh Collection, Budapest.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Anderemaeus sturmi J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985

Anderemaeus sturmi J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985a: 44, figs 2A–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

CEPHEIDAE BERLESE, 1896

Cepheus C. L. Koch, 1835

Cepheus transversalis Balogh, 1958

Cepheus transversalis Balogh, 1958: 19.

Cepheus transversalis: Balogh 1962d: 94.

Cepheus transversalis: Ermilov, Sidorchuk & Rybalov 2012: 38.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Oribatodes Banks, 1895

Oribatodes crenulatus Csiszár, 1962

Oribatodes crenulatus Csiszár, 1962: 284, figs 4–5.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, four Paratypes, with deposition not exactly stated. "The paratypes are in the collections of the author or in the HNHM."

Deposited in HNHM: One specimen labelled as "sp. n." but without typus marking. Holotype?

Sadocepheus Aoki, 1965

***Sadocepheus breviseta* (P. Balogh, 1986)**

Hamotegaeus breviseta P. Balogh, 1986b: 52, figs 4–6.
Sadocepheus breviseta: Ermilov 2020: 877.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Sadocepheus franzi* (P. Balogh, 1986)**

Hamotegaeus franzi P. Balogh, 1986b: 55, figs 7–9.
Sadocepheus franzi: Ermilov 2020: 877.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Sadocepheus granulatus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Hamotegaeus[!] *granulatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 4, figs 6–7.

Sadocepheus granulatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 32.
Sadocepheus granulatus: Ermilov 2020: 877.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-509-68/D-Am).

***Sadocepheus longiseta* (P. Balogh, 1986)**

Hamotegaeus longiseta P. Balogh, 1986b: 52, figs 1–3.
Sadocepheus longiseta: Ermilov 2020: 877.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Sadocepheus serratus* (Balogh, 1970)**

Compactozetes serratus Balogh, 1970b: 296, pl. II. figs 10–11.

Sadocepheus serratus: Mahunka 1987b: 788.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. The Holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

EUTEGEIDAE BALOGH, 1965

Atalotegaeus Luxton, 1988

***Atalotegaeus mensarosi* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983)**

Eutegaeus mensarosi J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 82, figs 2 A–C.

Atalotegaeus mensarosi: Luxton 1988: 82, fig. 5B.

Atalotegaeus mensarosi: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 97.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eighteen paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Four paratypes.

Remarks. According to Colloff & Halliday (1998) the holotype is in the collection of CSIRIO, Canberra.

Birotegaeus Luxton, 1988

***Birotegaeus biroi* (Balogh, 1970)**

Eutegaeus biroi Balogh, 1970b: 296, pl. II. fig. 12.

Birotegaeus biroi: Luxton 1988: 82.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nine paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and seven paratypes.

Dudichella Balogh, 1970

***Dudichella membranigera* Balogh, 1970**

Dudichella membranigera Balogh, 1970a: 36, figs 1–2.

Dudichella membranigera: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1986b: 271.

Dudichella membranigera: Ermilov, Khaustov & Jocharchi 2020: 880.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Eutegaeus* Berlese, 1916**

***Eutegaeus soror* P. Balogh, 1985**

Eutegaeus soror P. Balogh, 1985a: 86, fig. 4.
Eutegaeus soror: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 98.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Neoeutegaeus* Aoki, 1964**

***Neoeutegaeus phyllophorus* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Neoeutegaeus phyllophorus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983b: 291, fig. 6.
Neoeutegaeus phyllophorus: Luxton 1988: 77, fig. 2A.
Neoeutegaeus phyllophorus: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 98.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. The holotype is deposited in CSIRO Canberra, the paratypes partly in the above institute and partly in the Balogh Collection, later to be transferred to the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Four paratypes.

Remarks. The holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1994.

***Neseutegaeus* Woolley, 1965**

***Neseutegaeus denticulatus* P. Balogh, 1988**

Neseutegaeus denticulatus P. Balogh, 1988b: 180, figs 16–8.
Neseutegaeus denticulatus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Jocharchi 2020: 880.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Neseutegaeus monteithi* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Neseutegaeus monteithi J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983b: 293, fig. 7.

Neseutegaeus monteithi: Luxton 1988: 79, fig. 3C.

Neseutegaeus monteithi: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 99.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. The holotype is deposited in CSIRO Canberra, the paratypes partly in the above institute and partly in the Balogh Collection, later to be transferred to the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Five "types".

Remarks. The holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra on 05.12.1994. In the collection there are five specimens with type marking. Possibly they are the paratypes.

***Pareutegaeus* Wooley, 1965**

***Pareutegaeus pulcher* (Balogh & Csiszár, 1963)**

Eutegaeus pulcher Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 472, figs 15–16.
Pareutegaeus pulcher: Fredes 2018: 63.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Porrhotegaeus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

***Porrhotegaeus herminae* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Porrhotegaeus herminae J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 305, fig. 3.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three Paratypes, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Four syntypes.

Remarks. Although the original description states that the species is described on the ba-

sis of a holotype and three paratypes, in the collection we have found a vial with the label of "types" containing four specimens. They should therefore be considered as syntypes.

***Porrhotegaeus ornatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Porrhotegaeus ornatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966c: 557, figs 5–6.

Porrhotegaeus ornatus: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 100.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Austral Museum.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. According to the documentation in HNHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1995 but Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it there.

***Salvus Özdikmen*, 2008**

***Salvus incertus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1977)**

Pterobates incertus Balogh & Mahunka, 1977b: 248, fig. 1.

Salvus incertus: Özdikmen 2008: 697.

Brazilobates incertus: Koçak & Kemal 2008: 5.

Salvus incertus: Subías 2009: 143.

Brazilobates incertus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 32.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

MICROTEGEIDAE BALOGH, 1972

***Microtegeus* Berlese, 1916**

***Microtegeus borhidii* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Microtegeus[!] *borhidii* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 3, figs 2A–C.

Microtegeus[!] *borhidi*[!]: Aoki 1974: 136, fig. 6.

Microtegeus borhidii: Mahunka 1998: 842.

Microtegeus borhidii: Schatz 2006: 231.

Microtegeus borhidii: Baert 2018: 262.

Microtegeus borhidii: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 69.

Microtegeus borhidii: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 61.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. "The holotype (except where no paratypes representing the species are available) is deposited in the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba, while the paratypes and the exceptions mentioned above are in HNHM."

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Microtegeus ceylonicus* Balogh, 1970**

Microtegeus ceylonicus Balogh, 1970a: 35, fig. 3.

Microtegeus ceylonicus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Microtegeus cornutus* Balogh, 1970**

Microtegeus cornutus Balogh, 1970a: 35, fig. 4.

Microtegeus cornutus: P. Balogh 1988b: 172.

Microtegeus cornutus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 61.

Microtegeus cornutus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature: Holotype and two paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one vial of paratypes.

Remarks. It appears that there are no specimens in the paratype vial.

***Microtegeus foveolatus* Balogh, 1968**

Microtegeus foveolatus Balogh, 1968: 261, pl. I. figs 5–6.

Microtegeus foveolatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 69.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. The Holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Microtegeus hirashimai* Balogh, 1970**

Microtegeus[!] *hirashimai* Balogh, 1970b: 295, pl. I.
Figs 6–7.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. The Holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

***Microtegeus humeratus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Microtegeus[!] *humeratus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 4, figs 3A–D.

Microtegeus humeratus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 69.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and sixteen paratypes. "The holotype (except where no paratypes representing the species are available) is deposited in the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba, while the paratypes and the exceptions mentioned above are in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and ten paratypes.

***Microtegeus labyrinthicus* Balogh, 1968**

Microtegeus labyrinthicus Balogh, 1968: 261, pl. II.
figs 7–8.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Microtegeus quadrisetosus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

Microtegeus quadrisetosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 8, fig. 6.

Microtegeus quadrisetosus: P. Balogh 1988b: 172.

Microtegeus quadrisetosus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 33.
Microtegeus quadrisetosus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype ZIL.

Deposited in HNHM: Five paratypes.

***Microtegeus similis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Microtegeus[!] *similis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 26,
figs 3A–B.

Microtegeus similis: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 33.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty seven paratypes HNHM, three paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and twenty four paratypes.

NOSYBEIDAE MAHUNKA, 1994

***Topalia* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963**

***Topalia problematica* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963**

Topalia problematica Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 477,
figs 27–28.

Topalia problematica: Fredes 2018: 106.

Topalia problematica: Colloff 2019: 292.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1137-68/D-Am) and one paratype.

POLYPTEROZETOIDEA GRANDJEAN, 1959

NODOCEPHEIDAE PIFFL, 1972

***Nodocepheus* Hammer, 1958**

***Nodocepheus hammerae* Balogh, 1961**

Nodocepheus hammerae Balogh, 1961c: 5, figs 6–7.

Nodocepheus hammerae: Subias 2004: 85.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

MICROZETOIDEA GRANDJEAN, 1936

MICROZETIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1936

***Acanthozetes* Balogh, 1958**

***Acanthozetes platypterus* Balogh, 1958**

Acanthozetes platypterus Balogh, 1958: 29.
Acanthozetes platypterus: Balogh 1960b: 105, figs 37–40.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes (0-1064-68/Afr), one paratype (0-192-68/Afr).

Remarks. No holotype is designated in the original publication. Later Balogh (1960b) reported one holotype and two paratypes. In the collection there are two vials with one and two specimens labelled "paratype", but all these specimens should be considered as syntypes.

Acaroceras (Acaroceras) Grandjean, 1936

***Acaroceras (Acaroceras) becki* Balogh, 1962**

Acaroceras becki Balogh, 1962a: 413, fig. 13.
Acaroceras (Acaroceras) becki: Ermilov & Tolstikov 2015: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1075-68/D-Am) and one paratype (0-1076-68/D-Am).

***Acaroceras (Acaroceras) cavernosus* Balogh, 1962**

Acaroceras cavernosus Balogh, 1962a: 415, fig. 15.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Acaroceras (Acaroceras) furcatus* Balogh, 1962**

Acaroceras furcatus Balogh, 1962a: 415, fig. 16.
Acaroceras (Acaroceras) furcatus: Ermilov & Tolstikov 2015: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1077-68/D-Am).

***Acaroceras (Acaroceras) hamifer* Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

Acaroceras hamifer Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 12, fig. 9.

Acaroceras (Acaroceras) hamifer: Ermilov & Tolstikov 2015: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Acaroceras (Acaroceras) index* Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

Acaroceras index Balogh & Mahunka, 1977b: 249, fig. 2A–B.

Acaroceras (Acaroceras) index: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 33.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Acaroceras (Acaroceras) porosus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

Acaroceras porosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 13, fig. 10.

Acaroceras (Acaroceras) porosus: Ermilov & Tolstikov 2015: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Acaroceras (Acaroceras) pseudofurcatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Acaroceras pseudofurcatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 259, fig. 7.

Acaroceras (Acaroceras) pseudofurcatus: Ermilov & Tolstikov 2015: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Acaroceras (Acaroceras) pugio* Balogh, 1962**

Acaroceras pugio Balogh, 1962a: 413, fig. 12.
Acaroceras pugio: Schatz 2006: 233.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1078-68/D-Am).

***Acaroceras (Acaroceras) schalleri* Balogh, 1962**

Acaroceras schalleri Balogh, 1962a: 415, fig. 14.
Acaroceras (Acaroceras) schalleri: Ermilov & Tolstikov 2015: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two Paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1073-68/D-Am) and one paratype (0-1074-68/D-Am).

***Acaroceras (Acaroceras) similis* Balogh, 1962**

Acaroceras similis Balogh, 1962a: 413, fig. 11.
Acaroceras (Acaroceras) similis: Ermilov & Tolstikov 2015: 68.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1079-68/D-Am).

***Anakingia* Hammer, 1961**

***Anakingia reticulata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Anakingia reticulata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 260.
Anakingia reticulata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 33.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Berlesezetes* Mahunka, 1980**

***Berlesezetes africanus* (Balogh, 1958)**

Microzetes africanus Balogh, 1958: 28.
Berlesezetes ornatissimus ornatissimus (Berlese, 1913): Subías 2004: 87.
Berlesezetes africanus: Mahunka 2009b: 339.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1091-68/Afr) and an other paratype without reg. no.

Remarks. In the original description there is no information on the type material, therefore both specimens are part of the syntypes series.

***Berlesezetes brazilozetoides* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

Berlesezetes brazilozetoides Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 70, figs 54–57.
Berlesezetes brazilozetoides: Akrami 2015: 484.
Berlesezetes brazilozetoides: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 33.
Berlesezetes brazilozetoides: Fredes 2018: 64.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and sixteen paratypes HNHM, six paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and twenty six paratypes.

***Brazilozetes* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Brazilozetes flagellatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Brazilozetes flagellatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 36, fig. 6.
Brazilozetes flagellatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 34.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. "Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of. J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey."

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Brazilozetes fusiger* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

Brazilozetes fusiger Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 71, figs 58–61.

Brazilozetes fusiger: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 34.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Brazilozetes phaseolus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Brazilozetes phaseolus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 36, fig. 7.

Brazilozetes phaseolus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 34.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. "Holotype and the greater part of the Paratypes HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of. J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey."

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Calozetes* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Calozetes monticola* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Calozetes monticola Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 262, figs 10–11.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Cosmozetes (Cosmozetes)* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Cosmozetes (Cosmozetes) cubanus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Cosmozetes cubanus Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 7, figs 5A–D.

Cosmozetes cubanus: Mahunka 2005: 292.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and sixteen paratypes. "The holotype (except where no paratypes representing the species are available) are deposited in the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba, while the paratypes and the exceptions mentioned above are in HNHM."

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and fourteen paratypes.

***Cosmozetes (Cosmozetes) ecuadoriensis* P. Balogh, 1989**

Cosmozetes ecuadoriensis P. Balogh, 1989: 19, figs 9–10.

Cosmozetes ecuadoriensis: Mahunka 2005: 292.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Three type specimens in one vial without clearly distinguishing the holotype, so all represent syntypes.

***Cosmozetes (Cosmozetes) negroi* Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

Cosmozetes negroi Balogh & Mahunka, 1977b: 251, fig. 2C–E.

Cosmozetes negroi: Mahunka 2005: 292.

Cosmozetes (Cosmozetes) negroi: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 34.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Cosmozetes (Cosmozetes) rohri* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Cosmozetes rohri Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 38, fig. 10.

Cosmozetes rohri: Balogh & Mahunka 1977b: 252, fig. 2F–G.

Cosmozetes rohri: Mahunka 2005: 292.

Cosmozetes rohri: Ermilov & Smit 2017: 797.

Cosmozetes (Cosmozetes) rohri: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 34.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Cosmozetes (Cosmozetes) striatissimus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Cosmozetes striatissimus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 38, figs 8–9.

Cosmozetes striatissimus: Mahunka 2005: 292.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. "Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes HNHM. Some Paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey."

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Cosmozetes (Cosmozetes) vermiculatus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1980)**

Rhopalozetes vermiculatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 27, figs 3C–D.

Cosmozetes vermiculatus: Mahunka 2005: 292.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

Cosmozetes (Magoebazetes) Engelbrecht, 1972

***Cosmozetes (Magoebazetes) reticulatus* (Balogh, 1962)**

Rhopalozetes reticulatus Balogh, 1962a: 407, fig. 2.

Cosmozetes (Magoebazetes) reticulatus: Subías 2004: 88.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nine paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1086-68/D-Am).

***Dinozetes* Balogh, 1962**

***Dinozetes latissimus* Balogh, 1962**

Dinozetes latissimus Balogh, 1962a: 409.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1067-68/D-Am).

***Dinozetes mirabilis* Balogh, 1962**

Dinozetes mirabilis Balogh, 1962a: 409.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1093-68/D-Am) and four paratypes (0-1094-68/D-Am).

Remarks. The original description is based on a single holotype. Therefore the four specimens labelled as "paratypes" have no nomenclatural value.

***Fusozetes* Balogh, 1972**

***Fusozetes fusiger* (Balogh, 1962)**

Rhopalozetes fusiger Balogh, 1962a: 407, fig. 3.

Fusozetes fusiger: Balogh 1972: 149, pl. 18: 15.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Hymenozetes* Balogh, 1964**

***Hymenozetes mirabilis* Balogh, 1962**

Hymenozetes mirabilis Balogh, 1962e: 142, figs 32–33.

Hymenozetes mirabilis: Mahunka 2009a: 118.

Type material in the literature. Holotype l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Licnozetes (Licnozetes) Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

***Licnozetes (Licnozetes) flabellatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Licnozetes flabellatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 262, fig. 12.

Licnozetes (Licnozetes) flabellatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 34.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Licnozetes (Licnozetes) multiareolatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Licnozetes multiareolatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 38, fig. 13.

Licnozetes (Licnozetes) multiareolatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 34.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-577-68/D-Am).

Licnozetes (Undulozetes) Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Licnozetes (Undulozetes) granulatus (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)

Undulozetes granulatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 40, fig. 14.

Licnozetes (Undulozetes) granulatus: Subías 2004: 89.

Licnozetes (Undulozetes) granulatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 34.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. "Holotype and the greater part of the Paratypes HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of. J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley."

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

Licnozetes (Undulozetes) margaritatus (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)

Undulozetes (?) margaritatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 42, fig. 15.

Licnozetes (Undulozetes) margaritatus: Subías 2004: 89.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes. "Holotype and the greater part of the Paratypes HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of. J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley."

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

Microzetes (Megazetes) Balogh, 1970

Microzetes (Megazetes) micropterus (Balogh, 1959)

Megazetes micropterus Balogh, 1959b: 106, figs 47–49.

Microzetes (Megazetes) micropterus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 71.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Microzetes (Stylozetes) Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Microzetes (Stylozetes) discrepans (Balogh, 1962)

Nellacarus discrepans Balogh, 1962a: 417, fig. 19.

Microzetes (Stylozetes) discrepans: Ermilov & Corpuz-Raros 2016: 580.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Microzetes (Stylozetes) physoseta (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)

Stylozetes physoseta Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 39, fig. 3.

Microzetes (Stylozetes) physoseta: Subías 2004: 89.

Microzetes (Stylozetes) physoseta: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 35.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty two paratypes. "Holotype and the greater part of the Paratypes HNHM. Some Paratypes are deposited in the collections of. J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley."

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and fourteen paratypes.

Microzetes (Stylozetes) processus (Balogh & Mahunka, 1977)

Stylozetes processus Balogh & Mahunka, 1977b: 253, fig. 4.

Microzetes (Stylozetes) spinosus: Subías 2004: 89.

Microzetes (Stylozetes) processus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 35.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description only one paratype is mentioned.

Microzetes (Stylozetes) spinosus (Balogh & Mahunka, 1981)

Stylozetes spinosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 73, figs 62–65.

Microzetes (Stylozetes) spinosus: Subías 2004: 89.

Microzetes (Stylozetes) spinosus: Ermilov & Corpuz-Raros 2016: 580.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Mystacozetes Balogh, 1962

Mystacozetes nervosus (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)

Acaroceras nervosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 4, figs 8–9.

Mystacozetes nervosus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1988: 122.

Mystacozetes nervosus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 35.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffil, A. Rajsiki and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-510-68/D-Am).

Remarks. The vial labelled holotype contains two specimens. As in the early days the type specimens of J. Balogh (and sometimes S. Mahunka) were often not separated but put together in one vial, these two specimens may be syntypes.

Mystacozetes ornatus Balogh, 1962

Mystacozetes ornatus Balogh, 1962a: 411, fig. 10.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Orthozetes Balogh, 1962

Orthozetes depilatus Balogh, 1968

Orthozetes depilatus Balogh, 1968: 264, pl. III. figs 15–16.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

Orthozetes dispar Balogh, 1962

Orthozetes dispar Balogh, 1962a: 411, fig. 9.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Orthozetes papuanus Balogh, 1968

Orthozetes papuanus Balogh, 1968: 263, pl. III. Figs 13–14.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Oxyzetes Balogh, 1958

Oxyzetes pectiniger Balogh, 1958

Oxyzetes pectiniger Balogh, 1958: 28.

Oxyzetes pectiniger: Balogh 1960b: 104, figs 34–36.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes (0-1057-68/Afr, 0-1089-68/Afr).

Remarks. The original publication did not mention a holotype, but later Balogh (1960b) reported a holotype and three paratypes. All these specimens should be considered as syntypes.

Papuazetes Balogh, 1968

Papuazetes insignis Balogh, 1968

Papuazetes insignis Balogh, 1968: 263, pl. figs 11–12.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty four paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Plumozetes Balogh, 1972

Plumozetes plumifer (Balogh & Mahunka, 1968)

Rhopalozetes plumifer Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 320, figs 2–3.

Plumozetes plumifer: Balogh 1972: 150.

Plumozetes plumifer: Fredes 2018: 65.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty nine paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited also in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-381-68/D-Am), twenty two paratypes (0-382-68/D-Am) and three paratypes (0-383-68/D-Am).

Protozetes Balogh, 1962

Protozetes capitulum Balogh, 1962

Protozetes capitulum Balogh, 1962a: 407, fig. 1.

Protozetes capitulum: Mahunka 2005: 299, figs 12–13.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1069-68/D-Am).

Protozetes digitifer alticola P. Balogh, 1989

Protozetes digitifer alticola P. Balogh, 1989: 22, figs 2, 13–14.

Protozetes digitifer alticola: Mahunka 2005: 299.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Three type specimens.

Remarks. It appears that the holotype and the two paratypes were not separated and therefore represent syntypes.

Protozetes longicornis P. Balogh, 1989

Protozetes longicornis P. Balogh, 1989: 21, figs 11–12.

Protozetes longicornis: Mahunka 2005: 299.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Three type specimens.

Remarks. It appears that the holotype and the two paratypes were not separated and therefore represent syntypes.

Rhopalozetes Balogh, 1964

Rhopalozetes brazilianus (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)

Austrozetes brazilianus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 34, fig. 5.

Austrozetes brazilianus: Balogh & Mahunka 1977b: 251.

Rhopalozetes brazilianus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 35.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Rhopalozetes canagaratnami Balogh, 1970

Rhopalozetes canagaratnami Balogh, 1970a: 36, fig. 5.

Rhopalozetes canagaratnami: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Rhopalozetes milloti* Balogh, 1962**

Rhopalozetes milloti Balogh, 1962e: 143, figs 34–35.

Type material in the literature. Holotype l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar, and three paratypes, with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Rhopalozetes panabokkei* Balogh, 1970**

Rhopalozetes panabokkei Balogh, 1970: 38, fig. 7.
Rhopalozetes panabokkei: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Rhopalozetes topali* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963**

Rhopalozetes topali Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 472, figs 13–14.
Rhopalozetes topali: Fredes 2018: 65.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Rugozetes* Balogh, 1960**

***Rugozetes gladiator* Balogh, 1962**

Rugozetes gladiator Balogh, 1962a: 415, fig. 17.
Rugozetes gladiator: Balogh & Mahunka 1969b: 39.
Rugozetes gladiator: Balogh & Mahunka 1977b: 253, figs 3A–C.
Rugozetes gladiator: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 35.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Rugozetes grandjeani* (Balogh, 1959)**

Microzetes grandjeani Balogh, 1959b: 106, figs 45–46.
Rugozetes grandjeani: Balogh 1962f: 48.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren and two paratypes Musée de Dundo and ELTE.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1090-68/Afr) and an other paratype without registration number.

***Schalleria* Balogh, 1962**

***Schalleria bacillifera* Balogh, 1962**

Schalleria bacillifera Balogh, 1962a: 409, fig 7.
Schalleria bacillifera: Ermilov, Sandmann & Maraun 2013: 207.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1059-68/D-Am) and one paratype (0-1066-68/D-Am).

***Schalleria cruciata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Schalleria cruciata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 39, fig. 11.
Schalleria cruciata: Ermilov, Sandmann & Maraun 2013: 207.
Schalleria cruciata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 35.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Schalleria forceps* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Schalleria forceps Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 29, figs 4A–B.
Schalleria forceps: Ermilov, Sandmann & Maraun 2013: 207.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and ten paratypes.

***Schalleria incurvata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Schalleria incurvata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 5, figs 10–11.

Schalleria incurvata: Ermilov, Sandmann & Maraun 2013: 207.

Schalleria incurvata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 35.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-512-68/D-Am) and one paratype (0-513-68/D-Am).

***Schalleria latilamellata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Schalleria latilamellata Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 29, figs 4C–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and eight paratypes.

***Schalleria martii* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Schalleria martii Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 8, figs 6A–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seventeen paratypes. The holotype (except where no paratypes representing the species are available) are deposited in the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba, while the paratypes and the exceptions mentioned above are in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and ten paratypes.

***Schalleria monoceros* Balogh, 1962**

Schalleria monoceros Balogh, 1962a: 410, fig. 8.

Schalleria monoceros: Ermilov, Sandmann & Maraun 2013: 207.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1082-68 /D-Am/), one paratype (0-1083-68 /D-Am/).

***Schalleria ramosa* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Schalleria ramosa Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 263, fig. 13.

Schalleria ramosa: Balogh & Mahunka 1977b: 253, figs 3D–E.

Schalleria ramosa: Ermilov, Sandmann & Maraun 2013: 207.

Schalleria ramosa: Ermilov, Niedbała & Friedrich 2016: 63.

Schalleria ramosa: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 36.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype. HNHM.

***Schalleria sexcornuta* Balogh, 1962**

Schalleria sexcornuta Balogh, 1962a: 409, fig. 6.

Schalleria sexcornuta: Ermilov, Sandmann & Maraun 2013: 207.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1080-68/D-Am) and two paratypes (0-1081-68/D-Am).

***Schalleria trifurcata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

Schalleria trifurcata Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 38, fig. 3.

Schalleria trifurcata: Ermilov, Sandmann & Maraun 2013: 207.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Schizozetes* Balogh, 1962**

***Schizozetes quadrilineatus* Balogh, 1962**

Schizozetes quadrilineatus Balogh, 1962a: 417, fig. 18.

Schizozetes quadrilineatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 36.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1068/D-Am).

***Schizozetes similis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Schizozetes similis Balogh & Mahunka, 1966b: 26, figs 2–3.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nine paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-87-67/Afr) and four paratypes (0-88-67/Afr).

***Sturmozetes* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1992**

***Sturmozetes longisetus* (P. Balogh, 1989)**

Gymnozetes longisetus P. Balogh, 1989: 19, figs 6–8.
Sturmozetes longisetus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 161.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Two type specimens in one vial.

Remarks. The holotype and paratype are in one vial and indistinguishable, therefore they represent syntypes.

***Sturmozetes marginatus* (P. Balogh, 1984)**

Gymnozetes marginatus P. Balogh, 1984b: 316, figs 1–2.
Sturmozetes marginatus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 161, figs 335C–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

Remarks. The vial labelled holotype contains two specimens.

***Szentivanyella* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Szentivanyella latilamellata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Szentivanyiella[!] *latilamellata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 40, fig. 12.

Szentivanyella latilamellata: Subías 2004: 91.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. Holotype and the greater part of the

paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Trichozetes* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

***Trichozetes neutrichus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Trichozetes neutrichus Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 31, figs 5A–B.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Vermacarus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

***Vermacarus longissimus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Vermacarus longissimus Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 32, figs 5C–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

AMEROIDEA BULANOVA-ZACHVATKINA, 1957

AMERIDAE BULANOVA-ZACHVATKINA, 1957

***Andesamerus* Hammer, 1962**

***Andesamerus novaezealandiae* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Andesamerus novaezealandiae J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986b: 272, figs 18–19.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found under this name but see Remarks.

Remarks. We have found in the collection a vial labelled as *Hymenobelba novaezealandiae* holotype and one paratype, leg. Foster 2. As there is no species is described under the name *Hymenobelba novaezealandiae* and the collector

is the same as for *Andesamerus novaezealandiae* these *Hymenobelba novaezealandiae* specimens most likely represent the holotype and paratype of *Andesamerus novaezealandiae*.

Haplamerus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1992

***Haplamerus annulus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1966)**

Hymenobelba annulus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 6, figs 10–11.

Haplamerus annulus: Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 190.

Type material in the literature. Holotype NM, and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

***Haplamerus coarctata* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1966)**

Hymenobelba coarctata Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 4, figs 8–9.

Haplamerus coarctata: Mahunka 2010: 65.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and thirty paratypes NM, thirty paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Twenty seven paratypes (0-95-67/Afr).

***Hymenobelba* Balogh, 1962**

***Hymenobelba domahidyi* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Hymenobelba domahidyi J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 83, figs 3A–D.

Hymenobelba domahidyi: Luxton 1988: 428.

Hymenobelba domahidyi: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 104.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eleven paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Nine paratypes.

Remarks. According to the HNHM records, the holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1994.

***Hymenobelba ypsilon* Balogh, 1962**

Hymenobelba ypsilon Balogh, 1962b: 423, figs 9–11.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Pteramerus* Balogh, 1964**

***Pteramerus draco* Balogh, 1962**

Pteramerus draco Balogh, 1962e: 136, figs 26–28.

Type material in the literature. l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar. No information on the number of type material given.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. As no size variation is given in the description, it is possible that only a holotype was available, found in the collection.

BASILOBELBIDAE BALOGH, 1961

***Xiphobelba* Csiszár, 1961**

***Xiphobelba hammani* Csiszár, 1961**

Xiphobelba hammani Csiszár, 1961a: 353, figs 20–22.

Xiphobelba hammani: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 74.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

CALEREMAEIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1965

***Cristeremaeus* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963**

***Cristeremaeus humeratus* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963**

Cristeremaeus humeratus Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 477, figs 30–31.

Cristeremaeus cf. *humeratus*: Akrami 2015: 481.

Cristeremaeus humeratus: Fredes 2018: 62.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twelve paratypes. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1159-68/Afr).

Remarks. The status of this holotype is uncertain. The reg. No. refers to an African species, but *C. humeratus* was described from South Ame-

rica. There is another vial containing five specimens with the same species name and locality, but without type markings. Expert examination is required to determine the status of the intended holotype and the other five specimens.

Epiereumus Berlese, 1916

***Epiereumus granulatus andicola*
(P. Balogh, 1988)**

Carabodoides granulatus andicola P. Balogh, 1988c: 326, figs 6–10.

Epiereumus granulatus andicola: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 60.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Epiereumus braziliensis* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Carabodoides braziliensis Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 50, fig. 39.

Epiereumus braziliensis: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 235.

Epiereumus braziliensis: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 36.

Epiereumus braziliensis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 74.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Epiereumus granulatus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1979)**

Carabodoides granulatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 45, fig. 8.

Epiereumus granulatus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 235.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Epiereumus laticeps* (Balogh, 1963)**

Carabodoides laticeps Balogh, 1963: 36, figs 2–3.

Epiereumus laticeps: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 235.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren and two paratypes.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Epiereumus longicarinatus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1978)**

Carabodoides longicarinatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 284, figs 12A–B.

Epiereumus longicarinatus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 235.

Epiereumus longicarinatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 36.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Epiereumus longiseta* (P. Balogh, 1988)**

Carabodoides longiseta P. Balogh, 1988c: 325, figs 1–5.

Epiereumus longiseta: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 60.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Luxtoneremaeus* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985**

***Luxtoneremaeus forsteri* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985)**

Anderemaeus forsteri J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985a: 48, figs 3A–D.

Luxtoneremaeus forsteri: J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1992: 185.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

Yungaseremaeus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Yungaseremaeus longisetosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Yungaseremaeus longisetosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 54, fig. 46.
Yungaseremaeus longisetosus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1985a: 48, figs 4A.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

DAMAEOLIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1965

Caudamaeolus P. Balogh, 1988

Caudamaeolus petalus P. Balogh, 1988

Caudamaeolus petalus P. Balogh, 1988c: 329, figs 11–17.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nine paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and seven paratypes.

Damaeolus Paoli, 1908

Damaeolus bregetovae Csiszár, 1962

Damaeolus bregetovae Csiszár, 1962b: 286, figs 12–13.
Damaeolus bregetovae: Toluk & Akin 2017: 297, figs 4 a–c.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, and two paratypes with no deposition exactly stated. „The paratypes are in the collections of the author or in the HNHM.”

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. In the label the authors are Balogh & Csiszár, 1962 but in the publication it is only Csiszár.

Damaeolus ornatissimus Csiszár, 1962

Damaeolus ornatissimus Csiszár, 1962b: 287, figs 14–15.
Damaeolus ornatissimus: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 139.

Damaeolus ornatissimus: Murvanidze & Mumladze 2016: 33.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, ten paratypes with no deposition specified. „The paratypes are in the collections of the author or in the HNHM.”

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Fosseremus Grandjean, 1954

Fosseremus laciniatus (Berlese, 1905)

Fosseremaeus africanus Balogh, 1958: 10.
Fosseremaeus laciniatus: Subías 2004: 103.

Type material in the literature. No information on the number of type specimens given in the original publication. Deposited in the Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. The specimen labelled as paratype should be regarded as one of the syntypes.

Gressittolus Balogh, 1970

Gressittolus marginatus Balogh, 1970

Gressittolus marginatus Balogh, 1970b: 297, pl. II. figs 8–9.
Gressittolus marginatus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1986b: 272.
Gressittolus marginatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 75.
Gressittolus marginatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 66.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and a paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype a paratype.

EREMOBELBIDAE BALOGH, 1961

Eremobelba Berlese, 1908

Eremobelba bellicosa Balogh & Mahunka, 1967

Eremobelba bellicosa Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 41, pl. I. Figs 5–6.

Eremobelba bellicosa: Ermilov, Kalúz & Martens 2014: 60.

Eremobelba bellicosa: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 67.

Eremobelba bellicosa: Ermilov & Martens 2021: 44(2): 231.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Eremobelba bisulcata* Balogh, 1958**

Eremobelba bisulcata Balogh, 1958: 11.

Eremobelba bisulcata: Ermilov & Khaustov 2018: 158.

Type material in the literature. No information on the number of type specimens given in the original publication. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Three paratypes.

Remarks. The specimens labelled as paratypes should be considered as syntypes.

***Eremobelba breviseta* Balogh, 1968**

Eremobelba breviseta Balogh, 1968: 265, pl. IV. figs 21–22.

Eremobelba breviseta: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 75.

Eremobelba breviseta: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Eremobelba brevispathulata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Eremobelba brevispathulata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 43, fig. 17.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the

paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-585-68/D-Am) and one paratype (0-586-68/D-Am).

***Eremobelba esposi* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Eremobelba esposi Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 263, fig. 16.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight Paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Eremobelba mahunkai* Balogh, 1968**

Eremobelba mahunkai Balogh, 1968: 265, pl. IV. figs 19–20.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Eremobelba obscura* Balogh, 1958**

Eremobelba obscura Balogh, 1958: 11.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Eremobelba ornata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Eremobelba ornata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 43, fig. 18.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-567-68/D-Am) and five paratypes (0-588-68/D-Am).

***Eremobelba perrugosa* Balogh & Mahunka, 1968**

Eremobelba perrugosa Balogh & Mahunka, 1968b: 341, figs 1–2.

Eremobelba perrugosa: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 76.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, one paratype NSMT.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Eremobelba pulchella* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Eremobelba pulchella Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 43, fig. 19.

Eremobelba pulchella: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 37.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-589-68/D-Am), and one paratype (0-590-68/D-Am), another paratype without detailed locality.

***Eremobelba zicsii* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Eremobelba zicsii Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 43, fig. 20.

Eremobelba zicsii: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 37.

Eremobelba zicsii: Fredes 2018: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-591-68/D-Am) and seven paratypes (0-592-68/D-Am).

EREMULIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1965

***Eremulus* Berlese, 1908**

***Eremulus adami* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Eremulus adami Balogh & Mahunka, 1966b: 26, figs 4–5.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-85-67/Afr) and one paratype (0-86-67/Afr).

***Eremulus africanus* Balogh, 1958**

Eremulus africanus Balogh, 1958: 12.

Eremulus africanus: Balogh 1962d: 94.

Eremulus africanus: Ermilov & Hugo-Coetzee 2012: 569. spec. inq.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Eremulus lanceocrinus* Balogh, 1958**

Eremulus lanceocrinus Balogh, 1958: 11.

Eremulus lanceocrinus: Ermilov & Hugo-Coetzee 2012: 569. spec. inq.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Eremulus rigidisetus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Eremulus rigidisetus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 264, figs 14–15.

Eremulus rigidisetus: Ermilov, Niedbała & Friedrich 2016: 63.

Eremulus rigidisetus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 38.

Eremulus rigidisetus: Fredes 2018: 68.

Eremulus rigidisetus: Baert 2018: 139.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Eremulus translamellatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Eremulus translamellatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 5, fig. 14.

Eremulus translamellatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 38.

Eremulus cf. translamellata: Baert 2018: 138. species.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nine paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of

the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Pseuderemulus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1968**

***Pseuderemulus gladiator* Balogh & Mahunka, 1968**

Pseuderemulus gladiator Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 321, figs 4–5.

Pseuderemulus gladiator: Fredes 2018: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fifty five paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited also in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and Dr. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-370-68/D-Am), nine paratypes (0-371-68/D-Am), thirty five paratypes (0-372-68/D-Am), five paratypes (0-373-68/D-Am), and one paratype (0-374-68/D-Am).

***Reteremulus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

***Reteremulus aciculatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Reteremulus aciculatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 8, figs 12–13.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes NM, three paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

***Reteremulus aciculatus papuanus* Balogh, 1968**

Reteremulus aciculatus papuanus Balogh, 1968: 266, pl. V, figs 23–24.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

HETEROBELBIDAE BALOGH, 1961

***Haplobelba* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Haplobelba simplex* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Haplobelba simplex Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 44, figs 21–22.

Haplobelba simplex: Ermilov, Niedbała & Friedrich 2016: 63.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-594-68/D-Am) and one labelled with sp. n.

Remarks. The specimen labelled as sp. n. has the same locality data as of the paratype. It possibly represents the holotype.

***Heterobelba* Berlese, 1913**

***Heterobelba africana* Balogh, 1958**

Heterobelba africana Balogh, 1958: 9.

Heterobelba africana: Balogh 1962d: 94.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1147-68/Afr).

Remarks. As there are no holotype and paratypes designated in the original description, the specimen labelled as paratype should be considered as one of the syntypes.

***Heterobelba spinosissima* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

Heterobelba spinosissima Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 74, figs 66–71.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

HUNGAROBELBIDAE MIKO & TRAVÉ, 1996

***Hungarobelba* Balogh, 1943**

***Hungarobelba visnyai* (Balogh, 1938)**

Belba Visnyai Balogh, 1938: 84, figs 1–2.

Hungarobelba Visnyai: Balogh 1943: 40, tab. VIII, fig. 6.

Hungarobelba visnyai: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 129.

Hungarobelba visnyai: Schatz 2018: 32.

Type material in the literature. Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. The specimen is mounted on a microscope slide.

OXYAMERIDAE AOKI, 1965

***Oxyamerus* Aoki, 1965**

***Oxyamerus aokii* Balogh, 1968**

Oxyamerus aokii Balogh, 1968: 267, pl. V, figs 25–26.

Oxyamerus aokii: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 78.

Oxyamerus aokii: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 71.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

***Oxyamerus latyrostris* Balogh, 1968**

Oxyamerus latyrostris Balogh, 1968: 267, pl. V, figs 27–28.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

RHYNCHORIBATIDAE BALOGH, 1961

***Eurhynchoribates* (*Eurhynchoribates*) Miko, 2016**

***Eurhynchoribates* (*Eurhynchoribates*) *acutus* (Balogh, 1958)**

Rhynchoribates acutus Balogh, 1958: 15.

Eurhynchoribates (*Eurhynchoribates*) *acutus*: Miko 2016: 133.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Eurhynchoribates* (*Eurhynchoribates*) *montanus* (Balogh, 1962)**

Rhynchoribates montanus Balogh, 1962d: 103, fig. 24.

Eurhynchoribates (*Eurhynchoribates*) *montanus*: Miko 2016: 133.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Musée Royal de l’Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Eurhynchoribates* (*Eurhynchoribates*) *robinsoni* (Balogh, 1962)**

Rhynchoribates robinsoni Balogh, 1962b: 425, figs 23–24.

Eurhynchoribates (*Eurhynchoribates*) *robinsoni*: Mikó 2016: 133.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Eurhynchoribates* (*Eurhynchoribates*) *serratus* (Balogh, 1958)**

Rhynchoribates serratus Balogh, 1958: 15.

Eurhynchoribates (*Eurhynchoribates*) *serratus*: Miko 2016: 133.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Eurhynchoribates (Eurhynchoribates)*
subaequalis (Balogh, 1962)**

Rhynchoribates subaequalis Balogh, 1962b: 425, figs 21–22.

Eurhynchoribates (Eurhynchoribates) subaequalis: Miko 2016: 133.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype; no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Eurhynchoribates (Orinchobates) Miko,*
*Ermilov & Corpuz-Raros, 2017***

***Eurhynchoribates (Orinchobates) orientalis*
(Balogh, 1970)**

Rhynchoribates orientalis Balogh, 1970a: 54, fig. 37.

Eurhynchoribates (Orinchobates) orientalis: Miko, Ermilov & Corpuz-Raros 2017: 126.

Eurhynchoribates (Orinchobates) orientalis: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Rhynchoribates (Rhynchoribatodes) Miko, 2016

***Rhynchoribates (Rhynchoribatodes) dilatatus*
Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Rhynchoribates dilatatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 56, fig. 51.

Rhynchoribates (Rhynchoribatodes) dilatatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 39.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Rhynchoribates (Rhynchoribates)*
Grandjean, 1929**

***Rhynchoribates (Rhynchoribatodes)*
ecuadoriensis P. Balogh, 1988**

Rhynchoribates ecuadoriensis P. Balogh, 1988c: 331, figs 27–29.

Rhynchoribates (Rhynchoribatodes) ecuadoriensis: Miko 2016: 135.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Rhynchoribates (Rhynchoribates) edentatus*
Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Rhynchoribates edentatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 57, fig. 50.

Rhynchoribates edentatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 38.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Rhynchoribates (Rhynchoribates) insignis*
Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Rhynchoribates insignis Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 57, fig. 52.

Rhynchoribates insignis: Miko 2016: 134.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Rhynchoribates (Rhynchoribates) spatulatus*
Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Rhynchoribates spatulatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 57, fig. 54.

Rhynchoribates spatulatus: Miko 2016: 134.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Rhynchoribates (Rhynchoribates) spectabilis*
Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Rhynchoribates spectabilis Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 57, fig. 53.

Rhynchoribates spectabilis: Miko 2016: 134.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Suctoribates Balogh, 1963

***Suctoribates neotropicus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Suctoribates neotropicus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 271, figs 27–28.

Suctoribates neotropicus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 39.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

***Suctoribates suctorius* Balogh, 1963**

Suctoribates suctorius Balogh, 1963: 38, figs 8–9.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

STAUROBATIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1966

***Staurobates* Grandjean, 1966**

***Staurobates schusteri cordobensis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1968**

Staurobates schusteri cordobensis Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 322, figs 6–7.

Staurobates schusteri cordobensis: Balogh & Mahunka 1981: 52.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited also in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-387-68/D-Am), two paratypes (0-388-68/D-Am) and another paratype without reg. no.

ZETORCHESTOIDEA MICHAEL, 1898

ARCEREMAEIDAE BALOGH, 1972

***Arceremaeus* Hammer, 1961**

***Arceremaeus cubanus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Arceremaeus cubanus Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 51, figs 17A–B.

Arceremaeus cubanus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 39.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Tecteremaeus* Hammer, 1961**

***Tecteremaeus anoporosus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Tecteremaeus anoporosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 53, fig. 43.

Tecteremaeus anoporosus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 40.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Tecteremaeus cristatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Tecteremaeus cristatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 12, fig. 33.

Tecteremaeus cristatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 40.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nine paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

GUSTAVIOIDEA OUDEMANS, 1900

ASTEGISTIDAE BALOGH, 1961

Cultroribula Berlese, 1908

***Cultroribula argentinensis* Balogh & Csiszár,
1963**

Cultroribula argentinensis Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 472, figs 17–18.
Cultroribula argentinensis: Fredes 2018: 69.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1098-68/D-Am) and three paratypes.

***Cultroribula humerata* Balogh & Mahunka,
1966**

Cultroribula humerata Balogh & Mahunka, 1966b: 28, figs 6–7.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-81-67/Afr) and one paratype (0-82-67/Afr).

***Cultroribula laticuspis* Balogh, 1970**

Cultroribula laticuspis Balogh, 1970b: 298, pl. II. fig. 13, pl. III. fig. 14.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Cultroribula quinquesetosa* J. Balogh &
P. Balogh, 1983**

Cultroribula quinquesetosa J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 86, figs 5A–C.

Cultroribula quinquesetosa: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 106.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Cultroribula bicultrata* (Berlese, 1905)**

Cultroribula Szent-Iványi [!] Balogh, 1943: 70, tab. XIII, fig. 5–6.

Cultroribula bicultrata: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 157.

Cultroribula bicultrata: Behan-Pelletier & Lindo 2019: 73.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Cultroribula tropica* Balogh, 1958**

Cultroribula tropica Balogh, 1958: 24.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Cultroribula zicsii* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

Cultroribula zicsii Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 76, figs 77–81.

Cultroribula zicsii: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 40.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty four paratypes HNHM, five paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and ten paratypes.

***Furcoppia (Furcoppia)* Balogh & Mahunka,
1966**

***Furcoppia (Furcoppia) imitans* Balogh &
Mahunka, 1966**

Furcoppia imitans Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 8, figs 14–15.

Furcoppia imitans: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 74.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, NM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Furcoppia (Furcoppia) parva* Balogh &
Mahunka, 1967**

Furcoppia parva Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 43, pl. III. Figs 15–16.

Furcoppia parva: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 74.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-61-67/As) and two paratypes (0-62-67/As).

Remarks. In the original description there is only a single paratype mentioned. An expert's examination is necessary to assess the status of these two specimens.

Quadrribula J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1992

***Quadrribula quadrisetosa* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983)**

Cultrribula quadrisetosa J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 85, figs 4A–C.

Quadrribula quadrisetosa: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 193, figs 205C–D.

Cultrribula quadrisetosa: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 106.

Quadrribula quadrisetosa: Subías 2022: 150.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

GUSTAVIIDAE OUDEMANS, 1900

***Gustavia* Kramer, 1879**

***Gustavia rugosa* Balogh, 1958**

Gustavia rugosa Balogh, 1958: 24.

Gustavia rugosa: Balogh 1962d: 94.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

LIACARIDAE SELLNICK, 1928

***Liacarus (Liacarus) Michael*, 1898**

***Liacarus (Liacarus) celisi* Balogh, 1958**

Liacarus celisi Balogh, 1958: 24.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Liacarus (Liacarus) curvidentatus* Balogh, 1958**

Liacarus curvidentatus Balogh, 1958: 24.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Liacarus (Liacarus) koeszegiensis* Balogh, 1943**

Liacarus koeszegiensis Balogh, 1943: 72, tab. XIII, fig. 14–16.

Liacarus koeszegiensis: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 151.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

Remarks. Mounted on microscope slides.

***Liacarus (Liacarus) leleupi* Balogh, 1958**

Liacarus leleupi Balogh, 1958: 24.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Liacarus (Procorynetes) Wooley*, 1967**

***Liacarus (Procorynetes) andinus* (P. Balogh, 1984)**

Procorynetes andinus P. Balogh, 1984b: 318, fig. 6.

Liacarus (Procorynetes) andinus: Subías 2020: 155.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and seven paratypes.

***Liacarus (Procorynetes) espeletiae* (P. Balogh, 1984)**

Procorynetes espeletiae P. Balogh, 1984b: 318, figs 3–5.

Liacarus (Procorynetes) espeletiae: Subías 2020: 156.

Liacarus (Procorynetes) espeletiae: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 75.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

Liacarus (Rhaphidosus) Woolley, 1969

Liacarus (Rhaphidosus) alticola (P. Balogh, 1984)

Rhaphidosus alticola P. Balogh, 1984b: 318, fig. 9.
Liacarus (Rhaphidosus) alticola: Subías 2020: 156.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Xenillus (Xenillus) Robineau-Desvoidy, 1839

Xenillus (Xenillus) amazonicus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985

Xenillus amazonicus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 58, figs 8A–G.
Xenillus amazonicus: P. Balogh 1985f: 53, fig. 16.
Xenillus (Xenillus) amazonicus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 41.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty-four paratypes, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and twenty-one paratypes.

Xenillus (Xenillus) argentinensis J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985

Xenillus argentinensis J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 54, figs 1A–F.
Xenillus argentinensis: P. Balogh 1985f: 43, fig. 1.
Xenillus argentinensis: Fredes 2018: 70.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

Xenillus (Xenillus) baggioi P. Balogh, 1995

Xenillus baggioi P. Balogh, 1995: 4 figs 4–8.

Xenillus baggioi: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 41.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Xenillus (Xenillus) bolivianus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985

Xenillus bolivianus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 79, figs 15A–D.

Xenillus bolivianus: P. Balogh 1985f: 53, fig. 15.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Xenillus (Xenillus) brasilianus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Xenillus brasilianus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 8, fig. 17.

Xenillus brasilianus: P. Balogh 1985f: 52, fig. 12.

Xenillus (Xenillus) brasilianus: Ermilov & Smit 2017: 796.

Xenillus (Xenillus) brasilianus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 41.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one vial of paratypes.

Remarks. On loan to H. Schatz (Innsbruck).

Xenillus (Xenillus) capitatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1977

Xenillus capitatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 9, fig. 7.

Xenillus capitatus: P. Balogh 1985f: 43, fig. 5.

Xenillus (Xenillus) capitatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 42.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG, one paratype ZIL.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and six paratypes.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) columbianus* P. Balogh, 1984**

Xenillus columbianus P. Balogh, 1984b: 321, figs 10–13.

Xenillus columbianus: P. Balogh 1985f: 52, fig. 8.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) davisorum* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985**

Xenillus davisorum J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 59, figs 9A–F.

Xenillus davisorum: P. Balogh 1985f: 60, fig. 19.

Xenillus davisorum: Ermilov, Niedbała & Friedrich 2016: 63.

Xenillus (Xenillus) davisorum: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 42.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) deformatus* P. Balogh, 1986**

Xenillus deformatus P. Balogh, 1986a: 45 figs 4–7.

Xenillus deformatus: Ermilov, Niedbała & Friedrich 2016: 63.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) disjunctus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

Xenillus disjunctus Balogh & Mahunka, 1977b: 254, fig. 5.

Xenillus disjunctus: P. Balogh 1985f: 61, fig. 25.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) diversisetosus* P. Balogh, 1986**

Xenillus diversisetosus P. Balogh, 1986a: 48, figs 12–15.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) ecuadorensis* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985**

Xenillus ecuadorensis J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 59, figs 10A–E.

Xenillus ecuadorensis: P. Balogh 1985f: 60, fig. 18.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty-two paratypes, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and thirty paratypes.

Remarks. The number of paratypes in the publication and in the collection is different. Expert verification is needed to confirm that all the 30 specimens belong to the same species.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) fazendae* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985**

Xenillus fazendae J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 54, figs 2A–D.

Xenillus fazendae: P. Balogh 1985f: 43, fig. 4.

Xenillus (Xenillus) fazendae: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 42.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. On loan to H. Schatz (Innsbruck).

***Xenillus (Xenillus) fecundus* P. Balogh, 1986**

Xenillus fecundus P. Balogh, 1986a: 45, figs 8–11.

Xenillus (Xenillus) fecundus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 42.

Xenillus fecundus: Fredes 2018: 70.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) forceps* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985**

Xenillus forceps J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 55, figs 3A–D.

Xenillus forceps: P. Balogh 1985f: 43, fig. 3.

Xenillus (Xenillus) forceps: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 42.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) fusifer* Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

Xenillus fusifer Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 10, fig. 8.

Xenillus fusifer: P. Balogh 1985f: 61, fig. 25.

Xenillus (Xenillus) fusifer: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 42.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and sixteen paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG, one paratype ZIL.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and fourteen paratypes.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) hammerae* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985**

Xenillus hammerae J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 57, figs 7A–D.

Xenillus hammerae: P. Balogh 1985f: 52, fig. 10.

Xenillus (Xenillus) hammerae: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 42.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) heterotrichus* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985**

Xenillus heterotrichus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 60, figs 11A–E.

Xenillus heterotrichus: P. Balogh 1985f: 60, fig. 20.

Xenillus (Xenillus) heterotrichus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 43.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) irregularis* P. Balogh, 1986**

Xenillus irregularis P. Balogh, 1986a: 43, figs 1–3.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) lawrencei* Balogh & Mahunka, 1968**

Xenillus lawrencei Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 322, figs 8–9.

Xenillus lawrencei: P. Balogh 1985f: 53, fig. 13.

Xenillus lawrencei: Fredes 2018: 70.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited also in the collections of J. Aoki and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-352-68/D-Am) and one paratype.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) longisetosus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Xenillus longisetosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 264, fig. 17.

Xenillus longisetosus: P. Balogh 1985f: 60, fig. 23.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) penicilliger* Csiszár, 1961**

Xenillus penicilliger Csiszár, 1961b: 447, fig. 2.

Xenillus penicilliger: Oszuts *et al.* 2021: 151.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes, ELTE Department of Systematic Zoology.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-262-68/E).

***Xenillus (Xenillus) peruensis* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985**

Xenillus peruensis J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 57, figs 6A–E.
Xenillus peruensis: P. Balogh 1985f: 52, fig. 7.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) punctulatus* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985**

Xenillus punctulatus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 60, figs 12A–D.
Xenillus punctulatus: P. Balogh 1985f: 53, fig. 17.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) rohri* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985**

Xenillus rohri J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 56, figs 5A–F.
Xenillus rohri: P. Balogh 1985f: 52, fig. 11.
Xenillus (Xenillus) rohri: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 43.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and sixteen paratypes, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and sixteen paratypes.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) setiger* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985**

Xenillus setiger J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 61, figs 14A–D.
Xenillus setiger: P. Balogh 1985f: 53, fig. 14.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) subnudus* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985**

Xenillus subnudus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 56, figs 4A–F.
Xenillus subnudus: P. Balogh 1985f: 43, fig. 6.
Xenillus (Xenillus) subnudus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 43.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) variabilis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

Xenillus variabilis Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 76, figs 72–76.
Xenillus variabilis: P. Balogh 1985f: 43, fig. 2.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Xenillus (Xenillus) venezuelanus* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985**

Xenillus venezuelanus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1985b: 61, figs 13A–D.
Xenillus venezuelanus: P. Balogh 1985f: 60, fig. 21.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

MULTORIBULIDAE BALOGH, 1972

***Multoribula* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

***Multoribula multipunctata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Multoribula multipunctata Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 10, figs 16–17.
Multoribula multipunctata: Balogh & Mahunka 1977b: 256, figs 6C–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype NM, and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

***Multoribula suramericana* Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

Multoribula suramericana Balogh & Mahunka, 1977b: 255, figs 6A–B.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

PELOPPIIDAE BALOGH, 1943

***Amazoppia* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Amazoppia tricuspidata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Amazoppia tricuspidata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 6, figs 15–16.

Amazoppia tricuspidata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 41.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fourteen paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of. J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and fourteen paratypes.

***Austroceratoppia* Hammer, 1979**

***Austroceratoppia crassiseta* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)**

Ceratoppia crassiseta Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 42, pl. III. figs 13–14.

Austroceratoppia crassiseta: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 83.

Austroceratoppia crassiseta: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 76.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-75-67/As) and one paratype (0-76-67/As).

Remark. Only a holotype is designated in the original description. Although the locality and

date of the "paratype" match the holotype, it cannot be considered a paratype because it was not designated in the original publication.

***Ceratorchestes* (*Paraceratorchestes*) Ermilov & Kalúz, 2012**

***Ceratorchestes* (*Paraceratorchestes*) *globosus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Ceratorchestes globosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 42, fig. 16.

Ceratorchestes (*Paraceratorchestes*) *globosus:* Ermilov, Friedrich & Kontschán 2016: 809.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of. J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Ceratorchestes* (*Ceratorchestes*) Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Ceratorchestes* (*Ceratorchestes*) *setosus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Ceratorchestes setosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 6, figs 12–13.

Ceratorchestes (*Ceratorchestes*) *setosus:* Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 41.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of. J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-514-68/D-Am) and one paratype (0-515-68/D-Am).

***Notoppia* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

***Notoppia humerata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Notoppia humerata Balogh & Mahunka, 1966c: 555, figs 3–4.

Notoppia humerata: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 108.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The type specimens are in the Austral Museum and HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. The holotype was returned to the CSIRO in 1996, but the vial labelled as the holotype of *N. humerata* Balogh & Mahnka, 1966 proved to be a *Peloribates* species, so the holotype should be considered lost (Colloff & Halliday 1998).

***Pseudoceratoppia* Hammer, 1962**

***Pseudoceratoppia mariannae* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Pseudoceratoppia mariannae J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 87, figs 6A–C.

Pseudoceratoppia mariannae: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 109.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nineteen paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Sixteen paratypes.

***Trichoppia* Balogh, 1961**

***Trichoppia longiseta* Balogh, 1961**

Trichoppia longiseta Balogh, 1961d: 20, figs 20–22.

Trichoppia longiseta: Mahunka 2009a: 91.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes, no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Five paratypes.

CARABODOIDEA C. L. KOCH, 1837

CARABODIDAE C.L.KOCH, 1837

***Aokiella* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967**

***Aokiella florens* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967**

Aokiella florens Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 44, pl. II. Figs 11–12.

Aokiella florens: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 77.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes)* Hammer, 1966**

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) agalawatta* P. Balogh, 1988**

Austrocarabodes agalawatta P. Balogh, 1988b: 182, figs 28–31.

Austrocarabodes agalawatta: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) agressor* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Austrocarabodes agressor Balogh & Mahunka, 1978a: 36, figs 12–16.

Austrocarabodes agressor: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 110.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nine paratypes. The holotype and partly the paratypes are deposited in CSIRO, Canberra; another part of paratypes are deposited in HNHM:

Deposited in HNHM: Nine paratypes.

Remarks. The holotype was sent to CSIRO in 1977, but according to Colloff & Halliday (1998) the specimen cannot be found in CSIRO.

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) albidus* (Balogh, 1961)**

Carabodes albidus Balogh, 1961d: 22, figs 23–24.

Austrocarabodes albidus: Mahunka 1987a: 402.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) angulatus* (Balogh, 1958)**

Carabodes angulatus Balogh, 1958: 18.

Austrocarabodes angulatus: Mahunka 1987a: 402.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) australis*
(Balogh & Csiszár, 1963)**

Carabodes australis Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 474, fig. 29.

Austrocarabodes australis: Mahunka 1987a: 402.

Austrocarabodes australis: Fredes 2018: 71.

Austrocarabodes australis: Baert 2018: 72.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No deposition specified.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1104-68/D-Am).

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) bellicosus*
P. Balogh, 1988**

Austrocarabodes bellicosus P. Balogh, 1988b: 180, figs 21–27.

Austrocarabodes bellicosus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Jorharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No deposition information.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) cellularis*
(Balogh, 1962)**

Carabodes cellularis Balogh, 1962b: 425, figs 17–18.

Austrocarabodes cellularis: Mahunka 1987a: 402.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) costulatus*
(Balogh, 1958)**

Carabodes costulatus Balogh, 1958: 17.

Carabodes costulatus: Balogh 1960b: 92, figs 6–8.

Austrocarabodes costulatus: Mahunka 1987a: 403.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. Balogh (1960b) reported a holotype and three paratypes. As the original description

lacks detailed information on the type material, these specimens should be considered as syntypes.

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) davisii*
(Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Carabodes davisii Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 46, figs 23–25.

Austrocarabodes davisii: Mahunka 1987a: 403.

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) davisii: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 44.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) gressitti*
Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Austrocarabodes gressitti Balogh & Mahunka, 1978a: 36, figs 17–21.

Austrocarabodes gressitti: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 110.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. The holotype and partly the paratypes are deposited in CSIRO, Canberra; another part of paratypes are deposited in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Three paratypes.

Remarks. According to the files in HNHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO in 28. Nov. 1977, however, Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it.

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) longulus*
(Balogh, 1958)**

Carabodes longulus Balogh, 1958: 19.

Carabodes longulus: Balogh 1962d: 95.

Austrocarabodes longulus: Mahunka 1987a: 404.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) lunaris*
(Balogh, 1962)**

Carabodes lunaris Balogh, 1962b: 423, figs 15–16.
Austrocarabodes lunaris: Mahunka 1987a: 404.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) schwartzi*
(Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Carabodes schwartzi Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 47, figs 32–33.
Carabodes schwartzi: Balogh & Mahunka 1978c: 277, figs 6A–C.
Austrocarabodes schwartzi: Mahunka 1987a: 405.
Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) schwartzi:
Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 44.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty two paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and nine paratypes.

***Ausrtocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) sordidus*
(Balogh, 1958)**

Carabodes sordidus Balogh, 1958: 18.
Austrocarabodes sordidus: Mahunka 1987a: 405.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) sphaerula*
Balogh, 1970**

Austrocarabodes sphaerula Balogh, 1970a: 38, fig. 8.
Austrocarabodes sphaerula: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) szentivanyi*
(Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)**

Carabodes szentivanyi Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 43, pl. II, figs 9–10.
Austrocarabodes szentivanyi: Aoki 1987: 28, fig. 7.
Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) szentivanyi: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 78.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-41-67/As).

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) travei*
(Balogh & Csiszár, 1963)**

Carabodes travei Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 474, fig. 26.
Austrocarabodes travei: Mahunka 1987a: 405.
Austrocarabodes travei: Schatz 2006: 238.
Austrocarabodes travei: Fredes 2018: 72.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1103-68/D-Am) and three paratypes.

***Austrocarabodes (Uluguroides) Mahunka, 1983*
Austrocarabodes (Uluguroides) pentatrichus
(Balogh, 1962)**

Carabodes pentatrichus Balogh, 1962d: 98, figs 12–13.
Austrocarabodes pentatrichus: Mahunka 1987a: 405.
Ngorongobodes pentatrichus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 195, figs 220A–B.
Austrocarabodes (Uluguroides) pentatrichus: Subías 2004: 149.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Austrocarabodes (Uluguroides) polytrichus*
Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Austrocarabodes polytrichus Balogh & Mahunka, 1978a: 39, figs 22–23.
Austrocarabodes polytrichus: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 110.

Austrocarabodes (Uluguroides) polytrichus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 79.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and partly the paratypes are deposited in CSIRO, Canberra; another part of paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes.

Remarks. According to the files in HNHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO on 28 Nov. 1977 however, Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it.

Carabodes (Carabodes) C. L. Koch, 1835

***Carabodes (Carabodes) basilewskyi* Balogh, 1958**

Carabodes basilewskyi Balogh, 1958: 19.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Carabodes (Carabodes) bicolor* Balogh, 1958**

Carabodes bicolor Balogh, 1958: 18.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Carabodes (Carabodes) hungaricus* Balogh, 1943**

Carabodes hungaricus Balogh, 1943: 66, tab. XII, fig. 5–6.

Carabodes hungaricus: Schatz 2018: 37.

Type material in the literature. No data.

Deposited in HNHM: Syntypes.

Remarks. In HNHM, there are three specimens mounted on a microscope slide.

Carabodes (Klapperiches) Mahunka, 1979

***Carabodes (Klapperiches) borhidii* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

Carabodes borhidii Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 39, fig. 4.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Carabodes (Klapperiches) depilatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Carabodes depilatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 46, fig. 26.

Austrocarabodes depilatus: Mahunka 1987a: 403.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-597-68/D-Am).

***Carabodes (Klapperiches) ecuadoriensis* P. Balogh, 1988**

Carabodes ecuadoriensis P. Balogh, 1988c: 329, figs 18–23.

Carabodes (Klapperiches) ecuadoriensis: Subías 2004: 151.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and six paratypes.

***Carabodes (Klapperiches) excellens* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Carabodes excellens Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 46, figs 27–29.

Carabodes (Klapperiches) excellens: Ermilov, Niedbala & Friedrich 2016: 63.

Carabodes (Klapperiches) excellens: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 44.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in the HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-598-68/D-Am) and four paratypes (0-599-68/D-Am).

***Carabodes (Klapperiches) globiger* Balogh, 1970**

Carabodes globiger Balogh, 1970a: 38, fig. 7.

Carabodes (Klapperiches) globiger: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and a paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

***Carabodes (Klapperiches) kusseri* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Carabodes kusseri J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 307, fig. 4.

Carabodes (Klapperiches) kusseri: Subías 2004: 151.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Remarks. In the original description (J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1983c) only a holotype is mentioned, therefore the specimen labelled as paratype has no nomenclatural value.

***Carabodes (Klapperiches) samoensis* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Carabodes samoensis J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986b: 272, figs 20–25.

Carabodes (Klapperiches) samoensis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 79.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Carabodes (Klapperiches) strinovichi* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Carabodes strinovichi Balogh & Mahunka, 1978a: 40, figs 24–27.

Carabodes strinovichi: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 111.

Carabodes (Klapperiches) strinovichi: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 79.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and a paratype. The holotype and partly the paratypes are deposited in CSIRO, Canberra; another part of paratypes in HNHM:

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. The holotype was sent to CSIRO Canberra on 28 Nov. 1977 however, Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it.

Carabodes (Phyllocarabodes) Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

***Carabodes (Phyllocarabodes) insolitus* (P. Balogh, 1984)**

Pentabodes insolitus P. Balogh, 1984b: 322, figs 14–18.
Carabodes (Phyllocarabodes) insolitus: Subías 2004: 151.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and a paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Carabodes (Phyllocarabodes) octogonalis* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Phyllocarabodes octogonalis Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 48, figs 34–35.

Carabodes (Phyllocarabodes) octogonalis: Subías 2010: 37.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and a paratype. Holotype and the greater part of the Paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

***Carabodes (Phyllocarabodes) pbaloghi* Subías, 2021**

Phyllocarabodes ornatus P. Balogh, 1986c: 59, figs 1–4.

Carabodes (Phyllocarabodes) schatzi Subías, 2010: 37. **nom. nov.**

Carabodes (Phyllocarabodes) schatzi: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 80.

Carabodes (Phyllocarabodes) pbaloghi Subías, 2021: 107. **nom. nov.**

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. Subías (2010) provided a replacement name *C. (Ph.) schatzi* for the praecoccupied

Carabodes (Phyllocarabodes) ornatus. However, *C. (Ph.) schatzi* is itself preoccupied by *Carabodes (Klapperiches) schatzi* Bernini, 1976 therefore Subias (2021) provided a new replacement name *C. (Ph.) pbaloghi*.

Ceylobodes J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1992

***Ceylobodes capillatus* (Balogh, 1970)**

Trichocarabodes capillatus Balogh, 1970a: 42, figs 14–15.

Trichocarabodes capillatus: P. Balogh 1988b: 172.

Ceylobodes capillatus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 195, figs 218D–E.

Ceylobodes capillatus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. The holotype is broken.

***Ceylobodes hettigei* (Balogh, 1970)**

Trichocarabodes hettigei Balogh, 1970a: 42, figs 1–2.

Ceylobodes hettigei: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 195.

Ceylobodes hettigei: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Congocepheus (Congocepheus) Balogh, 1958

***Congocepheus (Congocepheus) heterotrichus* Balogh, 1958**

Congocepheus heterotrichus Balogh, 1958: 21.

Congocepheus heterotrichus: Mahunka 1986: 120.

Congocepheus heterotrichus: Fernandez *et al.* 2013: 600–604.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: ?

Remarks. There is a vial of ten specimens in the HNHM labelled as *Congocepheus heterotrichus* Balogh, but it lacks typus markings, but

the locality is the same as in the original description.

Mahunka (1986) in his revision of the species mentioned a holotype, 62 paratypes and 40 other specimens collected later. The holotype and thirty paratypes are reportedly deposited in MRAC thirty paratypes in HNHM and two paratypes in NHMG. Fernandez *et al.* (2013) did not find any material in MRAC and accessed only the two paratypes in Genève. However, in the original description there is no holotype designated consequently all the available material from the original collection (Tshikapa et Luluabourg, 14. IX. 1955) should be considered as syntypes.

***Congocepheus (Congocepheus) taurus* Balogh, 1961**

Congocepheus taurus Balogh, 1961b: 522, figs 10–11.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM and five paratypes, without deposition specified.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Cubabodes* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

***Cubabodes confertus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Cubabodes confertus Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 32, figs 6A–B.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Cubabodes hexagonalis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Cubabodes hexagonalis Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 10, figs 7A–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Remarks. The original description refers to a holotype only.

***Cubabodes radiatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Cubabodes radiatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 11, figs 8A–B.

Cubabodes radiatus: Schatz 2006: 239.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Remarks. In the original description only a holotype is designated.

***Cubabodes spatulatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Cubabodes spatulatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 34, figs 6C–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Cubabodes verrucatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Cubabodes verrucatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 34, figs 6E–F.

Cubabodes verrucatus: Schatz 2006: 239.

Cubabodes verrucatus: Ermilov & Smit 2017: 796.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Diplobodes (Neocarabodes) Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

***Diplobodes (Neocarabodes) sexpilosus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Neocarabodes sexpilosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 8, figs 18–20.

Gibbicepheus (Neocarabodes) sexpilosus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 44.

Diplobodes (Neocarabodes) sexpilosus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 87.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-522-68/D-Am) and one paratype.

Gibbicepheus (Gibbicepheus) Balogh, 1958

***Gibbicepheus (Gibbicepheus) elevatus* Balogh, 1958**

Gibbicepheus elevatus Balogh, 1958: 20.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Gibbicepheus (Gibbicepheus) ensifer* Balogh, 1958**

Gibbicepheus ensifer Balogh, 1958: 20.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Gibbicepheus (Gibbicepheus) tuberculatus* Balogh, 1970**

Gibbicepheus tuberculatus Balogh, 1970b: 299, pl. III, figs 15.

Gibbicepheus tuberculatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 87.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Gibbicepheus (Gibbicepheus) waterhousei* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Gibbicepheus waterhousei Balogh & Mahunka, 1978a: 40, figs 28–31.

Gibbicepheus waterhousei: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 111.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. The holotype and partly the paratypes are deposited in CSIRO, Canberra; another part of paratypes in HNHM:

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes.

Remarks. According to the files in HNHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO Canberra in 1977.11.28, but Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it.

Gymnobodes Balogh, 1965

Gymnobodes fraterculus (Balogh, 1963)

Carabodes fraterculus Balogh, 1963: 38, figs 6–7.

Gymnobodes fraterculus: Mahunka 1987a: 403.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Gymnobodes subnudus (Balogh, 1963)

Carabodes subnudus Balogh, 1963: 36, figs 4–5.

Gymnobodes subnudus: Mahunka 1987a: 405.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Hardybodes Balogh, 1970

Hardybodes mirabilis Balogh, 1970

Hardybodes mirabilis Balogh, 1970b: 298, pl. III, figs 16–17.

Hardybodes mirabilis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 88.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Machadocephus (Machadocephus) Balogh, 1958

Machadocephus (Machadocephus) excavatus Balogh, 1958

Machadocephus excavatus Balogh, 1958: 21.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Twenty-one paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description there is no information about the type material. Therefore all specimens should be considered as syntypes.

Machadocephus (Machadocephus) pauliani Balogh, 1962

Machadocephus pauliani Balogh, 1962b: 423, figs 12–14.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Machadocephus (Machadocephus) phyllophorus Balogh, 1970

Machadocephus phyllophorus Balogh, 1970b: 300, pl. IV, figs 21–22.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Machadocephus (Machadocephus) taprobanicus Balogh, 1970

Machadocephus taprobanicus Balogh, 1970a: 42, fig. 11.

Machadocephus taprobanicus: P. Balogh 1988b: 172.

Machadocephus (Machadocephus) taprobanicus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and a paratype, HNHM

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

Machadocepheus (Sagittabodes) J. Balogh & P. Balogh

Machadocepheus (Sagittabodes) sagitta Balogh & Mahunka, 1966

Machadocepheus sagitta Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 12, figs 20–22.

Sagittabodes sagitta: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 196, figs 226D–E.

Type material in the literature. Holotype NM, one paratype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Pasocepheus (Guineobodes) Mahunka, 1987

Pasocepheus (Guineobodes) papuanus (Balogh, 1970)

Machadocepheus papuanus Balogh, 1970b: 300, pl. III, fig. 19, pl. IV, Fig. 20.

Guineobodes papuanus: Mahunka: 1987: 408, figs. 9–13.

Pasocepheus (Guineobodes) papuanus: Subías 2004: 153.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

Spathulocepheus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Spathulocepheus amazonicus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Spathulocepheus amazonicus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 9, figs 21–22.

Spathulocepheus amazonicus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 45.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twentyfour paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are deposited in HNHM;

some paratypes in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and ten paratypes.

Spathulocepheus plumiger Balogh & Mahunka, 1977

Spathulocepheus plumiger Balogh & Mahunka, 1977b: 257, fig. 7.

Spathulocepheus plumiger: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 45.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Trichocarabodes Balogh, 1961

Trichocarabodes celisi (Balogh, 1958)

Carabodes celisi Balogh, 1958: 19.

Trichocarabodes celisi: Balogh 1961f: 302, pl. 15, figs 1–2.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Tuberocepheus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Tuberocepheus longus (Balogh, 1962)

Machadocepheus longus Balogh, 1962e: 139, figs 29–31.

Machadocepheus longus: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Tuberocepheus longus: Balogh & Mahunka 1969: 9.

Tuberocepheus longus: Mahunka 2009a: 91.

Tuberocepheus longus: Mahunka 2011a: 5, figs 5–12.

Tuberocepheus longus: Fernández, Theron, Rollard, Leiva & Tiedt 2016: 83, figs: 6–32.

Type material in the literature. Holotype l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar, and three paratypes with no information on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes (0-1101-68/Afr).

Remarks. Fernandez *et al.* (2016: 84) re-described the species using specimens from the collection of J.M. Betsch deposited in MNHM, Paris.

However, they erroneously stated that these specimens represent the type material of *Tuberocephalus longus* (Balogh, 1962). The original material was collected in IX.1958 by A. Robinson and the material studied by Fernandez *et al.* (2016) is almost a decade later (24.01.1971).

Yoshiobodes (Yoshiobodes) Mahunka, 1986

Yoshiobodes (Yoshiobodes) irmayi (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)

Carabodes irmayi Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 47, figs 30–31.

Yoshiobodes irmayi: Mahunka 1986a: 109, figs 143–146.

Yoshiobodes (Yoshiobodes) irmayi: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 45.

Yoshiobodes (Yoshiobodes) irmayi: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 90.

Yoshiobodes (Yoshiobodes) irmayi: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 82.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes (0-602-68/D-Am) and one paratype without reg. no.

Yoshiobodes (Yoshiobodes) pauanus (Balogh, 1970)

Austrocarabodes humeratus pauanus Balogh, 1970b: 299, pl. III. fig. 18.

Yoshiobodes humeratus papuanus: Mahunka 1987a: 407.

Yoshiobodes (Yoshiobodes) papuanus: Subías 2004: 154.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

Yoshiobodes (Yoshiobodes) plumosulus (Balogh, 1970)

Austrocarabodes plumosulus Balogh, 1970a: 40, fig. 10.

Yoshiobodes plumosulus: Mahunka 1987a: 407.

Austrocarabodes plumosulus: P. Balogh 1988b: 172.

Yoshiobodes plumosulus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. According to the HNHM records, the holotype should be in the museum, but we could not find it.

Yoshiobodes (Yoshiobodes) plumosus Balogh, 1970

Austrocarabodes plumosus Balogh, 1970a: 40, fig. 9.

Yoshiobodes (Yoshiobodes) plumosus: Mahunka 1987a: 407.

Yoshiobodes plumosus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Nine paratypes.

DAMPFIELLIDAE BALOGH, 1961

Beckiella Grandjean, 1964

Beckiella acuta Balogh & Mahunka, 1978

Beckiella acuta Balogh & Mahunka, 1978b: 340, figs 22–24.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and sixteen paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype ZIL, one paratype at J. Aoki, Japan.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and twenty paratypes.

Beckiella africana (Balogh, 1958)

Dampfiella africana Balogh, 1958: 10.

Dampfiella africana: Balogh 1960b: 90, figs 3–5.
Beckiella africana: Ermilov & Rybalov 2018: 1835.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Beckiella borhidii* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Beckiella borhidii Balogh & Mahunka, 1978b: 335, figs 7–9.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Beckiella bucephala* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Beckiella bucephala Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 278, figs 7A–B.

Beckiella bucephala: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 45.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and seven paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description there are only three paratypes mentioned.

***Beckiella capitulum* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Beckiella capitulum Balogh & Mahunka, 1978b: 341, figs 25–28.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty-three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype ZIL, one paratype Dr. Aoki Japan.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and twenty-four paratypes.

***Beckiella deficiens* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Beckiella deficiens Balogh & Mahunka, 1978b: 339, figs 19–20.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype at J. Aoki, Japan.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Beckiella discoidalis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Beckiella discoidalis Balogh & Mahunka, 1978b: 337, figs 13–15.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

***Beckiella duplicata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Beckiella duplicata Balogh & Mahunka, 1978b: 334, figs 4–6.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

***Beckiella elongata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Beckiella elongata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 58, figs 55–56.

Beckiella elongata Balogh & Mahunka 1978b: 343.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

***Beckiella foveolata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Beckiella foveolata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 14, figs 38–39.

Beckiella foveolata: Balogh & Mahunka 1978c: 279, figs 8A–C.

Beckiella foveolata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 46.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Beckiella fratercula* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Beckiella fratercula Balogh & Mahunka, 1978b: 338, figs 16–18.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Beckiella garciai* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

Beckiella garciai Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 40, figs 5A–B.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. There are two vials in HNHM labelled as holotype; one with locality Pinar del Rio, 1975 and the other Cuba No. 56-65/1975 leg. Borhidi. This vial is empty. However, the published locality data are as follows: Holotype (278-HOI-78) Cuba, Prov. Habana, Surgidero de Batabano, deciduous grove, wet type, decaying palm leaf sheath. 28.XI.1969, leg. A. Borhidi. Either the label in the vial or the published locality is wrong.

***Beckiella interlamellaris* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Beckiella interlamellaris Balogh & Mahunka, 1978b: 333, figs 1–3.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG, one paratype ZIL, one paratype J. Aoki, Japan.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and twenty paratypes.

***Beckiella irmayi* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Beckiella irmayi Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 60, fig. 57.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are Deposited in HNHM: Some paratypes in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffli, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-631-68/D-Am) and one paratype (0-632-68/D-Am).

***Beckiella lamellata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Beckiella lamellata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 60, fig. 58.

Beckiella lamellata: Ermilov, Niedbała & Friedrich 2016: 63.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Beckiella microseta* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

Beckiella microseta Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 42, figs 5C–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype NMT.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

***Beckiella recta* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Beckiella recta Balogh & Mahunka, 1978b: 336, figs 10–12.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype J. Aoki Japan.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and six paratypes.

Remarks. Four of the six paratypes are broken.

***Beckiella reticulofemorata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

Beckiella reticulofemorata Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 42, figs 5E–F.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Beckiella silvai* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

Beckiella silvai Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 43, fig. 6.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Beckiella synlamellata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Beckiella synlamellata Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 12, figs 8C–E.

Beckiella synlamellata Balogh & Mahunka 1978b: 344.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Remarks. In the original publication there is only a holotype designated.

***Dampfiella* Sellnick, 1931**

***Dampfiella foliata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Dampfiella foliata Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 244, figs 1A–F.

Dampfiella foliata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 91.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Remarks. In the original publication there is only a holotype designated.

***Dampfiella papuana* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Dampfiella papuana J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 41, figs 19–23.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

OTOCEPHEIDAE BALOGH, 1961

***Cavernocephus (Cavernocephus)* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Cavernocephus (Cavernocephus) acutus* P. Balogh & Palacios-Vargas, 1997**

Cavernocephus acutus P. Balogh & Palacios-Vargas, 1997: 31, figs 1–3.

Cavernocephus (Cavernocephus) acutus: Ermilov & Starý 2018: 500.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Cavernocephus (Cavernocephus) furcatus* P. Balogh & Palacios-Vargas, 1997**

Cavernocephus furcatus P. Balogh & Palacios-Vargas, 1997: 32, figs 6–7.

Cavernocephus (Cavernocephus) furcatus: Ermilov & Starý 2018: 499.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Cavernocephus (Cavernocephus) fusifer* P. Balogh & Palacios-Vargas, 1997**

Cavernocephus fusifer P. Balogh & Palacios-Vargas, 1997: 32, figs 4–5.

Cavernocephus (Cavernocephus) fusifer: Ermilov & Starý 2018: 500.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Cavernocephus (Cavernocephus) monticola* P. Balogh, 1989**

Cavernocephus monticola P. Balogh, 1989: 17, figs 1–5.

Cavernocephus (Cavernocephus) monticola: Ermilov & Starý 2018: 500.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. The specimen has been re-wetted and damaged.

***Cavernocephus (Cavernocephus) monstruosus*
Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Cavernocephus monstruosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 14, figs 40–43.

Cavernocephus monstruosus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 46.

Cavernocephus (Cavernocephus) monstruosus: Ermilov & Starý 2018: 500.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Cavernocephus (Cavernocephus) obliquus*
P. Balogh, 2002 *nomen nudum***

Cavernocephus obliquus P. Balogh, 2002: 150, pl. 217: 7.

Cavernocephus obliquus: Schatz 2006: 240.

Cavernocephus obliquus: Subias 2023:252.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. This name is not available according to ICZN because does not fulfill Art. 16.4.1 (“explicit fixation of a holotype, or syntypes, for the nominal taxon”) and 16.4.2 (“where the holotype or syntypes are extant specimens, by a statement of intent that they will be (or are) deposited in a collection and a statement indicating the name and location of that collection”).

***Cavernocephus (Cavernocephus) undulatus*
P. Balogh, 2002 *nomen nudum***

Cavernocephus undulatus P. Balogh, 2002: 150, pl. 217: 8–9.

Cavernocephus undulatus: Schatz 2006: 240.

Cavernocephus obliquus: Subias 2023:252.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. This name is not available according to ICZN because does not fulfill Art. 16.4.1 (“explicit fixation of a holotype, or syntypes, for the nominal taxon”) and 16.4.2 (“where the holotype or syntypes are extant specimens, by a statement of intent that they will be (or are) deposited in a collection and a statement indicating the name and location of that collection”).

***Eurostocephus (Cerostocephus) Mahunka,*
1973**

***Eurostocephus (Cerostocephus) trisetosus*
Balogh, 1970**

Eurostocephus trisetosus Balogh, 1970a: 48a, fig. 28.

Eurostocephus (Cerostocephus) trisetosus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 94.

Eurostocephus (Cerostocephus) trisetosus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Leptotocephus (Leptotocephus) Balogh, 1961*
Leptotocephus (Leptotocephus) trimucronatus
Balogh, 1961**

Leptotocephus trimucronatus Balogh, 1961b: 521, fig. 9.

Leptotocephus (Leptotocephus) trimucronatus: Ermilov & Minor 2018: 2270.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM and two paratypes.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Leptocephus (Longocephus) Balogh &*
Mahunka, 1996**

***Leptotocephus (Longocephus) australis*
(Balogh & Mahunka, 1966)**

Longocephus australis Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 16, figs 29–30.

Leptotocepheus (Longocepheus) australis: Ermilov & Minor 2018: 2271.

Type material in the literature. Holotype NM.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Leptotocepheus (Longocepheus) longus* (Balogh, 1961)**

Pseudotocepheus longus Balogh, 1961d: 25, figs 27–29.

Pseudotocepheus longus: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Pseudotocepheus longus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 153, pl. 220, fig. 7.

Leptotocepheus (Longocepheus) longus: Ermilov & Minor 2018: 2271.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Lophotocepheus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1983**

***Lophotocepheus simplex* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Lophotocepheus simplex J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 294, fig 8.

Lophotocepheus simplex: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 112.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype is deposited in CSIRO Canberra, the paratypes partly in the above institute and partly in the Balogh Collection, later to be transferred to the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One type series specimen.

Remarks. The specimen in HNHM most probably represents a paratype.

Megalotocepheus (Megalotocepheus) Aoki, 1965

***Megalotocepheus (Megalotocepheus) ceylonicus* Balogh, 1970**

Megalotocepheus ceylonicus Balogh, 1970a: 48, figs 26–27.

Megalotocepheus ceylonicus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

***Megalotocepheus (Megalotocepheus) loksai* Balogh, 1970**

Megalotocepheus loksai Balogh, 1970a: 47, fig. 25.

Megalotocepheus loksai: P. Balogh 1988b: 172.

Megalotocepheus loksai: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

***Megalotocepheus (Megalotocepheus) mahunkarum* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002**

Megalotocepheus mahunkarum J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 159, pls 226: 15, 227: 1. **nom. nov.** pro *M. ceylanicus* Mahunka, 1973 nec. Balogh, 1970.

Megalotocepheus ceylanicus Mahunka, 1973: 100, fig. X.

Megalotocepheus mahunkarum: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes MNHG, two paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes (*M. ceylanicus*).

Otocepheus (Acrotocepheus) Aoki, 1965

***Otocepheus (Acrotocepheus) bucephalus* (Balogh, 1970)**

Acrotocepheus bucephalus Balogh, 1970a: 47, fig. 22.

Acrotocepheus bucephalus: P. Balogh 1988b: 172.

Otocepheus (Acrotocepheus) bucephalus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Otocepheus (Acrotocepheus) consimilis* (Balogh, 1970)**

Acrotocepheus consimilis Balogh, 1970a: 47, figs 23–24.

Otocepheus (Acrotocepheus) consimilis: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Otocepheus (Acrotocepheus) duplicornutus discrepans* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)**

Acrotocepheus duplicornutus discrepans Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 49, pl. VI. figs 31–32.

Otocepheus (Acrotocepheus) duplicornutus discrepans: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 86.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-52-67/As).

***Otocepheus (Acrotocepheus) heterotrichus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1968**

Otocepheus (Acrotocepheus) heterotrichus Balogh & Mahunka, 1968b: 342, figs 5–6.

Otocepheus (Acrotocepheus) heterotrichus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 99.

Type material in the literature: Holotype HNHM, one paratype NSMT.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Otocepheus (Acrotocepheus) triplicicornutus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)**

Acrotocepheus triplicicornutus Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 50, pl. VI. figs 33–34.

Otocepheus (Acrotocepheus) triplicicornutus: Ermilov & Starý 2018: 335.

Otocepheus (Acrotocepheus) triplicicornutus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 87.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-47-67/As).

***Papuacepheus* Balogh, 1968**

***Papuacepheus geminatus* (Balogh, 1968)**

Megalotocepheus (Papuacepheus) geminatus Balogh, 1968: 271, pl. IX. figs 47–48.

Papuacepheus geminatus: Subías 2004: 147.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

TETRACONDYLINAE Aoki, 1965

***Carabocepheus* Berlese, 1910**

***Carabocepheus latior* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Carabocepheus lonsburyi latior Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 12, figs 18–19.

Carabocepheus latior: Subías 2009: 261.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eighteen paratypes NM, eighteen paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Eleven paratypes.

***Dolicheremaeus* Jacot, 1938**

***Dolicheremaeus absolon* (Balogh & Csiszár, 1963)**

Tetracondyla absolon Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 480, figs 2, 37.

Dolicheremaeus absolon: Fredes 2018: 72.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1119-68/).

***Dolicheremaeus alticola* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Dolicheremaeus alticola J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 39, figs 12–14.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Dolicheremaeus amazonicus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Dolicheremaeus[!] *amazonicus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 15, figs 44–45.

Dolicheremaeus amazonicus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 46.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. The holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are deposited in the HNHM, one paratype each, whenever it has been possible to do so, forwarded to the collections of Dr. J. Aoki, Tokyo; Dr. E. Piffel, Vienna; Dr. A. Rajsiki, Poznan; and Dr. T. A. Woolley, Louisiana.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-538-68/D-Am).

***Dolicheremaeus aokii* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)**

Dicondyla aokii Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 50, pl. VI, figs 35–36.

Dolicheremaeus aokii: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 238.

Dolicheremaeus aokii: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 88.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-51-67/As).

***Dolicheremaeus bifidus* (Csiszár, 1961)**

Tetracondyla bifida Csiszár, 1961a: 354, fig. 23.

Dolicheremaeus bifidus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 107.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Dolicheremaeus bolivianus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Dolicheremaeus bolivianus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 61, fig. 59.

Dolicheremaeus bolivianus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 46.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajsiki and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Dolicheremaeus capillatus* (Balogh, 1959)**

Tetracondyla capillata Balogh, 1959c: 14, figs 6–7.

Tetracondyla capillata: Balogh 1962d: 95.

Dolicheremaeus capillatus: Subías 2004: 142.

Dolicheremaeus capillatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 89.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and thirteen paratypes.

***Dolicheremaeus ceylonicus* Balogh, 1970**

Dolicheremaeus ceylonicus Balogh, 1970a: 44, fig. 18.

Dolicheremaeus ceylonicus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Dolicheremaeus crispus* (Balogh, 1962)**

Tetracondyla crista Balogh, 1962d: 106, figs 26–27.

Dolicheremaeus crispus: Subías 2004: 142.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Dolicheremaeus damoeoides* (Berlese, 1913)**

Dolicheremaeus berlesei J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 173, pl. 241: 13–14. **nom. nov.** pro *D. damoeoides*

Balogh, 1968 nec. Berlese, 1913. **Nomen nudum.**

Otocephalus damaeoides Berlese, 1913: 93, pl. 6: 66.

Dolicheremaeus damoeoides: Subías 2004: 142.

Remarks. J. Balogh & P. Balogh provided a replacement name *D. berlesei* for *D. damoeoides* Balogh, 1968 thought to be preoccupied by *D. damoeoides* (Berlese, 1913). However, *Dolicheremaeus damoeoides* Balogh, 1968 does not exist. Balogh (1968: 271) reports several specimens of *D. damoeoides* from New Guinea, but

he clearly refers these specimens to the species described by Berlese (1913). It is possible that J. Balogh & P. Balogh (2002) thought that this is a misidentification and these specimens represent a new species. However, in this case using "nom. nov." is clearly misleading and renders this name nomen nudum and unavailable according to ICZN Art. 16.4 and 16A. It requires further studies to decide whether the New Guinean specimens of Balogh (1968) represent really a new species.

***Dolicheremaeus densefoveolatus* P. Balogh, 1988**

Dolicheremaeus densefoveolatus P. Balogh, 1988b: 185, figs 35–37.

Dolicheremaeus densefoveolatus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Dolicheremaeus dorni* (Balogh, 1937)**

Oppia Dorni Balogh, 1937: 221, 1–3.

Otocephalus Dorni: Balogh 1943: 54, tab. X. fig. 8.

Dolicheremaeus dorni: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 173.

Dolicheremaeus dorni: Norton & Ermilov 2014: 62.

Dolicheremaeus dorni: Miko 2016: 65.

Type material in the literature. Balogh Collection in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Dolicheremaeus elizabethae* Balogh, 1970**

Dolicheremaeus elizabethae Balogh, 1970a: 46, fig. 20.

Dolicheremaeus elizabethae: P. Balogh 1988b: 172.

Dolicheremaeus elizabethae: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and thirteen paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. The vial labelled *Dolicheremaeus elizabethae* seems to be empty and the material is possibly lost.

***Dolicheremaeus furcatus* (Balogh, 1961)**

Tetracondyla furcata Balogh, 1961b: 521.

Tetracondyla furcata: Balogh 1962d: 95, figs 28–30.

Dolicheremaeus furcatus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Dolicheremaeus furcula* Balogh, 1970**

Dolicheremaeus furcula Balogh, 1970a: 44, fig. 17.

Dolicheremaeus furcula: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Dolicheremaeus heterotrichus* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Dolicheremaeus heterotrichus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986b: 275, figs 26–28.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Dolicheremaeus inaequalis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967**

Dolicheremaeus inaequalis Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 53, pl. VII. 40–41.

Dolicheremaeus inaequalis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 91.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-45-67/As) and one paratype (0-44-67/As).

Remarks. The original description lists only one holotype.

***Dolicheremaeus kummeri* Balogh, 1970**

Dolicheremaeus kummeri Balogh, 1970b: 301, pl. IV. figs 23–24.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Dolicheremaeus lineatus* Balogh, 1970**

Dolicheremaeus lineatus Balogh, 1970: 46, fig. 19.

Dolicheremaeus lineatus: P. Balogh 1988b: 172.

Dolicheremaeus lineatus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

***Dolicheremaeus lineolatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967**

Dolicheremaeus lineolatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 54, pl. VIII. Figs 42–43.

Dolicheremaeus lineolatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 91.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-37-67/As).

***Dolicheremaeus machadoi* (Balogh, 1958)**

Tetracondyla machadoi Balogh, 1958: 22.

Tetracondyla machadoi: Balogh 1960b: 94, figs 9–10.

Dolicheremaeus machadoi: Subías 2004: 143.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Three paratypes (0-116-68/Afr).

Remarks. There is no holotype designated in the original description, therefore all type material should be considered as syntypes.

***Dolicheremaeus magnus* (Balogh, 1958)**

Tetracondyla magna Balogh, 1958: 22.

Tetracondyla magna: Balogh 1960b: 94, figs 11–12.

Dolicheremaeus magnus: Subías 2004: 142.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Nineteen paratypes.

Remarks. Balogh (1960b) reported a holotype and eight paratypes, but these subsequent designations are invalid. Expert verification is required to determine whether all 19 specimens (syntypes) in the vial belong to the same species.

***Dolicheremaeus markusi* Balogh, 1970**

Dolicheremaeus markusi Balogh, 1970a: 44, fig. 16.

Dolicheremaeus markusi: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Dolicheremaeus ornatus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)**

Dicondyla ornata Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 51, pl. VII. fig. 37.

Dolicheremaeus ornata: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 238.

Dolicheremaeus ornatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 92.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-33-67/As) and one paratype (0-42-67/As).

***Dolicheremaeus pectinatus* Balogh, 1970**

Dolicheremaeus pectinatus Balogh, 1970a: 46, fig. 21.

Dolicheremaeus pectinatus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Dolicheremaeus repetitus* Subías, 2004**

Dolicheremaeus elongatus Balogh, 1968: 272, pl. X. figs 53–54. nom. praec. by Aoki, 1967.
Dolicheremaeus repetitus Subías, 2004: 143. **nom. nov.**

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one hundred paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Dolicheremaeus semicapillata* (Balogh, 1962)**

Tetracondyla semicapillata Balogh, 1962d: 107, figs 31–32.
Dolicheremaeus semicapillata: Subías 2004: 143.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal de l’Afrique Centrale á Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Dolicheremaeus simplex* (Balogh, 1962)**

Tetracondyla simplex Balogh, 1962d: 105, fig. 25.
Dolicheremaeus simplex: Subías 2004: 143.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal de l’Afrique Centrale á Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Dolicheremaeus subsimilis* Balogh, 1968**

Dolicheremaeus subsimilis Balogh, 1968: 271, pl. IX. figs 49–50.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Dolicheremaeus szentivanyi* Balogh, 1968**

Dolicheremaeus szentivanyi Balogh, 1968: 272, pl. X. figs 55–56.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Dolicheremaeus vilhenarum* (Balogh, 1958)**

Tetracondyla vilhenarum Balogh, 1958: 22.
Tetracondyla vilhenarum: Balogh 1960b: 94, fig. 15.
Dolicheremaeus vilhenarum vilhenarum: Subías 2004: 143.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, á Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Dolicheremaeus vitraea* (Balogh, 1958)**

Tetracondyla vitraea Balogh, 1958: 22.
Tetracondyla vitraea: Balogh 1960b: 94, figs 13–14.
Dolicheremaeus vitraeus: Subías 2004: 143.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, á Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Fissicepheus (Fissicepheus) Balogh & Mahunka, 1967

***Fissicepheus (Fissicepheus) elegans* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967**

Fissicepheus elegans Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 52, pl. VII. Figs 38–39.
Fissicepheus elegans: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 93.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Flagellocephus* P. Balogh, 1984**

***Flagellocephus sagittatus* P. Balogh, 1984**

Flagellocephus sagittatus P. Balogh, 1984a: 40, figs 7A–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Papillocepheus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966
Papillocepheus deficiens J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983

Papillocepheus deficiens J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 295, fig 9.

Papillocepheus deficiens: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 112.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, CSIRO Canberra.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Papillocepheus heterotrichus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966

Papillocepheus heterotrichus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 18, figs 31–32.

Type material in the literature. Holotype NM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Pseudotocepheus Balogh, 1961

Pseudotocepheus amostruosus Mahunka, 1973

Pseudotocepheus septemtuberculatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 277, figs 6D–E.

Pseudotocepheus amonstruosus Mahunka, 1973: 91, fig. V.

Pseudotocepheus amonstruosus: Grobler 1997: 5.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

Pseudotocepheus asymmetricus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983

Pseudotocepheus asymmetricus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 90, figs 9A–C.

Pseudotocepheus asymmetricus: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 113.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Five paratypes.

Pseudotocepheus bacilliger J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983

Pseudotocepheus bacilliger J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983b: 295, fig. 10.

Pseudotocepheus bacilliger: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 113.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, CSIRO Canberra.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Pseudotocepheus coarctatus P. Balogh, 1985

Pseudotocepheus coarctatus P. Balogh, 1985b: 49, figs 1A–F.

Pseudotocepheus coarctatus: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 113.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Two "type material".

Remarks. The two specimens in HNHM most probably represent the paratypes.

Pseudotocepheus geminatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Pseudotocepheus geminatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 61, fig. 60.

Pseudotocepheus geminatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 46.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Pseudotocepheus medius Balogh & Mahunka, 1966

Pseudotocepheus medius Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 14, figs 27–28.

Pseudotocepheus medius: Grobler 1998: 31, figs 30–35.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes NM, two paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes (0-102-67/Afr).

***Pseudotocepheus montheithi* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Pseudotocepheus montheithi J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 91, figs 10A–C.

Pseudotocepheus montheithi: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 113.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nine paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Eight paratypes.

***Pseudotocepheus paralellus* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Pseudotocepheus paralellus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983b: 297, fig. 11.

Pseudotocepheus paralellus: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 113.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype is deposited in CSIRO Canberra, the paratypes partly in the above institute and partly in the Balogh Collection, later to be transferred to HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One "type-material".

Remarks. As there is a vial labelled as holotype in CSIRO, Canberra (although the vial is empty; (Colloff & Halliday 1988)) the specimen in HNHM is one of the paratypes.

***Pseudotocepheus pauliani* Balogh, 1961**

Pseudotocepheus pauliani Balogh, 1961d: 23, figs 25–26.

Pseudotocepheus pauliani: P. Balogh 1984a: 39.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Pseudotocepheus pygmaeus* Balogh, 1962**

Pseudotocepheus pygmaeus Balogh, 1962b: 427, figs 19–20.

Pseudotocepheus pygmaeus: Ermilov & Bąkowski 2021: 136.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Pseudotocepheus sturmi* P. Balogh, 1984**

Pseudotocepheus sturmi P. Balogh, 1984a: 36, figs 6A–D.

Pseudotocepheus sturmi: Ermilov 2016a: 216.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Pseudotocepheus szentivanyorum* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Pseudotocepheus szentivanyorum Balogh & Mahunka, 1978a: 42, figs 32–35.

Pseudotocepheus szentivanyorum: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 114.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. The holotype and partly the paratypes are deposited in CSIRO, Canberra; another part of paratypes are deposited in HNHM:

Deposited in HNHM: Six paratypes.

Remarks. Holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1977.11.28. But, according to Colloff & Halliday (1998) the holotype is not in CSIRO.

***Pseudotocepheus vicarius* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Pseudotocepheus vicarius Balogh & Mahunka, 1978a: 44, figs 36–39.

Pseudotocepheus vicarius: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 114.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eleven paratypes. The holotype and partly the paratypes are deposited in CSIRO, Canberra; another part of paratypes are Deposited in HNHM:

Deposited in HNHM: Ten paratypes.

Remarks. Holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1977.11.28. According to Colloff & Halliday (1998) the holotype is not in CSIRO.

Trichocephus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966

***Trichocephus lamellatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Trichocephus lamellatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 18, figs 33–34.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes in NM, four paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-149-67/Afr).

Trichocondyla J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986

***Trichocondyla multisetosa* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Trichocondyla multisetosa J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 40, figs 15–18.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

OPPIOIDEA GRANDJEAN, 1951

AUTOGNETIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1960

***Autogneta* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963**

***Austrogneta multipilosa* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963**

Austrogneta multipilosa Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 480, figs 24–25.

Austrogneta multipilosa: Fredes 2018: 73.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

GRANULOPPIIDAE BALOGH, 1983

***Enantioppia* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Enantioppia multituberculata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Enantioppia multituberculata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 52, figs 40–41.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Granuloppia Balogh, 1958

***Granuloppia congoensis* Balogh, 1958**

Granuloppia congoensis Balogh, 1958: 12.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

Remarks. The "holotype" specimen is broken however, as in the original description no holotype was selected all the specimens should be regarded as syntypes.

Granuloppia major Balogh, 1958

Granuloppia major Balogh, 1958: 12.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Seven paratypes.

Remarks. No holotype was selected in the original description, so all specimens should be considered as syntypes.

Hammerella (Bornemisszaella) P. Balogh 1994

***Hammerella (Bornemisszaella) fournieri* (P. Balogh, 1994)**

Bornemisszaella fournieri P. Balogh, 1994: 17, figs 1–3.

Bornemisszaella fournieri: Schatz 2006: 250.

Hammerella (Interoppia) fournieri: Subías 2008: 237.

Hammerella (Bornemisszaella) fournieri: Ermilov, Shtanchaeva, Subías & Anichkin 2012: 160.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes, Balogh Collection, Budapest.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Hammerella (Bornemisszaella) ramirezi* (P. Balogh, 1994)**

Bornemisszaella ramirezi P. Balogh, 1994: 17, figs 7–9.

Bornemisszaella ramirezi: Schatz 2006: 250.
Hammerella (Interoppia) ramirezi: Subías 2008: 237.
Hammerella (Bornemisszaella) ramirezi: Ermilov, Shtanchaeva, Subías & Anichkin 2012: 160.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes, Balogh Collection, Budapest.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Hammerella (Bornemisszaella) salasi*
(P. Balogh, 1994)**

Bornemisszaella salasi P. Balogh, 1994: 17, figs 4–6.
Bornemisszaella salasi: Schatz 2006: 251.
Hammerella (Interoppia) salasi: Subías 2008: 237.
Hammerella (Bornemisszaella) salasi: Ermilov, Shtanchaeva, Subías & Anichkin 2012: 160.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes, Balogh Collection, Budapest.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

LYROPPIIDAE BALOGH, 1983

***Lyroppia* Balogh, 1961**

***Lyroppia anareolata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

Lyroppia anareolata Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 80, figs 85–88.
Lyroppia anareolata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 54.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.
Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Lyroppia neotropica* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Lyroppia neotropica Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 15, figs 11A–C.
Lyroppia neotropica: P. Balogh 1988c: 323.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype (except where no paratypes representing the species are available) is deposited in the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba, while the paratypes and the exceptions mentioned above are in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Lyroppia scutigera* Balogh, 1961**

Lyroppia scutigera Balogh, 1961c: 3, figs 1–3.
Lyroppia scutigera: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 97.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes. No data on deposition.
Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Lyroppia similis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

Lyroppia similis Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 22, fig. 17.
Lyroppia similis: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 54.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.
Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

MACHADOBELBIDAE BALOGH, 1972

***Machadobelba* Balogh, 1958**

***Machadobelba ceylonica* Balogh, 1970**

Machadobelba ceylonica Balogh, 1970a: 56, figs 38–39.
Machadobelba ceylonica: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 880.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Machadobelba dispar* Balogh, 1958**

Machadobelba dispar Balogh, 1958: 13.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Machadobelba neotropica* P. Balogh, 1988**

Machadobelba neotropica P. Balogh, 1988c: 333, fig. 30.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Machadobelba simplex* Csiszár, 1961**

Machadobelba simplex Csiszár, 1961a: 351, 17–18.

Machadobelba simplex: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 122.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fifteen paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One and 13 specimens respectively in two vials.

Remarks. The vials lack the usual type markings however, the locality is the same as in the publication and sp. n. is also written on the labels. The single specimen should be the holotype and the vial with the 13 specimens are the paratypes.

***Machadobelba symmetrica* Balogh, 1958**

Machadobelba symmetrica Balogh, 1958: 13.

Machadobelba symmetrica: Balogh 1959c: 14, figs 4–5.

Machadobelba symmetrica: Pérez-Iñigo 1969: 414, fig. 21.

Machadobelba symmetrica: Ermilov & Rybalov 2019b: 236.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Machadobelba tuberculata* Csiszár, 1961**

Machadobelba tuberculata Csiszár, 1961a: 352, fig. 19.

Machadobelba tuberculata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 122.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and a paratype.

Deposited in HNHM: Two vials, each with one specimen.

Remarks. There is no indication which is the holotype and the paratype.

***Rioppia* Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

***Rioppia nodulifera* Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

Rioppia nodulifera Balogh & Mahunka, 1977b: 259, fig. 8.

Rioppia nodulifera: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 47.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

OPPIIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1951

ARCOPIINAE BALOGH, 1983

***Arcoppia* Hammer, 1977**

***Acroppia amazonica* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Stachyoppia amazonica Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 52, fig. 42.

Acroppia amazonica: Balogh 1983: 30.

Acroppia amazonica: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 372.

Acroppia amazonica: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 47.

Stachyoppia cf. amazonica: Baert 2018: 410.

Acroppia amazonica: Subías 2023: 223.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. The holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

***Arcoppia arcualis novaeguineae* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Arcoppia arcualis novaeguineae J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 54, figs 49–50.

Arcoppia arcualis novaeguineae: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 98.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Arcoppia biflagellata* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Arcoppia biflagellata J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986b: 276, figs 29–31.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

Remarks. According to the original description there are only three paratypes.

***Arcoppia cronus papua* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Arcoppia cronus papua J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 52, figs 42–44.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Arcoppia curtipila* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Arcoppia curtipila J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 52, figs 45–46.

Arcoppia curtipila: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 98.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Arcoppia fenestralis orientalis* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Arcoppia fenestralis orientalis J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 56, figs 51–52.

Arcoppia fenestralis orientalis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 98.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

Remarks. Paratype is not mentioned in the original publication.

***Arcoppia incerta* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Arcoppia incerta J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 93, figs 12A–C.

Arcoppia incerta: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 99.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes.

***Arcoppia kaindicola* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Arcoppia kaindicola J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 48, figs 37–38.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Six paratypes.

Remarks. In the original publication there are only two paratypes mentioned.

***Arcoppia longisetosa* Balogh, 1982**

Arcoppia longisetosa Balogh, 1982: 5, figs 8–13.

Arcoppia longisetosa: Subías & P. Balogh 1998: 374.

Arcoppia longisetosa: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 135.

Arcoppia longisetosa: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 99.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, and three paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Arcoppia mcadami* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Arcoppia mcadami J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 50, figs 39–40.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Acroppia processigera* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)**

Stachyoppia processigera Balogh & Mahunka, 1967b: 36, figs 3–4.

? *Stachyoppia processigera:* Balogh 1970b: 303, pl. V, figs 29–30.

Acroppia processigera: Balogh 1983: 30, 11.1.

Acroppia processigera: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 372.

Acroppia processigera: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 135.

Acroppia processigera: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 112.

Acroppia papua J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 182.
nom. nov. **Nomen nudum.**

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. J. Balogh & P. Balogh (2002) provided a replacement name *Acroppia papua* for *A. processigera* Balogh, 1970. However, *A. processigera* Balogh, 1970 does not exist. Balogh (1970b: 303) reported a single specimen of *Stachyoppia processigera* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967 (now *Acroppia*) from New Guinea however, with a question mark before the species' name. It can be concluded that Balogh (1970) was uncertain about the identity of this specimen and later J. Balogh & P. Balogh (2002) considered it a misidentification. However, the use of "nom. nov." in this case is clearly misleading and renders this name nomen nudum and unavailable under ICZN 16.1 and 16A. Further study is required to determine if this is indeed a new species.

***Acroppia praearcuata* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Acroppia praearcuata J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 50, figs 41–42.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Acroppia rangifer* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Acroppia rangifer J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 54, figs 47–48.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and eleven paratypes.

***Acroppia serrulata* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1980)**

Oppia serrulata Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 38, figs 8A–B.

Acroppia serrulata: Balogh 1983: 34.

Acroppia serrulata: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 374.

Acroppia serrulata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 99.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and eleven paratypes.

***Acroppia translamellata* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1966)**

Stachyoppia translamellata Balogh & Mahunka, 1966b: 30, figs 11–12.

Acroppia translamellata: Balogh 1983: 30.

Acroppia translamellata: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 373.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-79-67/Afr) and one paratype (0-80-67/Afr).

***Acroppia waterhousei* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Acroppia waterhousei J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 92, figs 11A–C.

Acroppia waterhousei: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 126.

Acroppia waterhousei: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 100.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes.

***Basidoppia* Mahunka, 1983**

***Basidoppia angolensis* (Balogh, 1958)**

Oppia angolensis Balogh, 1958: 15.

Oppia angolensis Balogh 1961a: 71, figs 15–19.

Basidoppia (Basidoppia) angolensis: Mahunka 1999: 251, figs 31–33.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes (Balogh 1961a) Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. No hopotypes or paratypes are designated in the original description. The later designation (Balogh 1961a) is invalid (ICZN 1961 Art. 73), therefore all specimens in the type series should be considered as syntypes.

***Porrhoppia* Balogh, 1970**

***Porrhoppia crux* Balogh, 1970**

Porrhoppia crux Balogh, 1970a: 52, figs 31–32.
Porrhoppia crux: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 880.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Similoppia (Reductoppia)* P. Balogh, 1984**

***Similoppia (Reductoppia) espeletiae* (P. Balogh, 1984)**

Reductoppia espeletiae P. Balogh, 1984a: 44, figs 10A–D.
Similoppia (Reductoppia) espeletiae: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 371.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Eight "types".

Remarks. The holotype and paratypes are kept together and the holotype specimen undistinguishable from the paratypes.

BRACHIOPIINAE SUBÍAS, 1989

***Brachioppia* Hammer, 1961**

***Brachioppia guarani* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1981)**

Oppia guarani Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 83, figs 96–99.
Brachioppia guarani: Balogh 1983: 35.
Brachioppia guarani: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 375.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Brachioppia pseudocostulata* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Oppia pseudocostulata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 50, fig. 37.
Oppia pseudocostulata: Balogh & Mahunka 1977a: 18, fig. 14.
Brachioppia pseudocostulata: Balogh 1983: 35.
Brachioppia pseudocostulata: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 375.
Brachioppia pseudocostulata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 49.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Brachyoppia trigloch* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1977)**

Oppia trigloch Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 21, fig. 16.
Brachyoppia trigloch: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 375.
Brachyoppia trigloch: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 49.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG, one paratype ZIL.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and ten paratypes.

***Brachioppiella (Brachioppiella)* Hammer, 1961**

***Brachioppiella (Brachioppiella) biseriata* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1975)**

Oppia biseriata Balogh & Mahunka, 1975: 248, figs 5A–C.
Brachioppiella biseriata: Balogh 1983: 43.
Brachioppiella (Brachioppiella) biseriata: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 375.
Brachioppiella (Brachioppiella) biseriata: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 130.
Brachioppiella (Brachioppiella) biseriata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 100.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype CSIRO Canberra, one paratype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Brachyoppiella (Brachioppiella) hannecarti*
J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Brachyoppiella hannecarti J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 312, fig 8.

Brachyoppiella (Brachioppiella) hannecarti: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 375.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Four "types".

Remarks. Although the original description states that the species is described on the basis of a holotype and a paratype, we have found in the collection a vial labelled 'types' containing four specimens. They should therefore be considered as syntypes.

Brachioppiella (Gresittoppia) Balogh, 1983

***Brachioppiella (Gresittoppia) pernettyae*
(P. Balogh, 1988)**

Solenoppia pernettyae P. Balogh, 1988a: 112, figs 5–6.

Solenoppia (Campbelloppia) pernettyae: Subías 2004: 124.

Brachioppiella (Gresittoppia) pernettyae: Fredes 2018: 78.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Brachioppiella (Gresittoppia) usheri* (P. Balogh,
1988)**

Solenoppia usheri P. Balogh, 1988a: 112, figs 7–9.

Brachioppiella (Gressittoppia) usheri: Subías 2004: 122.

Brachioppiella (Gressittoppia) usheri: Fredes 2018: 79.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Brassoppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Brassoppia (Brassoppia) brassi* (Balogh, 1982)**

Oppia brassi Balogh, 1982: 7, figs 14–16.

Brassoppia brassi: Balogh 1983: 55, fig. 25.3.

Brassoppia (Brassoppia) brassi: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 370.

Brassoppia brassi: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 132.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, and a paratype with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

***Brassoppia (Brassoppia) lamellata* J. Balogh &
P. Balogh, 1986**

Brassoppia lamellata J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 56, figs 53–55.

Brassoppia lamellata: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 376.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

Remarks. According to the original publication the type series consists of three specimens. We have found a holotype and five specimens labelled as paratypes.

***Ctenoppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Ctenoppia eupectinata* (Balogh & Mahunka,
1975)**

Oppia eupectinata Balogh & Mahunka, 1975: 247, figs 4A–C.

Ctenoppia eupectinata: Balogh 1983: 35.

Ctenoppia eupectinata: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 376.

Ctenoppia eupectinata: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 132.

Type material in the literature. Holotype CSIRO Canberra, one paratype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Ctenoppia variopectinata* (Balogh & Mahunka,
1975)**

Oppia variopectinata Balogh & Mahunka, 1975: 246, figs 3A–C.

Ctenoppia variopectinata: Balogh 1983: 35.

Ctenoppia variopectinata: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 376.

Ctenoppia variopectinata: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 133.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes CSIRO Canberra, six paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Gittella* Hammer, 1961**

***Gittella maxima* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1981)**

Multioppia maxima Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 81, figs 89–92.

Gittella maxima: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 377.

Gittella maxima: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 50.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Kokoppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Kokoppia dudichi* (Balogh, 1982)**

Oppia dudichi Balogh, 1982: 7, figs 17–19.

Kokoppia dudichi: Subías & P. Balogh, 1989: 379.

Kokoppia dudichi: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 133.

Kokoppia dudichi: Ermilov & Hugo-Coetzee 2019: 294.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Kokoppia euramosa* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Oppia euramosa Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 267, fig. 21.

Kokoppia euramosa: Balogh 1983: 36.

Kokoppia euramosa: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 379.

Kokoppia euramosa: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 50.

Kokoppia euramosa: Ermilov & Hugo-Coetzee 2019: 294.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Trapezoppia* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Trapezoppia longipectinata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Trapezoppia longipectinata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 53, figs 44–45.

Trapezoppia longipectinata: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 389.

Trapezoppia longipectinata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 53.

Trapezoppia longipectinata: Fredes 2018: 92.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty two paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Seven paratypes.

LANCEOPPIINAE BALOGH, 1983

***Basiloppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Basiloppia hexatracha* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1975)**

Oppia hexatracha Balogh & Mahunka, 1975: 254, figs 10A–C.

Basiloppia hexatracha: Balogh 1983: 52.

Basiloppia hexatracha: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 374.

Basiloppia hexatracha: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 122.

Type material in the literature. Holotype CSIRO Canberra, one paratype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Chavinia* Hammer, 1961**

***Chavinia similis* P. Balogh, 1984**

Chavinia similis P. Balogh, 1984a: 42, figs 8A–D.

Chavinia similis: Akrami 2015: 474.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Eight "types".

Remarks. It seems that the holotype and paratypes were not separated therefore, these eight specimens should be regarded as syntypes.

Cycloppia Balogh, 1983

**Cycloppia latisternum J. Balogh & P. Balogh,
1986**

Cycloppia latisternum J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 59, figs 59–61.

Type material in the literature. Holotype.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and fifteen paratypes.

Remarks. The original description was based on a single holotype. The 15 specimens labelled as paratypes – although their locality is the same as that of the holotype – are of no nomenclatural value.

Cycloppia szentirmayi (Balogh, 1970)

Oppia szentirmayi Balogh, 1970b: 301, pl. IV. fig. 25, pl. V. fig. 26.

Cycloppia szentirmayi: Balogh 1983: 55.

Cycloppia szentirmayi: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1986a: 60.

Cycloppia szentirmayi: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 376.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Geminoppia J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983

**Geminoppia papineau J. Balogh & P. Balogh,
1983**

Geminoppia papineau J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 315, fig. 10.

Geminoppia papineau: Ermilov, Hugo-Coetzee & Khaustov 2021: 213.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Balogh Collection.

HNHM: One paratype.

Globoppia Hammer, 1962

Globoppia brinoni J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983

Globoppia brinoni J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 314, fig. 9.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: One "type".

Remarks. The holotype and paratype are from the same locality. It is not certain whether this single specimen is the holotype or the paratype.

**Globoppia heterotricha (Balogh & Mahunka,
1969)**

Oppia heterotricha Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 267, fig. 22.

Globoppia heterotricha: Balogh 1983: 41.

Globoppia heterotricha: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 378.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Lanceoppia (Convergoppia) Balogh, 1983

**Lanceoppia (Convergoppia) australis (Balogh,
1982)**

Teratoppia australis Balogh, 1982: 3, figs 1–3.

Lanceoppia (Convergoppia) australis Colloff & Halliday 1998: 124. comb. nov.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, and two paratypes without deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Lanceoppia (Hamoppia) Hammer, 1968

Lanceoppia (Hamoppia) soosi (Balogh, 1982)

Oppia soosi Balogh, 1982: 9, figs 20–24.

Lanceoppia soosi: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 369.

Lanceoppia (Hamoppia) soosi: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 124.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia)* Hammer, 1962**

***Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) kovacsi* (Balogh & Csiszár, 1963)**

Oppia kovacsi Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 479, fig. 23.
Globoppia kovacsi: Balogh 1983: 41.
Globoppia kovacsi: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 377.
Lanceoppia (Lancelalmoppia) kovacsi: Fredes 2018: 83.
Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) kovacsi: Subías 2023: 187.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nine paratypes. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes (0-1161-68/Afr, one is broken).

Remarks. There is a Reg. No. in the vial of the paratypes which refers to an African locality, however this species was described from South America.

***Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) lancearia* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1975)**

Oppia lancearia Balogh & Mahunka, 1975: 250, figs 6A–C.
Lanceoppia lancearia: Balogh 1983: 38.
Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) lancearia: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 379
Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) lancearia: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 125.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one partype CSIRO Canberra, three partypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) microlancearia* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1975)**

Oppia microlancearia Balogh & Mahunka, 1975: 251, figs 7A–C.
Lanceoppia microlancearia: Balogh 1983: 38.
Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) microlancearia: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 379.
Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) microlancearia: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 125.

Type material in the literature. Holotype CSIRO Canberra, one partype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) microtricha* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1975)**

Oppia microtricha Balogh & Mahunka, 1975: 252, figs 8: A–C.
Lanceoppia microtricha: Balogh 1983: 38.
Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) microtricha: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 379.
Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) microtricha: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 126.

Type material in the literature. Holotype CSIRO Canberra, one partype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) microtrichoides* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1975)**

Oppia microtrichoides Balogh & Mahunka, 1975: 253, figs 9A–C.
Lanceoppia microtrichoides: Balogh 1983: 38.
Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) microtrichoides: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 379.
Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) microtrichoides: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 126.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one partype CSIRO Canberra, three partypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Membranoppia* Hammer, 1968**

***Membranoppia (Pravoppia) argentinensis* (Balogh & Csiszár, 1963)**

Oppia argentinensis Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 479, fig. 19.
Globoppia argentinensis: Balogh 1983: 41.
Membranoppia (Pravoppia) argentinensis: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 381.
Membranoppia (Pravoppia) argentinensis: Kun et. al., 2010: 33.
Membranoppia (Pravoppia) argentinensis: Fredes 2018: 84.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Otoppia Balogh, 1983

***Otoppia midas* (Balogh, 1962)**

Otoppia midas Balogh, 1962e: 132, figs 20–22.
Otoppia midas: Balogh 1983: 42, fig. 17.5.
Otoppia midas: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 385.

Type material in the literature. Holotype l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Processoppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Processoppia sphagnicola* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986)**

Rhaphoppia sphagnicola J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 58, figs 56–58.
Processoppia sphagnicola: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 385.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes; no deposition stated.
Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Setoppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Setoppia antennata* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1966)**

Oppia antennata Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 14, figs 23–24.
Setoppia antennata: Balogh 1983: 39.
Setoppia antennata: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 388.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and thirteen paratypes NM, thirteen paratypes HNHM.
Deposited in HNHM: Nine paratypes (0-113-67/Afr).

***Setoppia bornemisszai* (Balogh, 1982)**

Oppia bornemisszai Balogh, (1982: 13, figs 34–36.)
Setoppia bornemisszai: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 388.
Setoppia bornemisszai: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 127.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, and a paratype with no data on deposition.
Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Setoppia compressa* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1975)**

Oppia compressa Balogh & Mahunka, 1975: 244, figs 1A–C.
Setoppia compressa: Balogh 1983: 39.
Setoppia compressa: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 388.
Setoppia compressa: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 127.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes CSIRO Canberra, five paratypes HNHM.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Setoppia fortis* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1966)**

Oppia fortis Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 14, figs 25–26.
Setoppia fortis: Balogh 1983: 39.
Setoppia fortis: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 388.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and thirty eight paratypes NM, thirty eight paratypes HNHM.
Deposited in HNHM: Forty-one paratypes (0-96-67/Afr).

***Setoppia longisetosa* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1975)**

Oppia longisetosa Balogh & Mahunka, 1975: 245, figs 2A–B.
Setoppia longisetosa: Balogh 1983: 39.
Setoppia longisetosa: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 388.
Setoppia longisetosa: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 128.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype CSIRO Canberra, two paratypes HNHM.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Setoppia strinovichi* (Balogh, 1982)**

Oppia strinovichi Balogh, 1982: 9, figs 25–27.
Setoppia strinovichi: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 388.
Setoppia strinovichi: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 128.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.
Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Setoppia toeroeki* (Balogh, 1982)**

Oppia toroki Balogh, 1982: 13, figs 31–33.
Setoppia toeroeki: Balogh 1983: 39, fig. 16.6.
Setoppia toeroeki: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 388.
Setoppia toroki: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 128.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, and one paratype with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Setoppia toxotes* (Balogh, 1982)**

Oppia toxotes Balogh, 1982: 11, figs 28–30.
Setoppia toxotes: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 388.
Setoppia toxotes: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 128.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, and one paratype with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

Remarks. The original description reports only a single paratype.

***Trematoppia* Balogh, 1964**

***Trematoppia cristipes* Balogh, 1962**

Trematoppia cristipes Balogh, 1962e: 135, figs 23–25.
Trematoppia cristipes: Balogh 1983: 40.
Trematoppia cristipes: Subías & Balogh 1989: 389.
Trematoppia cristipes: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Type material in the literature. Holotype l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

MEDIOPPIINAE SUBÍAS ET MÍNGUEZ, 1985

***Cognoppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Congoppia deboiszezoni* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1966)**

Oppia deboiszezoni Balogh & Mahunka, 1966b: 30, figs 9–10.
Congoppia deboiszezoni: Balogh 1983: 47, fig 22.3
Congoppia deboiszezoni: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 376.
Congoppia deboiszezoni: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 102.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-77-67/Afr) and two paratypes (0-78-67/Afr).

***Discoppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Discoppia limae* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1974)**

Oppia limae Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 245, figs 2A–C.

Discoppia limae: Balogh 1983: 55., fig. 25.5.

Discoppia (Discoppia) limae: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 376.

Discoppia limae: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 127.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

remarks. The usual holotype marking is missing, but the label is marked as "sp. n."

***Ramuloppia* Balogh, 1961**

***Ramuloppia ramiseta* (Balogh, 1959)**

Oppia ramiseta Balogh, 1959b: 96, figs 11–14.
Ramuloppia ramiseta: Balogh 1983: 37, fig. 15.10.
Ramuloppia ramiseta: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 386.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

MULTIOPPIINAE BALOGH, 1983

***Condyloppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Condyloppia pilosella* (Balogh, 1959)**

Oppia pilosella Balogh, 1959b: 93, figs 1–2.
Cilioppia pilosella: Balogh 1983: 51.
Condyloppia pilosella: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 376.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren, and four paratypes Musée de Dundo and ELTE.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Cryptoppia* Csiszár, 1961**

***Cryptoppia elongata* Csiszár, 1961**

Cryptoppia elongata Csiszár, 1961a: 351, figs 15–16.
Cryptoppia elongata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 128.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Cryptoppia mahunkai* (Wang & Li, 1997)**

Pulchroppia elegans Mahunka, 1988: 852, figs 63–65.
Pulchroppia mahunkai Wang & Li, 1997: 117.
Pulchroppia mahunkarum J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 199, pls: 276: 12, 277: 1. **nom. nov.**
Cryptoppia mahunkai: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 128.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes MHNG, one paratype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. *Pulchroppia elegans* Mahunka, 1988 is a primary homonym of *Pulchroppia elegans* Hammer, 1979 and permanently invalid (ICZN Art. 57.1). Wang & Li (1997) provided a replacement name *Pulchroppia mahunkai* but it was overlooked by J. Balogh & P. Balogh (2002) who provided a second replacement name *Pulchroppia mahunkarum*.

***Cubaoppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Cubaoppia fusisetosa* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1980)**

Oppia fusisetosa Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 36, figs 7A–B.
Cubaoppia fusisetosa: Balogh 1983: 47, fig. 22.4.
Cubaoppia fusisetosa: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 372.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Multioppia* (*Hammeroppia*) Vasiliu & Ivan, 2009**

***Multioppia* (*Hammeroppia*) *translamellaris* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Multioppia translamellaris J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 45, figs 30–31.
Multioppia (*Hammeroppia*) *translamellaris*: Subías 2011: 216.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Helioppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Helioppia sol* (Balogh, 1959)**

Oppia sol Balogh, 1959b: 93: figs 3–5.
Helioppia sol: Balogh 1983: 56, fig. 25.8.
Helioppia sol: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 378.
Helioppia sol: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 104.
Helioppia sol: Ermilov, Stanchaeva & Subías 2022: 379.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, á Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Multioppia* (*Multioppia*) Hammer, 1961**

***Multioppia* (*Multioppia*) *pauciramosa* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Multioppia pauciramosa J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 46, figs 32–33.
Multioppia pauciramosa: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 382.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Octoppia* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Octoppia irmayi* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Octoppia irmayi Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 12, figs 29–30.
Octoppia irmayi: Balogh 1983: 44.
Octoppia irmayi: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 372, 384.
Octoppia irmayi: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 51.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty three paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and thirty paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description only twenty three paratypes are mentioned.

***Pseudoamerioppia* Subías, 1989**

***Pseudoamerioppia circumciliata* (Balogh, 1959)**

Oppia deficiens circumciliata Balogh, 1959b: 96, fig. 8.

Amerioppia deficiens circumciliata: Balogh 1983: 46.

Pseudoamerioppia deficiens circumciliata: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 386.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren, and two paratypes Musée de Dundo and ELTE.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Pseudoamerioppia paraguayensis* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1981)**

Oppia barrancensis paraguayensis Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 81, figs 93–95.

Amerioppia barrancensis paraguayensis: Balogh 1983: 45.

Pseudoamerioppia barrancensis paraguayensis: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 386.

Amerioppia paraguayensis: Mahunka 1998: 844.

Pseudoamerioppia paraguayensis: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 52.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Ramusella (Insculptoppia)* Subías, 1980**

***Ramusella (Insculptoppia) merimna* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1977)**

Oppia merimna Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 16, fig. 13.

Insculptoppia merimna: Balogh 1983: 48.

Ramusella (Insculptoppia) merimna: Balogh & P. Balogh 1989: 387.

Ramusella (Insculptoppia) merimna: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 52.

Ramusella (Insculptoppia) merimna: Fredes 2018: 89.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype ZIL.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Ramusella (Insculptoppia) pocsi* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)**

Oppia pocsi Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 46, pl. IV. figs 21–22.

Rectoppia pocsi: Balogh 1983: 50.

Ramusella (Ramusella) pocsi: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 387.

Ramusella (Insculptoppia) pocsi: Corpuz-Raros & Er-milov 2020: 105.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-35-67/As).

***Ramusella (Insculptoppia) soror* (Balogh, 1958)**

Oppia soror Balogh, 1958: 14.

Oppia soror: Balogh 1961a: 69, figs 8–9.

Insculptoppia soror: Balogh 1983: 48.

Ramusella (Insculptoppia) soror: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 386.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Three paratypes (0-1167-68/Afr)

Remarks. In the original description there is no holotype selected therefore, all the specimen should be regarded syntypes.

Ramusella (Ramusella) Hammer, 1962

***Ramusella (Ramusella) cordobensis* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1968)**

Oppia cordobensis Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 326, figs 14–15.

Oppia cordobensis: Balogh & Mahunka 1977a: 14, fig. 11.

Rectoppia cordobensis: Balogh 1983: 50.

Ramusella (Ramusella) cordobensis: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 387.

Ramusella (Ramusella) cordobensis: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 53.

Ramusella (Ramusella) cordobensis: Fredes 2018: 89.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty four paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited also in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-389-68/D-Am) and eighteen paratypes (0-390-68/D-Am).

Ramusella (Rectoppia) Subías, 1980

Ramusella (Rectoppia) incisiva (Balogh & Mahunka, 1980)

Oppia incisiva Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 38, figs 7C–E.

Rectoppia incisiva: Balogh 1983: 50.

Ramusella (Rectoppia) incisiva: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 387

Type material in the literature. Holotype and sixteen paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNH.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and fifteen paratypes.

Remarks. There are two specimens in the vial marked holotype. It appears that one of the paratypes was also placed in the vial of the holotype. Expert revision is needed to select the true holotype, if this is possible at all.

Ramusella (Rectoppia) radiata (Balogh, 1961)

Oppia radiata Balogh, 1961b: 520, fig. 4.

Rectoppia radiata: Balogh 1983: 50.

Ramusella (Rectoppia) radiata: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 387.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM, and three paratypes with no deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

MYSTROPPINIAE BALOGH, 1983

Karenella (Glabroppia) Subías & Rodríguez, 1986

Karenella (Glabroppia) cohici (Balogh & Mahunka, 1966)

Oppia cohici Balogh & Mahunka, 1966b: 28, fig. 8.

Karenella (Glabroppia) cohici: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 378.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-91-67/Afr) and ten paratypes (0-92-67/Afr).

Remarks. In the original description only five paratypes are mentioned.

Karenella (Karenella) Hammer, 1962

Karenella (Karenella) acuta (Csiszár, 1961)

Oppia acuta Csiszár, 1961a: 350, figs 11–12.

Karenella acuta: Balogh 1983: 53.

Karenella (Karenella) acuta: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 131.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Karenella (Karenella) lanceoseta (Balogh, 1959)

Oppia lanceoseta Balogh, 1959b: 96, figs 9–10.

Karenella lanceoseta: Balogh 1983: 53.

Karenella (Karenella) lanceoseta: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 378.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Mystroppia Balogh, 1959

Mystroppia sellnicki Balogh, 1959

Mystroppia sellnicki Balogh, 1959a: 33, figs 7–9.

Mystroppia sellnicki: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 368.

Mystroppia sellnicki: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 192.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and many paratypes, ELTE.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

***Stachyoppia* Balogh, 1961**

***Stachyoppia muscicola* Balogh, 1961**

Stachyoppia muscicola Balogh, 1961c: 5, figs 4–5.

Stachyoppia muscicola: Balogh 1983: fig. 11.4.

Stachyoppia muscicola: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 386.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Striatoppia* Balogh, 1958**

***Striatoppia machadoi* Balogh, 1958**

Striatoppia machadoi Balogh, 1958: 16.

Striatoppia machadoi: Balogh 1983: 31.

Striatoppia machadoi: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 388.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, á Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Striatoppia madagascarensis* Balogh, 1961**

Striatoppia madagascarensis Balogh, 1961d: 19, figs 18–19.

Striatoppia madagascarensis: Balogh 1983: 32.

Striatoppia madagascarensis: Subías & Balogh 1989: 388.

Striatoppia madagascarensis: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Striatoppia madagascarensis: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Striatoppia madagascarensis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 185, pl. 257. figs 10–11.

Striatoppia madagascarensis: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012: 44.

Striatoppia madagascarensis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 107.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Striatoppia margaritifera* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Striatoppia margaritifera Balogh & Mahunka, 1966b: 32, figs 13–14.

Striatoppia margaritifera: Balogh 1983: 32.

Striatoppia margaritifera: Subías & Balogh 1989: 388.

Striatoppia margaritifera: Ermilov & Rybalov 2019b: 237.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-115-67/Afr).

***Striatoppia opuntiseta* Balogh & Mahunka, 1968**

Striatoppia opuntiseta Balogh & Mahunka, 1968b: 342, figs 3–4.

Striatoppia opuntiseta: Balogh 1983: 32.

Striatoppia opuntiseta: Subías & Balogh 1989: 388.

Striatoppia opuntiseta: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 53.

Striatoppia opuntiseta: Fredes 2018: 91.

Striatoppia opuntiseta: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 32.

Striatoppia opuntiseta: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 108.

Striatoppia opuntiseta: Ermilov *et al.* (2021a): 153.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, one paratype NSMT.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-203-67).

***Striatoppia papillata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Striatoppia papillata Balogh & Mahunka, 1966b: 32, figs 15–16.

Striatoppia papillata: Balogh 1983: 32.

Striatoppia papillata: Subías & Balogh 1989: 388.

Striatoppia papillata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 108.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nineteen paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-93-67/Afr) and fourteen paratypes (0-94-67/Afr).

***Striatoppia tribuliformis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

Striatoppia tribuliformis Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 86, figs 103–106.

Striatoppia tribuliformis: Balogh 1983: 32.

Striatoppia tribuliformis: Subías & Balogh 1989: 388.

Striatoppia tribuliformis: Fredes 2018: 90.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and ten paratypes.

OPPIELLINAE SENICZAK, 1975

***Elaphoppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Elaphoppia lapelerii* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Elaphoppia lapelerii J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 309, fig. 6.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Two "types".

Remarks. The original description states that the species is described on the basis of a holotype and six paratypes. In the collection we found a vial labelled "Types" containing two specimens. They may represent paratypes.

***Elaphoppia quadripilosa* (Balogh, 1960)**

Oppia quadripilosa Balogh, 1961d: 18: figs 16–17.

Elaphoppia quadripilosa: Balogh 1983: 25, fig. 9.4.

Elaphoppia quadripilosa: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 377.

Elaphoppia quadripilosa: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 109.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Liacaroppia* Subías & Rodríguez, 1986**

***Liacaroppia doryphoros* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983)**

Oppiella doryphoros J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 308, fig. 5.

Liacaroppia doryphoros: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 380.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Tripiloppia* Hammer, 1968**

***Tripiloppia Subiasi* Balogh, 1982**

Tripiloppia subiasi Balogh, 1982: 5, figs 4–7.

Tripiloppia subiasi: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 120.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, and one paratype with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

OPPIINAE SELLNICK, 1975

***Aethioppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Aethioppia bacilligera* (Balogh, 1962)**

Oppia bacilligera Balogh, 1962d: 101, figs 17–18.

Aethioppia bacilligera: Balogh 1983: 54, fig. 25.2.

Aethioppia bacilligera: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 371.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Aethioppia spinipes* (Balogh, 1962)**

Oppia spinipes Balogh, 1962e: 131, figs 16–19.

Aethioppia spinipes: Balogh 1983: 54.

Aethioppia spinipes: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 373.

Type material in the literature. Holotype l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar, and one paratype with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Amerioppia Hammer, 1961

Amerioppia meruensis (Balogh, 1961)

Oppia meruensis Balogh, 1961b: 519, fig. 3.
Amerioppia meruensis: Balogh 1983: 46.
Amerioppia meruensis: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 374.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM and two paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Erioppia Balogh, 1983

Erioppia problematica pacifica J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986

Erioppia problematica pacifica J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986b: 278, figs 32–35.
Erioppia problematica pacifica: Ermilov & Starý 2020: 451.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

Erioppia problematica problematica (Balogh, 1966)

Multioppia problematica Balogh, 1966: 70, fig. 4.
Erioppia problematica: J. Balogh 1983: 46.
Erioppia problematica: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1986b: 265.
Erioppia problematica pacifica: Ermilov & Starý 2020: 451.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-119-67/Afr) and one paratype (0-144-67/Afr).

Exanthoppia J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983

Exanthoppia ornatissima J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983

Exanthoppia ornatissima J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 317, fig. 11.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Balogh Collection eventually to be incorporated in the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Two "types".

Remarks The original description states that the species is described on the basis of a holotype and a paratype. In the collection we found a vial labelled "Types" containing two specimens. They should therefore be considered as syntypes.

Fusuloppia Balogh, 1983

Fusuloppia fusuligera (Balogh, 1962)

Oppia fusuligera Balogh, 1962d: 102, figs 19–21.
Fusuloppia fusuligera: Balogh 1983: 51.
Fusuloppia fusuligera: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 377.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes, Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. There is a vial in the HNHM with a single specimen labelled *Oppia fusuligera* "sp. n." and the locality, Tanganyika, Ngorongoro, is identical to that of the paratypes.

Fusuloppia simplex (Balogh, 1962)

Oppia simplex Balogh, 1962e: 129, figs 14–15.
Fusuloppia simplex: Balogh 1983: 51, fig. 23.3.
Fusuloppia simplex: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 377.
Fusuloppia neonominata Subías, 2004: 113.
Oppia concolor grp. nr. *simplex*: Behan-Pelletier & Lindo 2019: 90.

Type material in the literature. Holotype l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique de Madagascar, and two paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Goyoppia Balogh, 1983

Goyoppia sexpilosa (Balogh, 1961)

Oppia sexpilosa Balogh, 1961d: 17, figs 16–17.
Goyoppia sexpilosa: Balogh 1983: 53, 24.4.
Goyoppia sexpilosa: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 377.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes, no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1168-68/Afr).

Heteroppia (Heteroppia) Balogh, 1970

Heteroppia (Heteroppia) globigera Balogh, 1970

Heteroppia globigera Balogh, 1970a: 50, figs 29–30.

Heteroppia globigera: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 880.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

Lasiobelba (Antennoppia) Mahunka, 1983

Lasiobelba (Antennoppia) insignis Balogh, 1970

Lasiobelba insignis Balogh, 1970b: 302, pl. V, figs 27–28.

Lasiobelba (Antennoppia) insignis: Ermilov, Stan-chaeva, Subías & Martens 2014: 13.

Antennoppia insignis: Ermilov, Martens & Kontschán 2021: 225. comb. nov.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii),

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Lasiobelba (Lasiobelba) Aoki, 1959

Lasiobelba (Lasiobelba) kuehnelti (Csiszár, 1961)

Oppia kuehnelti Csiszár, 1961a: 350, figs 13–14.

Cilioppia kuehnelti: Balogh 1983: 51.

Oppia kuehnelti: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 384.

Lasiobelba (Lasiobelba) kuehnelti: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 134.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Lasiobelba (Lasiobelba) vietnamica Balogh, 1983

Lasiobelba remota Aoki, 1959: 6, fig. 4.

?*Oppia remota:* Balogh & Mahunka 1967a: 46, fig. 23.

Lasiobelba vietnamica Balogh, 1983: 52. **nom. nov.**

Lasiobelba vietnamica: Ermilov & Corpuz-Raros 2017b: 15.

Lasiobelba vietnamica: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 135.

Type material in the literature. Three syntypes. No deposition is stated.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. Balogh & Mahunka (1967a) reported three specimens under the name ?*Oppia remota* (Aoki, 1959) with some hesitation as to whether they really represent Aoki's species. Later, Balogh (1983) decided that these specimens belong to a new species, which he named *Lasiobelba vietnamica* nom. nov. However, ?*Oppia remota* of Balogh & Mahunka (1967) is not a homonym of *Lasiobelba remota* of Aoki (1959), but only a misidentification. However, as the original publication by Balogh & Mahunka contains a diagnosis and data on the type material, this "nom. nov." is available by indication (ICZN 1961 Art. 16)

Neoamerioppia (Amerigloboppia) Subías, 1987

Neoamerioppia (Amerigloboppia) espeletiarum (P. Balogh, 1984)

Amerioppia espeletiarum P. Balogh, 1984a: 47, figs 12A–D.

Neoamerioppia (Amerigloboppia) espeletiarum: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 382.

Amerioppia espeletiarum: Schatz 2006: 243.

Amerioppia espeletiarum: Baert 2018: 40.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and forty-nine paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Sixty-four "types".

Remarks. As there is a holotype and forty-nine paratypes in the original description, the status of these sixty-four specimens marked as "types" is uncertain. They may be syntypes, as none of the holotypes in the publication of P. Balogh (1984) were actually separated.

Neoamerioppia (Amerigloboppia) senecionis (P. Balogh, 1984)

Amerioppia senecionis P. Balogh, 1984a: 45, figs 11A–D.

Neoamerioppia (Amerigloboppia) senecionis: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 383.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Seven "types".

Remarks. It seems that the holotype and the six paratypes were not separated and therefore these specimens should be considered as syntypes.

Neoamerioppia (Neoamerioppia) Subías, 1989

***Neoamerioppia (Neoamerioppia) cocuyana*
(P. Balogh, 1984)**

Amerioppia cocuyana P. Balogh, 1984a: 47, figs 13A–D.

Neoamerioppia (Neoamerioppia) cocuyana: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 383.

Neoamerioppia cocuyana: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 111.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eleven paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Twelve "types".

Remarks. The holotype and the eleven paratypes were not separated, therefore these specimens should be regarded syntypes.

***Neoamerioppia (Neoamerioppia) deficiens*
(Balogh, 1959)**

Oppia deficiens Balogh, 1959b: 96, figs 6–7.

Amerioppia deficiens: Balogh 1983: 46.

Neoamerioppia (Neoamerioppia) deficiens: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 383.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren, and three paratypes Musée de Dundo and ELTE.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes (0-1173-68/Afr).

***Neoamerioppia (Neoamerioppia) longiclava*
microseta (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986)**

Amerioppia longiclava microseta J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 42, figs 24–25.

Neoamerioppia (Neoamerioppia) longiclava microseta: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 383.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Neoamerioppia (Neoamerioppia) papuana*
(J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986)**

Amerioppia papuana J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 43, figs 28–29.

Neoamerioppia (Neoamerioppia) papuana: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 383.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Neoamerioppia (Neoamerioppia) sturmi*
(P. Balogh, 1984)**

Amerioppia sturmi P. Balogh, 1984a: 51, figs 14A–D.

Neoamerioppia (Neoamerioppia) sturmi: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 383.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Oppia* C. L. Koch, 1835**

***Oppia leleupi* Balogh, 1958**

Oppia leleupi Balogh, 1958: 15.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Paroppia* Hammer, 1968**

***Paroppia breviseta* (Balogh, 1962)**

Oppia breviseta Balogh, 1962d: 100, figs 14–16.

Paroppia breviseta: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 385.

Paroppia breviseta: Ermilov & Hugo-Coetzee 2019: 299.

Paroppia breviseta: Ermilov & Starý 2020: 447.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Paroppia flagellata* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Paroppia flagellata J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 319, fig. 13.

Paroppia flagellata: Subías & P. Balogh, 1989: 385.

Paroppia flagellata: Ermilov & Hugo-Coetzee 2019: 299.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Paroppia hawaiiensis* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Paroppia hawaiiensis J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 318, fig. 12.

Paroppia hawaiiensis: Subías & P. Balogh, 1989: 385.

Paroppia hawaiiensis: Ermilov & Hugo-Coetzee 2019: 299.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Three "types".

Remarks. These three "types" are probably paratypes.

***Sphagnoppia* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

***Sphagnoppia biflagellata* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986**

Sphagnoppia biflagellata J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986a: 48, figs 34–36.

Sphagnoppia biflagellata: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 388, figs 64–65.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Taiwanoppia (Paragloboppia)* Subías, 1989**

***Taiwanoppia (Paragloboppia) trichotos* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1977)**

Oppia trichotos Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 19, fig. 15.

Vietoppia (Paragloboppia) trichotos: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 399.

Taiwanoppia (Paragloboppia) trichotos: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 53.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nine paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG, two paratypes ZIL.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and nine paratypes.

***Wallworkoppia* Subías, 1989**

***Wallworkoppia machadoi* (Balogh, 1958)**

Oppia machadoi Balogh, 1958: 14.

Oppia machadoi: Balogh 1961a: 69, figs 6–7.

Wallworkella machadoi: Balogh 1983: 37

Wallworkoppia machadoi: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 389.

Arcoppia (Wallworkoppia) machadoi: Mahunka 1999: 268, figs 27–30.

Wallworkoppia machadoi: Ermilov & Rybalov 2018: 1833.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Three paratypes.

Remarks. There is no holotype designated in the original description, therefore all specimens of the type series should be considered as syntypes.

OXYOPPIINAE SUBÍAS, 1989

***Lineoppia* J. Balogh & P. Balogh**

***Lineoppia frouini* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Lineoppia frouini J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 311, fig. 7.

Lineoppia frouini: Ermilov & Anichkin 2011: 41.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype (marked just as "type-mat." but the holotype is clearly marked).

***Lineoppia mastax* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1977)**

Oxyoppia mastax Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 23, fig. 18.

Oxyoppia mastax: Balogh & Mahunka 1981: 52.
Lineoppia mastax: Ermilov & Anichkin 2011: 41.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Mahunkella* Balogh, 1983**

***Mahunkella transitoria* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1978)**

Oppiella transitoria Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 280, figs 9A–C.

Mahunkella transitoria: Balogh 1983: 25, fig. 9.6.

Mahunkella transitoria: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 380.

Mahunkella transitoria: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 51.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Oxyoppia (Dzarogneta) Kulijev, 1978

***Oxyoppia (Dzarogneta) latisternalis* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1974)**

Oppia latisternalis Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 13, figs 9A–D.

Oxyoppia (Dzarogneta) latisternalis: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 385.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype (except where no paratypes representing the species are available) are deposited in the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba, while the paratypes and the exceptions mentioned above are in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Oxyoppia (Dzarogneta) pluripectinata* (Balogh, 1958)**

Oppia pluripectinata Balogh, 1958: 14.

Oppia pluripectinata: Balogh 1961a: 71, figs 10–11.

Oxyoppia (Dzarogneta) pluripectinata: Subías & Balogh 1989: 385.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Oxyoppia (Oxyoppia) Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

***Oxyoppia (Oxyoppia) polita* P. Balogh, 1984**

Oxyoppia polita P. Balogh, 1984a: 43, figs 9A–D.

Oxyoppia (Oxyoppia) polita: Subías 2004: 129.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Two "types".

Remarks. These two "types" most probably represent paratypes.

***Oxyoppia (Oxyoppia) spinosa* (Hammer, 1958)**

Oppia spinosa Hammer, 1958: 52, fig. 57.

Oxyoppia spinosa Hammer, 1958: Balogh & Mahunka 1969: 269, fig. 23

Oxyoppia espozi J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 183, pl. 254: 15. **nom nov.** pro *Oxyoppia spinosa* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969 nec *Oppia spinosa* Hammer, 1958.

Oxyoppia spinosa (Hammer, 1958) syn. *Oxyoppia espozi* J and P. Balogh, 2002: Subías 2004: 129.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks: The situation here is somewhat complicated. If the specimens identified by Balogh & Mahunka 1969: 269 as *Oppia spinosa* Hammer, 1958 and selected as type of the genus *Oxyoppia* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969 are indeed not conspecific with *Oppia spinosa* Hammer, then ICZN Art. 11.10 applies.: "If an author employs a specific or subspecific name for the type species of a new nominal genus-group taxon, but deliberately in the sense of a previous misidentification of it, then the author's employment of the name is deemed to denote a new nominal species and the specific name is available with its own author and date as though it were newly proposed in combination with the new genus-group name" Therefore the type of the genus *Oxyoppia* is *Oxyoppia spinosa* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969 and if Hammer's species belongs to *Oxyoppia* a sec-

ondary homonymy arises and the name *Oxyoppia espozi* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002 is valid.

Oxyoppia (Oxyoppiella) Subías & Rodríguez, 1986

Oxyoppia (Oxyoppiella) bituberculata (Balogh, 1958)

Oppia bituberculata Balogh, 1958: 15.
Oppia bituberculata: Balogh 1961a: 71, figs 12–14.
Oxyoppia bituberculata: Balogh 1983: 27.
Oxyoppia (Oxyoppiella) bituberculata: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 385.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Oxyoppia (Oxyoppiella) cubana Balogh & Mahunka, 1980

Oxyoppia cubana Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 40, figs 8C–D.
Oxyoppia (Oxyoppiella) cubana: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 52.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and nine paratypes.

Oxyoppia (Oxyoppiella) pilosa Balogh & Mahunka, 1981

Oxyoppia pilosa Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 85, figs 100–102.
non Oxyoppia (Oxyoppiella) polynesia (Hammer, 1972): Subías 2004: 129.
Oxyoppia (Oxyoppiella) pilosa: Subías 2021: 222.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

Remarks. Subías (2004) synonymised *O. pilosa* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981 with *O. polynesia* (Hammer, 1972) however, later he (Subías 2022) resurrected *O. pilosa* from the synonymy.

Oxyoppia (Oxyoppiella) saskai (Balogh, 1961)

Oppia saskai Balogh, 1961b: 518, fig. 2.
Oxyoppia saskai: Balogh 1983: 28.
Oxyoppia (Oxyoppiella) saskai: Subías & Balogh 1989: 385.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, and two paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Sacculoppia Balogh & Mahunka, 1968

Sacculoppia singularis Balogh & Mahunka, 1968

Sacculoppia singularis Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 326, figs 12–13.
Sacculoppia singularis: Balogh 1983: 29.
Sacculoppia singularis: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 387.
Sacculoppia singularis: Fredes 2018: 90.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty five paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited also in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-366-68/D-Am) and seven paratypes (0-368-68/D-Am), three paratypes (0-369-38/D-Am) and six more paratypes without reg. no.

PULCHROPIINAE BALOGH, 1983

***Multipulchroppia* Subías, 1989**

Multipulchroppia amazonica (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)

Multioppia amazonica Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 10, figs 27–28.
Pulchroppia (Multipulchroppia) amazonica: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 386.
Multipulchroppia amazonica: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 51.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited also in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-556-68/D-Am) and two paratypes (0-872-68/D-Am).

***Multipulchroppia gyoergyi* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Multioppia gyoergyi Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 50, fig. 38.

Pulchroppia (*Multipulchroppia*) *gyoergyi*: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 386.

Multipulchroppia gyoergyi: Subías 2004: 120.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Multipulchroppia pectinata* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)**

Multioppia pectinata Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 47, pl. V, figs 29–30.

Multioppia vietnamica Balogh, 1983: 45. **nom. nov.**

Multipulchroppia pectinata: Subías 2004: 120.

Multipulchroppia pectinata: Ermilov 2015:69.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. Balogh & Mahunka (1967a) described the species *Multioppia pectinata* from Vietnam. In the very same year Aoki (1967) also has published a new species *Multioppia pectinata* from Thailand. Suzuki (1976) recognizing the primary homonymy provided a replacement name for Aoki's species *Multioppia siamensis* Suzuki, 1976. Balogh (1983) obviously overlooked Suzuki's replacement name and provided an unnecessary replacement name for *Multioppia pectinata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967 *Multioppia vietnamica* Balogh, 1983.

***Pulchroppia Hammer*, 1979**

***Pulchroppia pendula* (Balogh, 1970)**

Brachyoppia pendula Balogh, 1970a: 52, figs 33–34.

Pulchroppia (*Pulchroppia*) *pendula*: Subías & P. Balogh 1989: 386.

Pulchroppia pendula: Subías 2004: 120.

Pulchroppia pendula: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 880.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and eight paratypes.

QUADROPPIDAE BALOGH, 1983

***Borhidia* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

***Borhidia andina* P. Balogh, 1988**

Borhidia andina P. Balogh, 1988c: 331, figs 24–26.

Borhidia andina: Subías 2022: 234.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Borhidia cubana* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Borhidia cubana Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 14, figs 10A–D.

Borhidia cubana: Balogh & Mahunka 1980: 22.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and sixty paratypes. The holotype (except where no paratypes representing the species are available) is deposited in the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba, while the paratypes and the exceptions mentioned above are in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and sixty seven paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description there are only sixty paratypes mentioned. Expert verification is required to ensure that all specimens are of the same species.

***Hexoppia* Balogh, 1958**

***Hexoppia heterotricha* Balogh, 1958**

Hexoppia heterotricha Balogh, 1958: 13.

Hexoppia heterotricha: Balogh 1961a: 69, fig. 5.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes (Balogh 1961a). Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1163-68/Afr) and an other paratype without reg. no.

Remarks. No holotype was selected in the original description, therefore all specimens in the type series are syntypes.

Quadroppia (Quadroppia) Jacot, 1939

Quadroppia (Quadroppia) cristata Balogh & Mahunka, 1980

Quadroppia cristata Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 41, figs 8E–F.

Quadroppia cristata: Fredes 2018: 92.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

STERNOPPIIDAE BALOGH & MAHUNKA, 1969

Sternoppia Balogh & Mahunka, 1968

Sternoppia boliviana Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Sternoppia boliviana Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 54, fig. 47.

Sternoppia boliviana: Balogh 1983: 33.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-623-68/D-Am) and one paratype (0-622-68/D-Am).

Remarks. The vial labelled as the holotype contains two specimens, one of which is broken. In the publication the Reg. No. for the holotype is 0-622-68/D-Am, so it is possible that the labelling of the vials has been reversed.

Sternoppia incisa Balogh & Mahunka, 1977

Sternoppia incisa Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 25, fig. 19.

Sternoppia incisa: Balogh 1983: 33.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype ZIL

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Sternoppia minor Balogh & Mahunka, 1980

Sternoppia minor Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 41, figs 9A–B.

Sternoppia minor: Balogh 1983: 33.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nine paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and ten paratypes.

Sternoppia mirabilis Balogh & Mahunka, 1968

Sternoppia mirabilis Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 324, figs 10–11.

Sternoppia mirabilis: Balogh 1983: 33, fig. 14.1.

Sternoppia mirabilis: Fredes 2018: 92.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fourteen paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-391-68/D-Am) and eight paratypes (0-392-68/D-Am).

Sternoppia quadriseta (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)

Synoppia quadriseta Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 56, figs 48–49.

Sternoppia quadriseta: Balogh 1983: 33.

Sternoppia (Synoppia) quadriseta: Mahunka 2006: 278.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Sternoppia reticulata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Sternoppia reticulata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 12, figs 31–32.

Sternoppia reticulata: Balogh & Mahunka 1978c: 284, figs 11A–D.

Sternoppia reticulata: Balogh 1983: 33.

Sternoppia reticulata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 54.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Sternoppia sphaerodendron* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

Sternoppia sphaerodendron Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 44, fig. 7.

Sternoppia sphaerodendron: Balogh 1983: 33.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Sternoppia vicina* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Sternoppia vicina Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 43, figs 9C–D.

Sternoppia vicina: Balogh 1983: 33.

Sternoppia vicina: Schatz 2006: 251.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

TERATOPPIIDAE BALOGH, 1983

***Granuloteratoppia* P. Balogh, 1988**

***Granuloteratoppia annulata* P. Balogh, 1988**

Granuloteratoppia annulata P. Balogh, 1988b: 185, figs 38–45.

Granuloteratoppia annulata: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Teratoppia (Teratoppia) Balogh, 1959

***Teratoppia (Teratoppia) calcarata* Balogh, 1959**

Teratoppia calcarata Balogh, 1959b: 98, figs 16–18.

Teratoppia calcarata: Balogh 1983: 32

Type material in the literature. Two types, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren and one paratype Musée de Dundo and ELTE.

Deposited in HNHM: Ten paratypes (0-1170-68/Afr).

Remarks. The original description lists only two syntype specimens. The vial labelled with the original locality data contains seven specimens that should be considered as syntypes. There is another vial containing three specimens labelled paratype but without locality data. Expert examination is required to determine the status of these specimens.

***Teratoppia (Teratoppia) reducta* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Teratoppia reducta Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 13, figs 34–35.

Teratoppia (Teratoppia) reducta: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 55.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty-six paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and sixteen paratypes.

Teratoppia (Teratoppiella) Balogh, 1983

***Teratoppia (Teratoppiella) brevipectinata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Teratoppia brevipectinata Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 281, figs 10A–C.

Teratoppiella brevipectinata: Balogh 1983: 32

Teratoppia (Teratoppiella) brevipectinata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 55.

Teratoppia brevipectinata: Fredes 2018: 93.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Teratoppia (Teratoppiella) pectinata* Balogh, 1961**

Teratoppia pectinata Balogh, 1961b: 521, fig. 5–6.

Teratoppia (Teratoppiella) pectinata: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2009: 57, figs 25–27.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype?

Remarks. There is a vial in the collection labelled as "Holotype det: Mahunka, Tanganyika, Leg. Szunyogyh". The original material was collected by Szunyogyh on the Meru Mts. Tanzania (then Tanganyika), so this specimen possibly represents the holotype of *T. (T.) pectinata* Balogh, 1961 found by S. Mahunka in the collection.

***Teratoppia (Teratoppiella) pluripectinata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Teratoppia pectinata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 270, fig. 24.

Teratoppia pluripectinata Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 283, fig. 10D. **nom. nov.**

Teratoppia (Teratoppiella) pluripectinata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 55.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twelve paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Remarks. *Teratoppia pectinata* Balogh *et al.* Mahunka, 1969 is a primary homonym of *Teratoppia pectinata* Balogh, 1961.

THYRISOMIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1953

***Banksinoma* Oudemans, 1930**

***Banksinoma insignis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1965**

Banksinoma insignis Balogh & Mahunka, 1965: 455, figs 7–9.

Banksinoma insignis: Bayartogtokh 2010: 50, figs 48Ж, 3.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Banksinoma monoceros* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1968)**

Oribella spinifera monoceros Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 328, figs 2–3.

Banksinoma monoceros: Fredes 2018: 94.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and sixteen paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited also in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-384-68/D-Am) and eight paratypes (0-385-68/D-Am).

***Kaszabobates* Balogh, 1972**

***Kaszabobates kaszabi* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1965)**

Gobiella kaszabi Balogh & Mahunka, 1965: 459, figs 12–13.

Kaszabobates kaszabi: Balogh 1972: 162, figs 31: 10–11.

Kaszabobates kaszabi: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2000: 57.

Kaszabobates kaszabi: Bayartogtokh 2010: 51 figs 49K, Л.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fourteen paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and seven paratypes.

***Montizetes* Kunst, 1971**

***Pantelozetes (Montizetes) mongolicus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1965)**

Oribella mongolica Balogh & Mahunka, 1965: 457, figs. 10–11.

Montizetes mongolica: Bayartogtokh 2010: 51, 49D–E.

Pantelozetes mongolicus: Ermilov *et al.* 2015: 51.

Pantelozetes (Montizetes) mongolicus: Subías 2015: 194.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

TRIZETOIDEA EWING, 1917

CUNEOPPIIDAE BALOGH, 1983

***Cuneoppia* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Cuneoppia laticeps* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Cuneoppia laticeps Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 10, figs 23–26.

Cuneoppia laticeps: Mahunka 1998: 844.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

SUCTOBELBIDAE JACOT, 1938

***Coartobelba* Mahunka, 2001**

***Coartobelba campestris* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1981)**

Suctobelba pontigera campestre Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 92, figs 123–126.

Coartobelba campestris: Mahunka 2001: 249.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Coartobelba carinata* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Suctobelba carinata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 270, fig. 25.

Suctobelbella carinata: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 42.

Coartobelba carinata: Subías 2017: 257.

Suctobelbella (Suctobelbella) carinata: Ermilov & Hugo-Coetzee 2017: 540.

Coartobelba carinata: Subías 2022: 236.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Coartobelba loksai* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1981)**

Suctobelba loksai Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 90, figs 114–116.

Suctobelbella loksai: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 44.

Coartobelba loksai: Subías 2017: 257.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

***Fenestrobella* Balogh, 1970**

***Fenestrobella annulata* Balogh, 1970**

Fenestrobella annulata Balogh, 1970a: 54, figs 35–36.

Fenestrobella annulata: Ermilov, Khaustov & Johar-chi 2020: 881.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Fenestrobella octo* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Fenestrobella octo Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 251, figs 5D–F.

Fenestrobella octo: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 140.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Kuklosuctobelba (Niosuctobelba) chinone*, 2003**

***Kuklosuctobelba (Niosuctobelba) asinus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1980)**

Suctobelba asinus Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 43, figs 10A–B.

Kuklosuctobelba (Niosuctobelba) asinus: Subías 2017: 258.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Kuklosuctobelba (Niosuctobelba) multituberculata* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)**

Suctobelba multituberculata Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 47, pl. V, figs 25–26.

Kuklosuctobelba (Niosuctobelba) multituberculata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 140.

Kuklosuctobelba (Niosuctobelba) multituberculata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 117.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes (0-32-67/As) and (0-43-67/As).

Remarks. The original description was based on a single holotype which was not found in the collection. The two specimens marked "paratype" are from the same locality as the holotype. The status of these two specimens should be checked.

***Neosuctobelba* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Neosuctobelba quatuor* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1974)**

Fenestrobella quatuor Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 251, figs 5A–C.

Neosuctobelba quatuor[:]; Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 140.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Neosuctobelba transitoria* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Neosuctobelba transitoria Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 13, figs 36–37.

Neosuctobelba transitoria: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 56.

Neosuctobelba transitoria: Fredes 2018: 94.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are de-

posited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-534-68/D-Am) and six paratypes (0-535-68/D-Am).

***Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) Chinone*, 2003**

***Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) andrassyi* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1981)**

Suctobelba andrassyi Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 88, figs 107–110.

Suctobelbella andrassyi: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 43.

Suctobelbella (Ussuribata) andrassyi: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 57.

Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) andrassyi: Subías 2017: 259.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) baculifer* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1981)**

Suctobelba perdentata baculifer Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 91, figs 117–122.

Suctobelbella baculifera: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 43.

Suctobelbella baculifera: Mahunka 1998: 845.

Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) baculifera: Subías 2017: 259.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) geometrica* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1974)**

Suctobelba geometrica Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 248, figs 3D–F.

Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) geometrica: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 141.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) roigi* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1980)**

Suctobelba roigi Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 48, figs 14A–B.

Suctobelbella roigi: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 42.
Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) roigi: Subías 2017: 260.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

***Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) transitoria* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1974)**

Suctobelba transitoria Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 250, figs 4E–G.

Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) transitoria: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 142.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) vietnamica* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)**

Suctobelba vietnamica Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 48, pl. IV, fig. 24.

Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) vietnamica: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 118.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-40-67/As).

Novosuctobelba (Novosuctobelba) Hammer, 1977

***Novosuctobelba (Novosuctobelba) horrida* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1966)**

Suctobelba horrida Balogh & Mahunka, 1966b: 34, figs 17–18.

Novosuctobelba (Novosuctobelba) horrida: Subías 2017: 259.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eleven paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-89-67/Afr) and five paratypes.

Parasuctobelba Hammer, 1977

***Parasuctobelba hamifera* (Balogh, 1958)**

Suctobelba hamifera Balogh, 1958: 16.

Suctobelba hamifera: Balogh 1961a: 73, fig. 21.

Parasuctobelba hamifera: Hammer 1977: 42.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description, no holotype was selected and no information on the type material was given. Therefore, these two specimens should be considered as syntypes.

***Parasuctobelba medialis* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1974)**

Suctobelba medialis Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 249, figs 4A–D.

Parasuctobelba medialis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 143.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Parasuctobelba mirabilis* (Balogh, 1958)**

Suctobelba mirabilis Balogh, 1958: 16.

Suctobelba mirabilis: Balogh 1961a: 73, fig. 20.

Parasuctobelba mirabilis: Hammer 1977: 42.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Parasuctobelba monstrosa* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1980)**

Suctobelba monstrosa Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 46, figs 12A–B.

Parasuctobelba monstrosa: Hammer 1977: 42.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Parasuctobelba subcomplexa* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1968)**

Suctobelba subcomplexa Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 328, fig. 18.

Parasuctobelba subcomplexa: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 56.

Suctobelbella subcomplexa: Fredes 2018: 97.

Parasuctobelba subcomplexa: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 143.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the Paratypes in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited also in the collections of J. Aoki and E Piff. l.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-364-68/D-Am).

***Rhynchoppia* Balogh, 1968**

***Rhynchoppia azaisi* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Rhynchoppia azaisi J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 320, fig. 14.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Two "types".

Remarks. Although in the original description it is stated that the species is described on the basis of a holotype and one paratype, in the collection we have found a vial with the label of "types" containing two specimen. Therefore they should be regarded as syntypes.

***Rhynchoppia capillata* (Balogh, 1963)**

Suctobelbilla (?) capillata Balogh, 1963: 40, fig. 10.

Rhynchoppia capillata: Balogh 1968: 270.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren, and one paratype with no deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

***Rhynchoppia sedlaceki* Balogh, 1968**

Rhynchoppia sedlaceki Balogh, 1968: 270, pl. VIII. Figs 45–46.

Rhynchoppia sedlaceki: Ermilov, Kalúz & Martens 2014: 61.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. The species was revised by Moritz (1974).

Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) Hammer, 1979

***Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) acutissima* (Balogh, 1958)**

Suctobelba acutissima Balogh, 1958: 16.

Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) acutissima: Subías 2017: 266. sp. inq.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) lineata* (Balogh, 1970)**

Suctobelba lineata Balogh, 1970a: 303, pl. V. fig. 31, VI. fig. 32.

Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) lineata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 144.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) penicillata* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1966)**

Suctobelba penicillata Balogh & Mahunka, 1966b: 36, figs 19–20.

Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) penicillata: Subías 2004: 138.

Suctobelbella penicillata: Schatz 2006: 253.

Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) penicillata: Subías 2023: 244.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype (0-127-68/Afr).

Remarks. The original description only mentions a holotype, but the species was certainly described on several specimens, as a range is given for the dimensions.

***Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) peracuta*
(Balogh & Mahunka, 1980)**

Suctobelba peracuta Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 47, figs 13A–B.

Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) peracuta: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 56.

Suctobelbella peracuta: Fredes 2018: 97.

Suctobelbella (flagrosuctobelba) peracuta: Ermilov *et al.* 2021a: 153.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eleven paratypes HNHM, three paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) semiplumosa*
(Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)**

Suctobelba semiplumosa Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 48, pl. V. figs 27–28.

Suctobelba semiplumosa: Balogh 1968: 267, pl. VI. figs 29–30.

Flagrosuctobelba simillima: J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 141. **nom. nov.** pro *Scutobelba simillima* Balogh, 1968 nec *Scutobelba semiplumosa* Balogh & Mahunka 1967. **Nomen nudum.**

Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) semiplumosa: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 56.

Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) semiplumosa: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 145.

Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) semiplumosa: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 119.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-34-67/As).

Remarks. J. Balogh and P. Balogh (2002) published a new name *Flagroscutobelba simillima* **nom. nov.** writing “pro *Scutobelba simillima* Balogh, 1968 nec *Scutobelba semiplumosa* Balogh

& Mahunka 1967”. The name *Scutobelba simillima* Balogh, 1968 did not exist and from the book of Balogh & Balogh (2002) it can only be assumed that they provided this name to the six specimens from New Guinea, previously identified by Balogh (1968: 267) as *Scutobelba semiplumosa* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967. However, in this case “nom. nov.” was mistakenly provided and the name *Flagroscutobelba simillima* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002 represents a nomen nudum (ICZN 16.1 and 16A).

***Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) simplex*
(Balogh, 1968)**

Suctobelba semiplumosa simplex Balogh, 1968: 268, pl. VI. figs 31–32.

Suctobelbella (Flagrosuctobelba) simplex: Subías 2017: 267.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Suctobelbella (Suctobelbella) Jacot, 1937

***Suctobelbella (Suctobelbella) bullocki* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1974)**

Suctobelba bullocki Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 247, figs 3A–C.

Suctobelbella (Suctobelbella) bullocki: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 146.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Suctobelbella (Suctobelbella) decorata*
(P. Balogh, 1984)**

Suctobelba decorata P. Balogh, 1984b: 322, figs 19–22.

Suctobelbella (Suctobelbella) decorata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 56.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

***Suctobelbella (Suctobelbella) finlayi* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Suctobelba finlayi Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 44, figs 11A–B.

Kuklosuctobelba (Kuklosuctobelba) finlayi: Subías 2017: 258.

Suctobelbella (Suctobelbella) finlayi: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 120.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

***Suctobelbella (Suctobelbella) flabellifera* (Balogh, 1958)**

Suctobelba flabellifera Balogh, 1958: 17.

Suctobelbella (Suctobelbella) flabellifera: Subías 2004: 136.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, á Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Suctobelbella (Suctobelbella) pseudornatissima* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1981)**

Suctobelba pseudoornatissima Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 94, figs 127–129.

Suctobelbella (Suctobelbella) pseudornatissima: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 57.

Suctobelbella pseudornatissima: Fredes 2018: 97.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes HNHM, two paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Suctobelbella (Suctobelbella) scrofa* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1968)**

Suctobelba scrofa Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 328, figs 19–20.

Suctobelbella scrofa: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 42.

Suctobelbella (Suctobelbella) scrofa: Subías 2004: 137.

Suctobelbella scrofa: Fredes 2018: 97.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited also in the collections of J. Aoki and E. Piffel.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-393-68/D-Am) and one paratype (0-395-68/D-Am).

Suctobelbella (Ussuribata) Rjabinin, 1975

***Suctobelbella (Ussuribata) flagellata* (Balogh, 1959)**

Suctobelba flagellata Balogh, 1959b: 98, fig 15.

Suctobelbella (Ussuribata) flagellata: Subías 2017: 268.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, á Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Suctobelbella (Ussuribata) papuana* (Balogh, 1968)**

Suctobelba papuana Balogh, 1968: 268, pl. VII, figs 35–38.

Suctobelbella permixta J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 147. **nom. nov.** pro *Suctobelbella papuana* Balogh, 1968 pro parte) **nomen nudum.**

Suctobelbella (Ussuribata) papuana: Ermilov, Stanchaeva & Subías 2014: 1594.

Suctobelbella (Ussuribata) permixta: Subías 2022: 245.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Remarks. Balogh & P. Balogh (2002) proposed a replacement name for part of the *Scutobelba papuana* Balogh, 1968 material as if it were a homonym. However, this is only a possible misidentification and the proposed new replace-

ment name is invalid as it does not comply with ICZN 16.1 and 16A and is therefore a **nomen nudum**.

***Suctobelbella (Ussuribata) womersleyi* (Balogh, 1968)**

Suctobelba womersleyi Balogh, 1968: 268, pl. VI. figs 33–34.

Suctobelbella (Ussuribata) womersleyi: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 149.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Suctobelbilla Jacot*, 1937**

***Suctobelbilla approximata* Balogh, 1968**

Suctobelbilla approximata Balogh, 1968: 269, pl. VIII. figs 43–44.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. Mislabelled as *Scutobelba approximata*.

***Suctobelbilla cornuta* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Suctobelbilla cornuta Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 16, figs 12A–B.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. The holotype (except where no paratypes representing the species are available) are deposited in the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba, while the paratypes and the exceptions mentioned above are in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Suctobelbilla globulifera* (Balogh, 1958)**

Suctoppia globulifera Balogh, 1958: 17.

Suctobelbilla globulifera: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 258.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Suctobelbilla longitudinalis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Suctobelbilla longitudinalis Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 17, figs 12C–E.

Suctobelbilla longitudinalis: Balogh & Mahunka 1980: 22.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype (except where no paratypes representing the species are available) are deposited in the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba, while the paratypes and the exceptions mentioned above are in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

***Suctobelbilla margaritata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Suctobelbilla margaritata Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 49, figs 15A–B.

Suctobelbilla margaritata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 122.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Suctobelbilla ornata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Suctobelbilla ornata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 270, fig. 26.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Suctobelbilla pocsi* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Suctobelbilla pocsi Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 50, figs 16A–B. p

Suctobelbilla pocsi: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 122.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Suctobelbilla quinquenodosa* Balogh, 1968**

Suctobelbilla quinquenodosa Balogh, 1968: 269, pl. VIII. figs 41–42.

Suctobelbilla quinquenodosa: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 150.

Suctobelbilla quinquenodosa: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 122.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Suctobelbilla sexnodosa* Balogh, 1968**

Suctobelbilla sexnodosa Balogh, 1968: 269, pl. VII. figs 39–40.

Suctobelbilla sexnodosa: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 150.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. Mislabeled as *Scutobelba sexnodosa*.

***Suctobelbilla suctobelboides* Balogh, 1970**

Suctobelbilla suctobelboides Balogh, 1970b: 304, pl. VI. figs 27–28.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop

Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Suctobelbilla tripartita* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Suctobelbilla tripartita Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 18, figs 12F–H.

Suctobelbilla tripartita: Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 22.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Remarks. The original description only mentions a single holotype, but the specimen labelled "paratype" has the same locality as the holotype.

***Suctobelbilla waterhousei* Balogh, 1970**

Suctobelbilla waterhousei Balogh, 1970b: 303, pl. VI. fig 33.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

TECTOCEPHEOIDEA GRANDJEAN, 1954

TECTOCEPHEIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1954

***Tectocephus* Berlese, 1896**

***Tectocephus cervus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Tectocephus cervus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 267, fig. 20.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Tectocephus velatus velatus* (Michael, 1880)**

Tectocephus vicarius Balogh, 1958: 22.

Tectocephus velatus velatus: Subías 2016: 304.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren (*Tectocephus vicarius*).

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Tegezozetes Berlese, 1913

Tegezozetes angolensis Balogh, 1958

Tegezozetes angolensis Balogh, 1958: 27.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

LIMNOZETOIDEA THOR, 1937

HYDROZETIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1954

Hydrozetes Berlese, 1902

Hydrozetes vicarius Balogh, 1958

Hydrozetes vicarius Balogh, 1958: 13.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

AMERONOTHROIDEA WILLMANN, 1931

AMERONOTHRIDAE WILLMANN, 1931

Pseudantarctica Balogh, 1970

Pseudantarctica tropica Balogh, 1970

Pseudantarctica tropica Balogh, 1970b: 305, pl. VI. figs 36–37.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

TEGEOCRANELLIDAE BALOGH P., 1987

Tegeocranellus Berlese, 1913

Tegeocranellus bolivianus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Tegeocranellus bolivianus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 48, fig. 36.

Tegeocranellus bolivianus: Balogh & Mahunka 1981: 79, figs 82–84.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Tegeocranellus concavus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983

Tegeocranellus concavus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 88, figs 7A–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and thirty-seven paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Thirty-three paratypes.

Tegeocranellus convexus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983

Tegeocranellus convexus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 89, figs 8A–E.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes.

CYBAEREMAEOIDEA SELLNICK, 1928

CYBAEREMAEIDAE SELLNICK, 1928

Glanderemaeus Balogh & Csiszár, 1963

Glanderemaeus hammerae Balogh & Csiszár, 1963

Glanderemaeus hammerae Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 481, figs 20–22.

Glanderemaeus hammerae: Fredes 2018: 103.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Scapheremaeus* Berlese, 1910**

***Scapheremaeus cornutus* Balogh, 1958**

Scapheremaeus cornutus Balogh, 1958: 8.

Scapheremaeus cornutus: Colloff 2009: 33.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. In the original description, no holotype was selected, and therefore all the specimens in the type series should be considered to be syntypes.

***Scapheremaeus patella* (Berlese, 1886)**

Eremaeus patella Berlese, 1886: 33, 10.

Scapheremaeus? patella: Hammer 1966: 43, figs. 52, 52a.

Scapheremaeus hammerae Balogh & Balogh, 2002: 116, pl. 175: 8. **nom. nov.** pro *S. patella* Hammer, 1966 nec *S. patella* (Berlese, 1886). **Nomen nudum.**

Scapheremaeus patella: Subías 2004: 159.

Remarks. J. Balogh & P. Balogh provided a replacement name for *Scapheremaeus patella* (Berlese) in Hammer (1966: 43), as if it were a homonym of *Scapheremaeus patella* (Berlese, 1886). However, this is only a possible misidentification and at most these specimens represent a new species. However, the use of "nom. nov." in this case is clearly misleading and renders this name **nomen nudum** and unavailable according to ICZN Art. 16.4 and 16A.

***Scapheremaeus humeratus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967**

Scapheremaeus humeratus Balogh & Mahunka, 1967b: 35, figs 1–2.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-138/67/Afr).

Remarks. In the vial labelled as holotype there are two specimens. Expert verification is required to determine their status.

***Scapheremaeus johnsi* Balogh, 1970**

Scapheremaeus johnsi Balogh, 1970b: 306, pl. VI. figs 40–41.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Scapheremaeus morenoi* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1974)**

Scutovertex morenoi Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 19, figs 13A–D.

Scapheremaeus morenoi: Colloff 2009: 39.

Scapheremaeus morenoi: Akrami 2015: 483.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nineteen paratypes. The holotype (except where no paratypes representing the species are available) are deposited in the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba, while the paratypes and the exceptions mentioned above are in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and twenty-one paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description only nineteen paratypes are mentioned.

***Scapheremaeus ornatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1968**

Scapheremaeus ornatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 330, figs 23–24.

Scapheremaeus ornatus: Fredes 2018: 104.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-400-68/D-Am).

Scapheremaeus subglaber Balogh & Mahunka, 1978

Scapheremaeus subglaber Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 285, figs 13A–B.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Scapheremaeus taurus Balogh, 1970

Scapheremaeus taurus Balogh, 1970b: 305, pl. VI. figs 38–39.

Scapheremaeus taurus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 155.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

Remarks. The vial of the paratype seems to be empty.

EREMAEOZETOIDEA PIFFL, 1972

EREMAEOZETIDAE PIFFL, 1972

***Eremaozetes* Berlese, 1913**

***Eremaozetes bilunatifer* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

Eremaozetes bilunatifer Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 66, figs 45–46.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Eremaozetes ephippiger* Balogh, 1968**

Eremaozetes ephippiger Balogh, 1968: 273, pl. XI. figs 60–61.

Eremaozetes ephippiger: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 155.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and sixty-five paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Eremaozetes reticulatus* Balogh, 1958**

Eremaozetes (?) reticulatus Balogh, 1958: 22.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Rogerzetes* Fernandez, Theron & Cleva, 2014**

***Rogerzetes spathulatus* (Balogh, 1968)**

Eremaozetes spathulatus Balogh, 1968: 273, pl. XI. fig. 59.

Rogerzetes spathulatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 156.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Seteremaeozetes* P. Balogh, 1988**

***Seteremaeozetes obtectus* (P. Balogh, 1988)**

Eremaozetes (Seteremaeozetes) obtectus P. Balogh, 1988b: 178, figs 19–20.

Seteremaeozetes obtectus: Subías 2004: 165.

Eremaozetes (Eremaozetes) obtectus: Colloff 2012: 4.

Seteremaeozetes obtectus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

Remarks. The paratype is labelled *Seteremaeus obtectus*.

LICNEREMAEOIDEA GRANDJEAN, 1931

CHARASSOBATIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1958

Charassobates Grandjean, 1929

**Charassobates incipatus Balogh & Mahunka,
1974**

Charassobates incipatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a:
6, figs 4A–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype (except where no paratypes representing the species are available) are deposited in the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba, while the paratypes and the exceptions mentioned above are in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

**Charassobates minimus Balogh & Mahunka,
1981**

Charassobates minimus Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 67,
figs 47–49.

Charassobates minimus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 60.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

**Charassobates ornatus Balogh & Mahunka,
1969**

Charassobates ornatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c:
266, fig. 18.

Charassobates ornatus: Balogh & Mahunka 1978c:
277.

Charassobates ornatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 60.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fourteen paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

**Charassobates simplex Balogh & Mahunka,
1969**

Charassobates simplex Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c:
266, fig. 19.

Charassobates simplex: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 60.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

**Charassobates tuberosus Balogh & Mahunka,
1981**

Charassobates tuberosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1981:
67, figs 50–53.

Charassobates tuberosus: Fredes 2018: 106.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

EREMELLIDAE BALOGH, 1961

Archeremella Balogh & Mahunka, 1974

**Archeremella leowae (Balogh & Mahunka,
1974)**

Eremella (Archeremella) leowae Balogh & Mahunka,
1974b: 254, figs 6A–D.

Archeremella leowae: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019:
157.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Eremella Berlese, 1913

Emella africana (Balogh, 1966)

Proteremella africana Balogh, 1966: 72, fig. 5.

Eremella africana: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 254.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-97-67/Afr).

Eremella ensifera Balogh & Mahunka, 1968

Eremella ensifera Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 330,
figs 21–22.

Triteremella ensifera: Mahunka 2011: 56.

Eremella ensifera: Akrami 2015: 481.
Eremella ensifera: Fredes 2018: 106.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fifty-five paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited also in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Fifty paratypes (0-359-68/D-Am).

***Eremella kaszabi* Csiszár, 1962**

Eremella kaszabi Csiszár, 1962a: 401, figs 1–2.
Eremella kaszabi: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 177.
Eremella kaszabi: Ermilov & Frolov 2019: 223.
Eremella (Licnocephus) kaszabi: Subías 2020: 290.

Type material in the literature: Holotype and four paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Seven paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description there are only four paratypes mentioned.

***Emella pulchella* (Balogh, 1959)**

Proteremella pulchella Balogh, 1959a: 31, figs 4–6.
Eremella pulchella: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 254.
Eremella pulchella: Subías 2004: 106.
Proteremella pulchella: Starý 2006: 29.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM, several paratypes ELTE.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and fourteen paratypes.

LAMELLAREIDAE BALOGH, 1972

***Tenuelamellarea Subías & Iturrondobeitia,*
1978**

***Tenuelamellarea hawaiiensis* P. Balogh, 1985**

Tenuelamellarea hawaiiensis P. Balogh, 1985c: 61, figs 4A–B.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Three vials without type markings.

Remarks. One of the vials contains eight specimens with the same locality as in the original publication. These specimens may represent the type series.

LICNEREMAEIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1931

***Licneremaeus Paoli,* 1908**

***Licneremaeus cubanus* Balogh & Mahunka,
1980**

Licneremaeus cubanus Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 53, figs 18A–B.
Licneremaeus cubanus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 60.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Licneremaeus novaeguineae* Balogh, 1968**

Licneremaeus novaeguineae Balogh, 1968: 272, pl. X, figs 57–58.
Licneremaeus novaeguineae: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 158.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Licneremaeus propinquus* Balogh, 1958**

Licneremaeus propinquus Balogh, 1958: 14.
Licneremaeus propinquus: Bomfim *et al.* 2017: 1872.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

MICREREMIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1954

***Fenichelia* Balogh, 1970**

***Fenichelia biroi* Balogh, 1970**

Fenichelia biroi Balogh, 1970b: 318, pl. XII, figs 71–72.

Fenichelia biroi: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1998: 18.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Micreremus* Berlese, 1908**

***Micreremus africanus* Balogh, 1963**

Micreremus africanus Balogh, 1963: 41, fig. 11.

Micreremus africanus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1998: 23.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Micreremus granulatus* Balogh, 1970**

Micreremus (?) *granulatus* Balogh, 1970a: 56, figs 40–41.

Micreremus granulatus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Phylloribatula* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

***Phylloribatula pulchella* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Phylloribatula pulchella Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 288, figs 15A–B.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

PASSALOZETIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1954

***Passalozetes* Grandjean, 1932**

***Passalozetes prominens* Balogh & Mahunka, 1968**

Passalozetes prominens Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 332, figs 25–26.

Passalozetes (Passalozetes) prominens: Akrami 2015: 484.

Passalozetes prominens: Fredes 2018: 108.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

SCUTOVERTICIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1954

***Arthrovertex* Balogh, 1970**

***Arthrovertex segmentatus* Balogh, 1970**

Arthrovertex segmentatus Balogh, 1970b: 307, pl. VII, figs 42–43.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

***Latoververtex* Mahunka, 1987**

***Latoververtex laticuspis* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1965)**

Scutovertex laticuspis Balogh & Mahunka, 1965: 461, figs 16–17.

Latoververtex laticuspis: Mahunka 1987a: 376.

Exochocephus laticuspis: Subías 2004: 161.

Latoververtex laticuspis: Bayartogtokh 2010: 57, figs 60K–L.

Latoververtex laticuspis: Ermilov *et al.* 2021c: 702.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Scutovertex* Michael, 1879**

***Scutovertex contiguus* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963**

Scutovertex contiguus Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 482, fig. 34.

Exochocephus contiguus: Subías 2004: 161.
Scutovertex contiguus: Fredes 2018: 108.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Scutovertex foliatus* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963**

Scutovertex foliatus Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 481, figs 35–36.

Cymbaeremaeus foliatus: Subías 2004: 158.

Scutovertex foliatus: Fredes 2018: 109.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1157-68/Afr) and one paratype.

Remarks. The holotype reg. no. in the vial refers to an African species, so it must be a mislabelling.

***Scutovertex glandulosus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1965**

Scutovertex glandulosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1965: 459, figs 14a–c.

Scutovertex glandulosus: Bayartogtokh 2010: 57, figs 61Ě, Ж.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

***Scutovertex subspinipes* Balogh, 1959**

Scutovertex subspinipes Balogh, 1959c: 14, figs 8–10.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Thirteen paratypes.

***Scutovertex transversalis* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963**

Scutovertex transversalis Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 482, fig. 32.

Hypoverte *transversalis*: Subías 2004: 161.

Scutovertex transversalis: Fredes 2018: 109.

Ethiovertex (Ethiovertex) transversalis: Subías 2020: 293.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fifteen paratypes. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1138-68/Afr) and nine paratypes.

Remarks. The holotype reg. no. in the vial refers to an African species so it must be a mislabeling.

PHENOPELOPOIDEA PETRUNKEVICH, 1955

PHENOPELOPIDAE PETRUNKEVICH, 1955

***Eupelops* Ewing, 1917**

***Eupelops ecuadoriensis* P. Balogh, 1988**

Eupelops ecuadoriensis P. Balogh, 1988c: 334, figs 37–41.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and about two hundred paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

***Eupelops erinaceus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

Eupelops erinaceus Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 53, fig. 14.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Eupelops forsslundi* (Balogh, 1959)**

Pelops forsslundi Balogh, 1959c: 18, figs 31–32.

Eupelops forsslundi: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 130.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes (0-1144-68/Afr), and nine further paratypes without reg. no.

Remarks. In the original description no holotype was selected therefore the whole type series should be considered as syntypes.

***Eupelops heegi* (Balogh, 1958)**

Pelops heegi Balogh, 1958: 31.
Eupelops heegi: Subías 2004: 163.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, á Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Eupelops kivuensis* (Balogh, 1958)**

Pelops kivuensis Balogh, 1958: 30.
Eupelops kivuensis: Subías 2004: 163.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, á Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Nesopelops Hammer, 1973

***Nesopelops higginsii* (Balogh, 1970)**

Eupelops higginsii Balogh, 1970b: 323, pl. XV. figs 87–88.
Nesopelops higginsii: Subías 2004: 164.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Nesopelops laensis* (Balogh, 1970)**

Eupelops laensis Balogh, 1970b: 323, pl. XVI. figs 89–90.
Nesopelops laensis: Subías 2004: 164.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Nesopelops transversus* (Balogh, 1970)**

Eupelops transversus Balogh, 1970b: 322, pl. XV. figs 85–86.
Nesopelops transversus: Subías 2004: 164.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype (broken).

ACHIPTERIOIDEA THOR, 1929

ACHIPTERIIDAE THOR, 1929

***Austrachipteria* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

***Austrachipteria bidactylus* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983)**

Parahypozetes bidactylus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 96, figs 15A–E.
Austrachipteria bidactyla: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. According to the documentation in HNHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1995, but Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it there.

***Austrachipteria breviseta* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983)**

Parahypozetes breviseta J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 96, figs 14A–D.
Austrachipteria breviseta: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. According to the documentation in HNHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO, Can-

berra in 1995, but Colloff & Holliday (1998) did not find it.

***Austrachipteria hammerae* (Mahunka, 1997)**

Parahypozetes lobatus J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 94, figs 13A–C.

Parahypozetes hammeri Mahunka, 1997b: 86. nom. nov. pro *P. lobatus* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983 non *P. lobatus* Hammer, 67.

Austrachipteria marieae Colloff & Halliday, 1998: 183. **nom. nov.**

Austrachipteria hammerae Subías 2004: 166.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eleven paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Ten paratypes.

Remarks. Colloff & Halliday (1998) have overlooked the replacement name previously suggested by Mahunka (1997b).

***Austrachipteria lamellata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Austrachipteria lamellata Balogh & Mahunka, 1966c: 559, figs 7–8.

Austrachipteria lamellata: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 183.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. Type specimens are in the Austral Museum.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. According to the documentation in HMHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1995 but Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it there.

***Cubachipteria* Balogh & Mahunka, 1972**

***Cubachipteria remota* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1979)**

Achipteria (Cubachipteria) remota Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 56, fig. 16.

Cubachipteria remota Subías 2004: 169.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and seven paratypes.

***Plakoribates* Popp, 1960**

***Plakoribates africanus* (Balogh, 1959)**

Tectoribates africanus Balogh, 1959b: 108, figs 52–53.
Plakoribates africanus: Subías 2008: 316.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

EPACTOZETIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1936

***Epactozetes* Grandjean, 1970**

***Epactozetes setosus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Epactozetes setosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 64, fig. 64–65.

Epactozetes setosus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 61.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

***Truncozetes* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Truncozetes mucronatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Truncozetes mucronatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 16, figs 48–49.

Truncozetes mucronatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 61.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and seven paratypes.

***Truncozetes sturmi* P. Balogh, 1984**

Truncozetes sturmi P. Balogh, 1984b: 325, figs 19–22.

Truncozetes sturmi: P. Balogh 1988c: 324.

Truncozetes sturmi: Schatz 2006: 281.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and thirty-nine paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and thirty-five paratypes.

TEGORIBATIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1954

***Plakoribates* Popp, 1960**

***Plakoribates confluens* Balogh, 1970**

Plakoribates confluens Balogh, 1970a: 66, fig. 58.

Plakoribates confluens: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 882.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Plakoribates neotropicus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Plakoribates neotropicus Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 293, figs 20A–B.

Plakoribates neotropicus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 133.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

***Tectoribates*, Berlese, 1910**

***Tectoribates deserticola* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1965)**

Anoribatella (?) *deserticola* Balogh & Mahunka, 1965: 461, figs 18–19.

Tectoribates deserticola: Balogh & Balogh 1992: 232.

Tectoribates deserticolus: Bayartogtokh 2010: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

ORIBATELLOIDEA JACOT, 1925

ORIBATELLIDAE JACOT, 1925

***Fenestrobates* Balogh & Mahunka, 1968**

***Fenestrobates capucinus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Fenestrobates capucinus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 62, figs 61–62.

Oribatella (*Fenestrobates*) *capucinus*: Subías 2001: 172.

Fenestrobates capucinus: Ermilov & Behan-Pelletier 2014: 260.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Oribatella* (*Oribatella*) Banks, 1895**

***Oribatella* (*Oribatella*) *angulosa* Csiszár, 1962**

Oribatella angulosa Csiszár, 1962b: 289, figs 22–23.

Oribatella angulosa: Murvanidze & Mumladze 2016: 61.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: ?

Remarks. There is a vial in the HNHM labelled as *Oribatella angulosa* with the locality Bulgaria. However, it lacks type marking and appears to be empty.

***Oribatella* (*Oribatella*) *avicula* P. Balogh, 1989**

Oribatella aviculus P. Balogh, 1989: 28, figs 22–27.

Oribatella (*Oribatella*) *avicula*: Subías 2014: 345.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Four "type" specimens.

Remarks. The holotype and paratypes are in one vial and undistinguishable, therefore all specimens should be regarded as syntypes.

***Oribatella (Oribatella) brevilamellata* Balogh, 1958**

Oribatella (?) *brevilamellata* Balogh, 1958: 27.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1153-68/Afr).

Remarks. In the original description, no holotype was designated and there is also no information on the number of specimens examined, therefore all the material should be considered as syntypes.

***Oribatella (Oribatella) incurvata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Oribatella incurvata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 271, fig. 31.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Oribatella (Oribatella) malaya* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Oribatella malaya Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 263, figs 13A–F.

Oribatella malaya: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 160.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Oribatella (Oribatella) punctulata* Balogh, 1958**

Oribatella punctulata Balogh, 1958: 27.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Oribatella (Oribatella) reducta* P. Balogh, 1985**

Oribatella reducta P. Balogh, 1985a: 92, figs 7A–B.

Oribatella reducta: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 188.

Type material in the literature. "The holotype of the new species, after the completion of the research, will be deposited in the National Insect Collection, CSIRO, Canberra".

Deposited in HNHM: One "type".

Remarks. There is no data on the specimens examined, but a range is given for the size of the new species, so there may have been more specimens available that represent syntypes.

***Oribatella (Oribatella) serrata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Oribatella serrata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 15, figs 46–47.

Oribatella serrata: Ermilov, Niedbała & Friedrich 2016: 63.

Oribatella (Oribatella) serrata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 61.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eighteen paratypes. The holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and seventeen paratypes.

***Oribatella (Oribatella) szunyoghyi* Balogh, 1961**

Oribatella szunyoghyi Balogh, 1961b: 522, fig. 12.

Oribatella szunyoghyi: Balogh 1962d: 95, figs 33–35.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, and ten paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Oribatella (Bioribatella) Subías, 2017

***Oribatella (Bioribatella) hungarica* Balogh, 1943**

Oribatella hungarica Balogh, 1943: 95, tab. XVII, fig. 8.

Oribatella hungarica: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 287.

Oribatella hungarica: Schatz 2018: 60.

Oribatella (Birobatella) hungarica: Subías 2017b: 22.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one vial of paratypes.

Remarks. The original description does not include a holotype, so all the specimens in the type series are considered to be syntypes.

Oribatella (Monoribatella) Subías, 2017

***Oribatella (Monoribatella) szaboi* Balogh & Mahunka 1979**

Oribatella szaboi Balogh & Mahunka 1979: 54, fig. 15.

Oribatella (Monoribatella) szaboi: Subías 2017b: 22.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype NMT.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

***Oribatella (Monoribatella) tenuis* Csiszár, 1962**

Oribatella tenuis Csiszár, 1962b: 288, figs 20–21.

Oribatella tenuis: Murvanidze & Mumladze 2016: 62.

Oribatella (Monoribatella) tenuis: Subías 2017b: 22.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, and one paratype, with deposition not exactly stated. "The paratypes are in the collections of the author or in the HNHM".

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Pseudotectoribates* Subías, 1977**

***Pseudotectoribates subsimilis subsimilis* (Mihelčič, 1956)**

Anachipteria kittenbergeri Balogh, 1959c: 15, figs 15–16.

Anoribatella kittenbergeri: Balogh & Mahunka 1965: 462.

Pseudotectoribates subsimilis subsimilis: Subías 2011: 342.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes (*A. kittenbergeri*).

Remarks. As no holotype was selected in the original publication, all five specimens are considered to be syntypes of *Anachipteria kittenbergeri* Balogh, 1959.

ORIPODOIDEA JACOT, 1925

CALOPPIIDAE BALOGH, 1960

***Brassiella* Balogh, 1970**

***Brassiella arboricola* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Brassiella arboricola J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 323, fig. 16.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Reticuloppia* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

***Reticuloppia reticulata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Reticuloppia reticulata Balogh & Mahunka, 1966c: 566, figs 14–15.

Reticuloppia reticulata: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 154.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. Type specimens are in the Austral Museum.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. The holotype is probably lost. It is not in the CSIRO (Colloff & Halliday 1998) and also nor in the HNHM.

***Stelechobates* Grandjean, 1965**

***Stelechobates brazilianus* P. Balogh, 1995**

Stelechobates brazilianus P. Balogh, 1995: 7, figs 11–14.

Stelechobates brazilianus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 62.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes Balogh Collection, Budapest.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Zetorchella Berlese, 1916

Zetorchella basilewskyi (Balogh, 1958)

Caloppia basilewskyi Balogh, 1958: 10.
Caloppia basilewskyi: Balogh 1960b: 96, figs 18–19.
Chaunoproctus basilewskyi: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 235.
Zetorchella basilewskyi: Özdikmen 2008b: 694.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Four paratypes.

Remarks. There is no holotype designated in the original description, therefore all specimens should be considered as syntypes.

Zetorchella minor (Balogh, 1958)

Caloppia minor Balogh, 1958: 11.
Caloppia minor: Balogh 1960b: 95, fig. 17.
Chaunoproctus minor: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 235.
Zetorchella minor: Özdikmen 2008b: 695.
Zetorchella minor: Ermilov *et al.* 2021a: 154.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. There is no holotype designated in the original description, therefore all specimens should be considered as syntypes.

Zetorchella pedestris Berlese, 1916

Caloppia papillata Balogh, 1958: 11.
Caloppia papillata: Balogh 1960b: 95, fig. 16.
Chaunoproctus papillata: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 235.
Zetorchella pedestris: Subías 2008: 363.
Zetorchella pedestris: Özdikmen 2008b: 695.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes (*Caloppia papillata*) (Balogh 1960b). Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes.

Remarks. There is no holotype designated in the original description, therefore all specimens should be considered as syntypes.

Zetorchella vargai (Balogh, 1959)

Caloppia vargai Balogh, 1959c: 13, figs 1–3.
Chaunoproctus vargai: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 235.
Zetorchella vargai: Subías 2008: 363.
Zetorchella vargai: Özdikmen 2008b: 695.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. There is no information on the type material in the original publication, but it is clear that it is based on several specimens. Therefore all specimens in the type series should be considered as syntypes.

HAPLOZETIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1936

Acutozetes Balogh, 1970

Acutozetes bornemisszai J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986

Acutozetes bornemisszai J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1986b: 278, figs 43–46.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Acutozetes nadchatrami Balogh & Mahunka, 1974

Acutozetes nadchatrami Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 258, figs 9A–E.
Acutozetes nadchatrami: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 162.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes, no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: "Types".

Remarks. There are two vials in the HNHM, one with one specimen, and the other with two. However, they are not properly labelled.

Acutozetes rostratus Balogh, 1970

Acutozetes rostratus Balogh, 1970b: 319, pl. XIII. figs 77–78.

Acutozetes rostratus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 136.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

Conozetes Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

***Conozetes arcualis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Conozetes arcualis Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 20, figs 55–56.

Conozetes arcualis: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 62.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Cribozetes* Balogh & Mahunka, 1970**

***Cribozetes multiareolatus* Balogh, 1970**

Cribozetes multiareolatus Balogh, 1970a: 60, figs 49–50.

Cribozetes multiareolatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 162.

Cribozetes multiareolatus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 883.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Haplozetes* Willmann, 1935**

***Haplozetes madagascarensis* (Balogh, 1961)**

Scheloribates madagascarensis Balogh, 1961d: 25, figs 30–31.

Indoribates (Haplozetes) madagascarensis: Subías 2017: 440.

Haplozetes madagascarensis: Ermilov & Khaustov 2018: 153.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and a paratype.

Indoribates (Indoribates) Jacot, 1929

***Indoribates (Indoribates) brevisetus* (Balogh, 1970)**

Cosmobates brevisetus Balogh, 1970b: 320, pl. XIV, figs 79–80.

Indoribates (Indoribates) brevisetus: Subías 2011: 410.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Indoribates (Indoribates) gregoryi* (Balogh, 1970)**

Cosmobates gregoryi Balogh, 1970b: 320, pl. XIV, figs 81–82.

Indoribates (Indoribates) gregoryi: Subías 2004: 208.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fourteen paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and thirteen paratypes.

***Indoribates (Indoribates) punctulatus* Sellnick, 1925**

Cosmobates panabokkei Balogh, 1970a: 64, fig. 56.

Indoribates (Indoribates) punctulatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 163.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

Lauritzenia (Lauritzenia) Hammer, 1958

***Lauritzenia (Lauritzenia) insignis* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1966)**

Haplozetes (?) insignis Balogh & Mahunka, 1966b: 38, figs 26–27.

Lauritzenia (Lauritzenia) insignis: Subías 2004: 208.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-104-67/Afr) and two paratypes (0-147-67/Afr).

***Lauritzenia (Lauritzenia) furtadoi* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1974)**

Haplozetes furtadoi Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 259, figs 10A–D.

Lauritzenia (Lauritzenia) furtadoi: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 165.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes; no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

Remarks. The proper type marking is missing, but the label has sp. n. written on it.

***Paraxylobates* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Paraxylobates imitans* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Paraxylobates imitans Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 20, figs 59–60.

Paraxylobates imitans: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 63.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. The original description is based on a single holotype. There is another vial in the collection labelled as *P. imitans* with the same locality but without a type mark.

Peloribates (Peloribates) Berlese, 1908

***Peloribates (Peloribates) gressitti* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967**

Peloribates gressitti Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 59, pl. X, figs 54–55.

Peloribates (Peloribates) gressitti: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 139.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-67-67/As) and one paratype (0-39-67/As). There is an other vial (0-68-67/As) with two specimen labelled as paratypes.

Remarks. In the original publication only a holotype is reported.

***Peloribates (Peloribates) hungaricus* (Balogh, 1943)**

Capillozetes hungaricus Balogh, 1943: 78, tab. XIV, figs 13–14.

Peloribates hungaricus: Balogh 1959c: 17, figs 27–30.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. The holotype is on a permanent slide.

***Peloribates (Peloribates) longipilosus* Csiszár, 1962**

Peloribates longipilosus Csiszár, 1962b: 292, fig. 38.

Peloribates longipilosus: Murvanidze & Mumladze 2016: 63.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM, and ten paratypes, with deposition not exactly stated. "The paratypes are in the collections of the author or in the HNHM".

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Peloribates (Peloribates) paraguayensis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

Peloribates paraguayensis Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 95, figs 136–141.

Peloribates (Peloribates) paraguayensis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 140.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Peloribates (Peloribates) plumosus* P. Balogh,
1985**

Peloribates plumosus P. Balogh, 1985a: 87, figs 5A–D.
Peloribates plumosus: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 177.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Two syntypes.

***Peloribates (Peloribates) pseudoporosus* Balogh
& Mahunka, 1967**

?*Peloribates pseudoporosus* Balogh & Mahunka,
1967a: 61, pl. XI. Figs 58–59.

Peloribates (Peloribates) pseudoporosus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 140.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-60-67/As).

***Peloribates (Peloribates) reticulatus* Balogh,
1970**

Peloribates reticulatus Balogh, 1970b: 317, pl. XII.
figs 73–74.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Peloribates (Peloribates) stellatus* Balogh &
Mahunka, 1967**

Peloribates stellatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 60,
pl. XI. Figs 56–57.

Peloribates (Peloribates) stellatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 141.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-73-67/As) and one paratype (0-74-67/As).

Remarks. The original description mentions only a holotype.

***Peloribates (Tentaculozetes) Balogh, 1970*
Peloribates (Tentaculozetes) loksai (Balogh, 1970)**

Tentaculozetes loksai Balogh, 1970b: 319, pl. XIII. figs
75–76.

Peloribates (Tentaculozetes) loksai: Subías 2004: 417.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. The Holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and six paratypes.

***Perxylobates* Hammer, 1972**

***Perxylobates vermiseta* (Balogh &
Mahunka, 1968)**

Xylobates vermiseta Balogh & Mahunka, 1968b: 344,
figs 7–8.

Perxylobates vermiseta: Hammer 1972: 46, fig. 52.

Perxylobates vermiseta: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov
2019: 169.

Perxylobates vermiseta: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov
2020: 142.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype NSMT.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-209-67).

***Pilobatella (Pilobatella) Balogh &
Mahunka, 1967***

***Pilobatella (Pilobatella) punctulata* Balogh &
Mahunka, 1967**

Pilobatella punctulata Balogh & Mahunka, 1967b: 40,
figs 7–8.

Pilobatella punctulata: Basu & Sanyal 2016: 324.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-122-67/Afr) and one paratype (0-123-67/Afr).

Pilobates Balogh, 1960

***Pilobates pilosellus* (Balogh, 1958)**

Protoribates pilosellus Balogh, 1958: 30.
Pilobates pilosellus Balogh, 1960b: 98, figs 24–25.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Rostrozetes* Sellnick, 1925**

***Rostrozetes angulifer* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

Rostrozetes angulifer Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 48, figs 10A–C.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG, two paratypes NMT.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and ten paratypes.

Remarks. In the vial labelled as holotype there are two specimens.

***Rostrozetes bothulifer* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

Rostrozetes bothulifer Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 50, figs 11A–B.

Rostrozetes bothulifer: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 64.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype NMT.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and eleven paratypes.

***Rostrozetes cristatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Rostrozetes cristatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 66, fig. 68.

Rostrozetes cristatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 65.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

***Rostrozetes cubanus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Rostrozetes cubanus Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 22, figs 16A–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and ten paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description only a holotype is mentioned. However, a size range is given, indicating that the description is based on several specimens.

***Rostrozetes dispar* (Balogh, 1958)**

Peloribates dispar Balogh, 1958: 30.

Trachyoribates dispar Balogh, 1960b: 100, figs 28–29.

Rostrozetes dispar: Subías 2017: 447.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes (0-1152-68/Afr).

Remarks. In the original description there are no data on the type material examined, therefore all specimens in the type series must be considered as syntypes.

***Rostrozetes florens* Balogh, 1970**

Rostrozetes florens Balogh, 1970a: 64, fig. 55.

Rostrozetes florens: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 149.

Rostrozetes florens: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 883.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Rostrozetes geminisetosus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Rostrozetes geminisetosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 289, figs 16A–B.

Rostrozetes geminisetosus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 65.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Rostrozetes irregularis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Rostrozetes irregularis Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 66, fig. 69–70.

Rostrozetes irregularis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 149.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Rostrozetes monstruosus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Rostrozetes monstruosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 66, fig. 71.

Rostrozetes monstruosus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 65.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Rostrozetes ovulum* (Berlese, 1908)**

Trachyoribates ovulum Berlese, 1908: 3

Peloribates areolatus Balogh, 1958: 29.

Trachyoribates areolatus: Balogh 1960b: 100, fig. 31.

Trachyoribates dorsalis Balogh, 1958: 27.

Peloribates punctulatus Balogh, 1958: 30.

Trachyoribates punctulatus Balogh 1960b: 100, fig. 30.

Rostrozetes punctulifer Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 51, fig. 12.

Rostrozetes trimorphus Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 52, fig. 13.

Rostrozetes ovulum: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 149.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren (*Peloribates areolatus*). Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren. (*Peloribates punctulatus*). Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG (*Rostrozetes punctulifer*). Holotype and eighteen paratypes HNHM, two paratypes MHNG, one paratype NMT (*Rostrozetes trimorphus*). Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren. (*Trachyoribates dorsalis*)

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found (*Peloribates areolatus*). Six paratypes (0-1151-68/Afr) (*Peloribates punctulatus*). Holotype and one paratype (*Rostrozetes punctulifer*). Holotype and five paratypes (*Rostrozetes trimorphus*). No material was found (*Trachyoribates dorsalis*).

Remarks. Balogh (1960b) give additional information on the type series of *Peloribates areolatus* (holotype and thirty paratypes) and *Peloribates punctulatus* (holotype and eight paratypes). The original descriptions did not include data on the type specimens, therefore the holotype and paratype designations are invalid. Consequently, both type series should be considered as syntypes.

***Rostrozetes perezinigo* P. Balogh, 1995**

Rostrozetes perezinigo P. Balogh, 1995: 6, figs 9–10.

Rostrozetes perezinigo: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 65.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fifteen paratypes, Balogh Collection, Budapest.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Rostrozetes pinguis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Rostrozetes pinguis Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 290, figs 17A–C.

Rostrozetes pinguis: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 66.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and seven paratypes.

***Rostrozetes polygonatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Rostrozetes polygonatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 68, fig. 72–73.

Rostrozetes polygonatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 66.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. Holotype and greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and eight paratypes.

Remarks. Only six paratypes are mentioned in the original description.

***Rostrozetes pseudofurcatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1968**

Rostrozetes pseudofurcatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 334, figs 33–34.

Rostrozetes pseudofurcatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 66.

Rostrozetes pseudofurcatus: Fredes 2018: 118.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fifty paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited also in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-396-68/D-Am) and fifty paratypes (0-397-68/D-Am).

***Rostrozetes pulcherrimus* Balogh, 1961**

Rostrozetes pulcherrimus Balogh, 1961d: 29, fig. 35.

Trachyoribates (Rostrozetes) pulcherrimus: Mahunka 2009a: 120.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Trachyoribates* Berlese, 1908**

***Trachyoribates fenestrata* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1974)**

Magyaria fenestrata Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 262, figs 12A–C.

Magyaria fenestrata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 165.

Trachyoribates fenestratus: Ermilov 2019: 2323.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and six paratypes.

Remarks. There are no type markings on the vials but both are labelled "sp. nov." and collected by K. Choo in Malaysia.

***Trachyoribates incisa* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1974)**

Magyaria incisa Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 261, figs 11A–D.

Magyaria incisa: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 166.

Trachyoribates incius: Ermilov 2019: 2323.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty paratypes.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

Remarks. There are no type markings on the vials but both are labelled "sp. nov."

***Trachyoribates ornata* (Balogh, 1963)**

Magyaria ornata Balogh, 1963: 46, fig. 20.

Trachyoribates ornatus: Ermilov 2019: 2323.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren. and two paratypes.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Trachyoribates pulcherrima* (Balogh, 1970)**

Magyaria pulcherrima Balogh, 1970a: 62, fig. 54.

Trachyoribates pulcherrimus: Ermilov 2019: 2323.

Magyaria pulcherrima: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 883.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Trachyoribates reticulata* (Balogh, 1958)**

Scheloribates reticulatus Balogh, 1958: 26.
Magyaria reticulata: Balogh 1963: 44, figs 17–19.
Trachyoribates reticulata: Ermilov 2019: 2323.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Trachyoribates strinovichi* (Balogh, 1970)**

Magyaria strinovichi Balogh, 1970b: 321, pl. XIV.
Figs 83–84.
Trachyoribates strinovichi: Ermilov 2019: 2323.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Setoxylobates* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967**

***Setoxylobates foveolatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967**

Setoxylobates foveolatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 59, pl. XII. Figs 62–63.
Setoxylobates foveolatus: Ermilov & Liao 2020: 1518.
Setoxylobates foveolatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 150.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Trixylobates* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

***Trixylobates bidactylus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Trixylobates bidactylus Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 291, figs 18A–B.
Trixylobates bidactylus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 66.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and six paratypes.

***Vilhenabates* Balogh, 1963**

***Vilhenabates minutus* (Balogh, 1958)**

Peloribates minutus Balogh, 1958: 29.
Vilhenabates minutus: Balogh 1963: 43, fig. 16.
Vilhenabates (Vilhenabates) minutus: Subías 2004: 207.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. According to the HNHM records, there should be two "paratypes" in the collection, which are actually syntypes due to the lack of holotype designation in the original publication, but we did not find them.

***Vilhenabates simplex* Balogh, 1970**

Vilhenabates simplex Balogh, 1970a: 62, fig. 53.
Vilhenabates (Vilhenabates) simplex: Subías 2004: 207.
Vilhenabates simplex: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 883.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

MOCHLOZETIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1960

***Drymobatoides (Rykella)* Balogh, 1962**

***Drymobatoides (Rykella) insignis* (Balogh, 1962)**

Rykella insignis Balogh, 1962d: 110, figs 36–37.
Drymobatoides insignis: Ermilov & Corpuz-Raros 2017: 300.
Drymobatoides (Rykella) insignis: Subías 2018: 393.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. There is no clear type marking in the vial, but the locality is identical to the paratype (No. 111087 Africa Or.).

Mahunkazetes J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1992

Mahunkazetes longicuspis (Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)

Podoribates longicuspis Balogh & Mahunka, 1967b: 38, figs 5–6.

Mahunkazetes longisuspis: Subías 2004: 185.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-134-64/Afr) and four paratypes (0-135/67/Afr).

Unguizetes Sellnick, 1925

Unguizetes incertus (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)

Uracrobates incertus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 20, figs 57–58.

Unguizetes incertus: Mahunka 1998: 866, fig. 42.

Unguizetes (Unguizetes) incertus: Subías 2004: 186.

Unguizetes incertus: Ermilov 2016b: 1296.

Unguizetes incertus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-550-68/D-Am) and one paratype (0-551-68/D-Am).

Unguizetes longiporosus (Balogh & Mahunka, 1966)

Terrazetes longiporosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 23, figs 37–38.

Unguizetes (Unguizetes) longiporosus: Subías 2004: 186.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twelve paratypes NM, eleven paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Nine paratypes (0-120-64/Afr).

Unguizetes setiger (Balogh & Mahunka, 1978)

Uracrobates setiger Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 292, figs 19A–B.

Unguizetes setiger: Ermilov 2016b: 1295.

Unguizetes setiger: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 67.

Unguizetes (Unguizetes) setiger: Subías 2019: 350.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and eight paratypes.

Uracrobates (Uracrobates) Balogh & Mahunka, 1967

Uracrobates (Uracrobates) magniporosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1967

Uracrobates magniporosus Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 58, pl. XII, figs 60–61.

Uracrobates (Uracrobates) magniporosus: Ermilov & Martens 2015: 189.

Uracrobates magniporosus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 153.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-71-67/As) and one paratype (0-72-67/As).

NASOBATIDAE BALOGH, 1972

Nasobates Woolley, 1966

Nasobates mirabilis Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Nasobates mirabilis Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 21, figs 61–62.

Nasobates mirabilis: Balogh & Mahunka 1977b: 262, figs 9D–E.

Nasobates mirabilis: Mahunka 1998: 846.

Nasobates mirabilis: Ermilov, Niedbała & Friedrich 2016: 63.

Nasobates mirabilis: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

ORIBATULIDAE THOR, 1929

***Capiloppia* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

***Capiloppia capillata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Capiloppia capillata Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 23, figs 39–40.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes NM, five paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Four paratypes.

***Constrictobates* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

***Constrictobates lineolatus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Constrictobates lineolatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966c: 561, figs 9–11.

Constrictobates lineolatus: Lee 1987: 40, figs 3–8.

Constrictobates lineolatus: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 159.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twelve paratypes. Type specimens are in the Austral Museum and HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Four paratypes.

Remarks. According to the documentation in HNHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1995.

***Gerloubia (Monophauloppia)* P. Balogh, 1988**

***Gerloubia (Monophauloppia) planissima* (P. Balogh, 1988)**

Paraphauloppia (Monophauloppia) planissima P. Balogh, 1988c: 334, figs 31–34.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Grandjeania* Balogh, 1963**

***Grandjeania bicaudata* (Balogh, 1961)**

Grandjeanella bicaudata Balogh, 1961f: 306.

Grandjeania bicaudata: Balogh 1963: 43, figs 14–15.

Grandjeania bicaudata: Ermilov & Smit 2017: 797.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren and three paratypes (Balogh 1963).

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. We did not find the original description of *Grandjeanella* Balogh, 1961 nor its type *G. bicaudata*. Nomenclator Zoologicus Vol. 7 (Edwards & Vevers 1975) refers this name to Balogh (1961f) world Oribatida key. Might be both names were published first in that paper.

***Jornadia* Wallwork & Weems, 1984**

***Jornadia dactyloscopica* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1968)**

Oribatula dactyloscopica Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 334, figs 29–30.

Woolleybates dactyloscopica: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 78.

Jornadia dactyloscopica: Akrami 2015: 485.

Jornadia dactyloscopica: Fredes 2018: 122.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-403-68/D-Am).

***Liebstadia (Liebstadia)* Oudemans, 1906**

***Liebstadia (Liebstadia) piligera* Balogh, 1958**

Liebstadia piligera Balogh, 1958: 25.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Oribatula* Berlese, 1896**

***Oribatula (Oribatula) elegantissima* Balogh & Mahunka, 1965**

Oribatula elegantissima Balogh & Mahunka, 1965: 464, figs 24–26.

Oribatula elegantissima: Bayartogtokh 2010: 59, figs 65Г, Д.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

***Oribatula (Oribatula) fraenzlei* Balogh & Mahunka, 1968**

Oribatula fraenzlei Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 332, figs 27–28.

Paraphauloppia (Paraphauloppia) fraenzlei: Subías 2017: 401.

Oribatula fraenzlei: Fredes 2018: 123.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-404-68/D-Am).

***Phauloppia* Berlese, 1908**

***Phauloppia rauschenensis* (Sellnick, 1908)**

Phauloppia paspalevi Csiszár, 1962b: 291, figs 30–31.

Eremaeus rauschenensis Sellnick, 1908: 27, figs 2–3.

Phauloppia rauschenensis: Aroyyo, O'Connell & Bloger 2017: 139.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Phauloppia topali* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963**

Phauloppia topali Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 485, fig. 33.

Phauloppia topali: Fredes 2018: 124.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1112-68/D-Am).

***Reductobates* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

***Reductobates brassi* Balogh, 1970**

Reductobates brassi Balogh, 1970b: 314, pl. X. Figs 62–63.

Reductobates brassi: Ermilov & Minor 2016: 1131.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Reductobates humeratus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Reductobates humeratus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966c: 566, figs 16–17.

Reductobates humeratus: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 174.

Reductobates humeratus: Ermilov 2016b: 1131.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and sixteen paratypes. Type specimens are in the Austral Museum and HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Eighteen paratypes.

Remarks. According to the documentation in the HMHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1995 but Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it there.

***Zygoribatula* Berlese, 1916**

***Zygorybatula baloghi* Mahunka, 1986**

Zygorybatula undulata Balogh, 1966: 77, fig. 10.

Zygoribatula baloghi Mahunka, 1986: 77, **nom. nov.** pro *Zygoribatula undulata* Balogh, 1966 nec *Zygoribatula undulata* Berlese, 1916

Zygoribatula koki J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 276: pl. 382: 5. **nom. nov.** pro *Zygoribatula undulata* Balogh, 1966 nec *Zygoribatula undulata* Berlese, 1916.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-116-67/Afr).

Remarks. J. Balogh & P. Balogh (2002) overlooked the fact that Mahunka (1986) has provided yet a new replacement name for the primary homonym *Zygoribatula undulata* Balogh, 1966.

Zygoribatula dentata Balogh, 1958

Zygoribatula dentata Balogh, 1958: 26.
Oribatula (Zygoribatula) dentata: Subías 2004: 188.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Zygorybatula longicuspis Balogh, 1966

Zygorybatula longicuspis Balogh, 1966: 77, fig. 11.
Oribatula (Zygoribatula) longicuspis: Subías 2004: 189.

Type material in the literature. No data available.
Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-130-67/Afr) and one paratype (0-131-67/Afr).

Zygorybatula sabulosa Balogh, 1966

Zygorybatula sabulosa Balogh, 1966: 77, fig. 12.
Oribatula (Zygoribatula) sabulosa: Subías 2004: 189.

Type material in the literature. No data available.
Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-118-67/Afr).

Zygorybatula salina Balogh, 1966

Zygorybatula salina Balogh, 1966: 76, fig. 9.
Oribatula (Zygoribatula) salina: Subías 2004: 189.

Type material in the literature. No data available.
Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-117-67/Afr) and one paratype (0-151-67/Afr).

ORIPODIDAE JACOT, 1925

***Benoibates* Balogh, 1958**

***Benoibates amazonicus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Benoibates amazonicus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 273, figs 29–30.
Benoibates amazonicus: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 144.

Benoibates amazonicus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 68.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Benoibates bolivianus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Benoibates bolivianus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 21, figs 63–64.

Benoibates bolivianus: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 145.

Benoibates bolivianus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 68.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Benoibates borhidii* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

Benoibates borhidii Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 54, figs 19A–B.

Benoibates borhidii: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 68.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Benoibates flagelliger* Balogh, 1958**

Benoibates flagelliger Balogh, 1958: 25.

Benoibates flagelliger: Balogh 1960b: 96, figs 22–23.

Benoibates flagelliger: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 144.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Benoibates reducta* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1967)**

Haploripoda reducta Balogh & Mahunka, 1967b: 43, figs 11–12.

Haploripoda reducta: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 145.

Benoibates reductus: Subías 2004: 203.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-132/67/Afr) and three paratypes (0-133-67/Afr).

***Birobates* Balogh, 1970**

***Birobates fenicheli* Balogh, 1970**

Birobates fenicheli Balogh, 1970b: 313, pl. X. Figs 58–59.

Nanobates fenicheli J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1984: 277, figs 175–176.

Euscheloribates (Trischeloribates) fenicheli Subías 2008: 372.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Birobates reductus* Balogh, 1970**

Birobates reductus Balogh, 1970b: 313, pl. IX. fig. 56, pl. X. Fig. 57.

Birobates reductus: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 144.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in the HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Five paratypes.

***Brachyoripoda* Balogh, 1970**

***Brachyoripoda foveolata* Balogh, 1970**

Brachyoripoda foveolata Balogh, 1970a: 58, figs 45–46.

Brachyoripoda foveolata: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 143.

Brachyoripoda foveolata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 154.

Brachyoripoda foveolata: Ermilov, Khaustov & Johar-chi 2020: 883.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Campbellobates* Wallwork, 1964**

***Campbellobates acanthus hawaiiensis* P. Balogh, 1985**

Campbellobates acanthus hawaiiensis P. Balogh, 1985c: 61.

Campbellobates acanthus hawaiiensis: Swift & Norton 1998: 16.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Two "types".

Remarks. The taxon has been described on two specimens, therefore they are syntypes.

***Cosmopirnodus* Balogh, 1970**

***Cosmopirnodus pulcherrimus* Balogh, 1970**

Cosmopirnodus pulcherrimus Balogh, 1970b: 315, pl. XI. Figs 66–67.

Cosmopirnodus pulcherrimus: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 141.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Oripoda* Banks, 1904**

***Oripoda alata* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1980)**

Gymnobates alatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 55, figs 20A–B.

Oripoda alata: Subías 2004: 204.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Oripoda angolensis* (Balogh, 1963)**

Truncopes angolensis Balogh, 1963: 47, figs 21–22.

Oripoda angolensis: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 138.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. The species is described on a

single holotype, so the specimen marked as paratype, although the locality matches the holotype, may not belong to the type series (or represents the holotype).

***Oripoda anguina* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Truncopes anguinus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 273, fig. 32.

Oripoda anguina: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 138.

Oripoda anguina: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 105.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Oripoda cordobensis* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1990)**

Truncopes australis Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 336, figs 35–36.

Oripoda australis: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 138.

Oripoda cordobensis J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1990: 105. nom. nov.

Oripoda cordobensis: Fredes 2018: 127.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited also in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffil, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-398-68/D-Am) and three paratypes (0-399-68/D-Am).

***Oripoda canagaratnami* (Balogh, 1970)**

Truncopes canagaratnami Balogh, 1970a: 57, fig. 44.

Oripoda canagaratnami: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 138.

Oripoda canagaratnami: Ermilov, Khaustov & Johar-chi 2020: 883.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Oripoda cubana* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1980)**

Truncopes cubanus Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 57, figs 21A–B. No

Oripoda cubana: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 105.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Oripoda divergens* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Truncopes divergens Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 274, fig. 33.

Oripoda divergens: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 138.

Oripoda divergens: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 105.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Oripoda humerata* (Balogh, 1959)**

Benoibates humeratus Balogh, 1959b: 102, figs 30–32.

Oripoda humerata Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 138.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Oripoda lenkoi* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Oripoda lenkoi Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 286, figs 14A–B.

Oripoda lenkoi: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 68.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

***Oripoda magna* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Truncopes magnus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969c: 274, fig. 34.

Oripoda magnus: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 138. comb. nov.

Oripoda magna: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 105.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Oripoda prominens* P. Balogh, 1985**

Oripoda prominens P. Balogh, 1985c: 57, figs 1A–B.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Oripoda scissuratus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1980)**

Truncopes scissuratus Balogh & Mahunka, 1980: 58, figs 22A–B.

Oripoda scissurata: Subías 2004: 204.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Four "types".

Remarks. The vial labelled holotype contains four specimens. The other vial labelled paratype is empty. It seems that the holotype and the paratypes were put together at some point.

***Parapirnodus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1968**

***Parapirnodus longus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1968**

Parapirnodus longus Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 338, figs 39–40.

Parapirnodus longus: Fredes 2018: 132.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fourteen paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-401-68/D-Am) and one paratype.

***Protoripoda (Baloghates) Özdikmen* 2008**

***Protoripoda (Baloghates) ornatissima* (Balogh, 1959)**

Oripoda ornatissima Balogh, 1959b: 102, figs 33–35.

Baloghates (Baloghates) ornatissimus: Özdikmen 2008a: 226.

Protoripoda (Baloghates) ornatissima: Subías 2009: 390.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Teruren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Protoripoda (Protoripoda) Balogh, 1970

***Protoripoda (Protoripoda) insularis* Balogh, 1970**

Protoripoda insularis Balogh, 1970a: 57, figs 42–43.

Protoripoda insularis: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 136.

Protoripoda insularis: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 883.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Protoripoda (Protoripoda) woolleyi* Balogh, 1970**

Protoripoda woolleyi Balogh, 1970b: 316, pl. XI. Figs 68–69.

Protoripoda woolleyi: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 136.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Pseudopirnodus* Baranek, 1985**

***Pseudopirnodus domrowi* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1978)**

Pirnodus domrowi Balogh & Mahunka, 1978b: 46, figs 40–42.

Pirnodus domrowi: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 172.

Pseudopirnodus domrowi: Subías 2004: 204.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, CSIRO Canberra.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. The holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1994 but Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it there.

***Pseudopirnodus imitans* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1968)**

Pirnodus imitans Balogh & Mahunka, 1968a: 338, figs 37–38.

Pirnodus imitans: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 142.

Pseudopirnodus imitans: Subías 2004: 204.

Truncopes imitans: Fredes 2018: 128.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited also in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffil, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-405-68/D-Am) and one paratype (0-404-68/D-Am).

***Pteroripoda* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

***Pteroripoda minutissima* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Pteroripoda minutissima Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 20, figs 14A–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Scriptoripoda* P. Balogh, 1985**

***Scriptoripoda excellens* P. Balogh, 1985**

Scriptoripoda excellens P. Balogh, 1985c: 59, figs 2A–B.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Scriptoripoda tenorioae* P. Balogh, 1985**

Scriptoripoda tenorioae P. Balogh, 1985c: 59, figs 3A–B.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

PARAKALUMMIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1936

***Neoribates* (*Neoribates*) Berlese, 1914**

***Neoribates* (*Neoribates*) *erectus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Protokalumma erecta Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 64, fig. 66.

Neoribates erectus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 144.

Neoribates (*Neoribates*) *erectus*: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 69.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffil, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Neoribates* (*Neoribates*) *flagellum* (Balogh, 1970)**

Protokalumma flagellum Balogh, 1970b: 324, pl. XVI, fig. 93, pl. XVII, fig. 94.

Neoribates (*Neoribates*) *flagellum*: Subías 2008: 404.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Neoribates* (*Neoribates*) *jacoti* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967**

Protokalumma jacoti Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 55, pl. VIII, Figs 44–45.

Neoribates (*Protokalumma*) *jacoti*: Subías 2004: 212.

Neoribates (*Neoribates*) *jacoti*: Subías 2008: 404.

Neoribates jacoti: Ermilov & Kalúz 2020: 1610.

Neoribates jacoti: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 156.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-58-67/As).

***Neoribates* (*Neoribates*) *punctulata* (Balogh, 1970)**

Protokalumma punctulata Balogh, 1970b: 325, pl. XVII, fig. 95.

Neoribates (*Neoribates*) *punctulatus*: Subías 2008: 404.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Neoribates (Neoribates) setiger* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Neoribates setiger Balogh & Mahunka, 1978a: 47, figs 43–44.

Neoribates setiger: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 161.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and partly the paratypes are deposited in CSIRO, Canberra; another part of paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. Holotype was sent to CSIRO Canberra in 1977.11.28 but, Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it there.

***Neoribates (Neoribates) szabadosi* (Balogh, 1970)**

Protokalumma szabadosi Balogh, 1970b: 325, pl. XVII, fig. 96.

Neoribates (Neoribates) szabadosi: Subías 2008: 404.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Neoribates (Perezinigokalumma) Subías, 2004

***Neoribates (Perezinigokalumma) foveolata* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1969)**

Parakalumma foveolata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 16, figs 50–51.

Parakalumma foveolata: Balogh & Mahunka 1978c: 294, figs 21A–B.

Parakalumma foveolata: Mahunka 1998: 864, fig. 37.

Neoribates (Perezinigokalumma) foveolata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 69.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fifteen paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of

the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajska and T. Woolley.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and fourteen paratypes.

***Neoribates (Perezinigokalumma) munizi* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1974)**

Parakalumma munizi Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 23, figs 17A–C.

Parakalumma munizi: Balogh & Mahunka 1980: 22.

Neoribates (Perezinigokalumma) munizi: Subías 2008: 405.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and forty-three paratypes. The holotype (except where no paratypes representing the species are available) are deposited in the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba, while the paratypes and the exceptions mentioned above are in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and eighteen paratypes.

SCHELOBATIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1933

***Balazsella* Mahunka, 1983**

***Balazsella ilhabellae* J. Balogh & Palacios-Vargas, 1996**

Balazsella ilhabellae J. Balogh & Palacios-Vargas, 1996: 11, figs 1–4.

Balazsella ilhabellae: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 69.

Balazsella ilhabellae: Subías 2017: 322.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM, and six paratypes. The paratypes are deposited in the collection of both authors and MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and four paratypes.

***Balazsella mexicana* J. Balogh & Palacios-Vargas, 1996**

Balazsella mexicana J. Balogh & Palacios-Vargas, 1996: 13, figs 5–8.

Phylloribatula mexicana Subías 2017: 322.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM, and eight paratypes. The paratypes are deposited in the collection of both authors and MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

Cosmobates Balogh, 1959

***Cosmobates tunicatus* Balogh, 1959**

Cosmobates tunicatus Balogh, 1959b: 104, figs 36–39.
Cosmobates tunicatus: Balogh 1970b: 321.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren and four paratypes Musée de Dundo and ELTE.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Cryptozetes Hammer, 1962

***Cryptozetes elongata* (Balogh & Csiszár, 1963)**

Dometorina elongata Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 485, figs 42–43.

Cryptozetes elongata: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 91.

Cryptozetes elongata: Fredes 2018: 129.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Dometorina (Dometorina) Grandjean, 1951

***Dometorina (Dometorina) tropica* (Balogh, 1958)**

Hemileius tropicus Balogh, 1958: 25.

Hemileius tropicus: Balogh 1960b: 96, figs 20–21.

Dometorina tropica: Coetzer 1968: 20.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. There is no information on the type material in the original description. In HNHM we found a vial labelled "paratypes" but the locality on the label is Congo Belge. This may refer to the museum from which the material came. Expert

verification is required to determine the status of this specimen.

***Fissurobates* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Fissurobates spectabilis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Fissurobates spectabilis Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 65, fig. 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Hammerabates* Balogh, 1970**

***Hammerabates trisetosus* Balogh, 1970**

Hammerabates trisetosus Balogh, 1970b: 312, pl. X.

Figs 60–61.

Hammerabates trisetosus: Aoki & Ohkubo 1974: 140.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Hemileius (Hemileius) Berlese, 1916

***Hemileius (Hemileius) glaber* (Balogh, 1970)**

Tuberemaesus glaber Balogh, 1970b: 309, pl. IX. fig.

51.

Hemileius (Hemileius) glaber: Subas 2014: 396.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nine paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and eight paratypes.

***Hemileius (Hemileius) gressitti* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Hemileius gressitti J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 321, fig. 15.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Hemileius (Monoscheloribates)* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Hemileius (Monoscheloribates) foveolatus* (Balogh, 1958)**

Liebstadia foveolata Balogh, 1958: 25.

Liebstadia foveolata: Balogh 1959c: 15, figs 11–14.

Liebstadia foveolata: Balogh 1962d: 96.

Hemileius (Monoscheloribates) foveolatus: Subías 2008: 366.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Hemileius (Tuberemaeus)* Sellnick, 1930**

***Hemileius (Tuberemaeus) tridactylus* (Balogh, 1959)**

Liebstadia foveolata tridactyla Balogh, 1959c: 15, fig. 13.

Tuberemaeus foveolatus tridactylus: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2009: 57, figs 28–29.

Hemileius (Tuberemaeus) tridactylus: Subías 2014: 409.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Heteroleius* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

***Heteroleius longissimus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Heteroleius longissimus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966b: 38, figs 24–25.

Heteroleius longissimus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 184.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-101-67/Afr).

***Monoschelobates* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Monoschelobates parvus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Monoschelobates parvus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 18, figs 53–54.

Hemileius (Monoschelobates) parvus: Subías 2017: 408.

Monoschelobates parvus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 70.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and thirteen paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and eight paratypes.

***Mucrobates* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

***Mucrobates fissuratus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

Mucrobates fissuratus Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 47, fig. 9.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Muliercula* Coetzer, 1968**

***Muliercula discrepans* (Balogh, 1959)**

Scheloribates discrepans Balogh, 1959b: 100, figs 25–26.

Muliercula discrepans: Shtanchaeva, Ermilov, Tolsitkov & Subías 2014: 83.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Plumobates Balogh & Mahunka, 1966

**Plumobates decoratus Balogh & Mahunka,
1966**

Plumobates decoratus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966c: 564, figs 12–13.

Plumobates decoratus: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 165.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. The type specimens are in the Austral Museum.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. According to the documentation in the HMHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1995 but Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it there.

**Poroscheloribates Arillo, Gil-Martin & Subías
1994**

Poroscheloribates incertus (Balogh, 1970)

Areozetes (?) incertus Balogh, 1970a: 60, figs 51–52.

Poroscheloribates incertus: Subías 2017: 413.

Areozetes incertus: Ermilov 2015: 74.

Poroscheloribates incertus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 161.

Poroscheloribates incertus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 883.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Scheloribates (Perscheloribates) Hammer, 1973

**Scheloribates (Perscheloribates) setiger
(P. Balogh, 1988)**

Ischeloribates setiger P. Balogh, 1988c: 336, figs 35–36.

Scheloribates (Perscheloribates) setiger: Subías 2016: 423.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Scheloribates (Scheloribates) Berlese, 1908

**Scheloribates (Scheloribates) bilineatus Balogh,
1958**

Scheloribates bilineatus Balogh, 1958: 26.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

**Scheloribates (Scheloribates) caprai Bernini,
1973**

Scheloribates subsimilis Balogh, 1962d:127, fig. 77.

Scheloribates caprai Bernini, 1973: 459, figs a–g.

nom. nov. pro *Scheloribates subsimilis* Balogh, 1962 non Michelčič, 1956

Scheloribates baloghi Pérez-Íñigo, 1982: 230. **nom.**

nov. pro *Scheloribates subsimilis* Balogh, 1962 non Michelčič, 1956 nec. *Scheloribates baloghi* Kardar, 1977.

Scheloribates (S.) caprai: Subías 2004: 199.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. Bernini (1973) provided a replacement name for the junior homonym *Scheloribates subsimilis* Balogh, 1962. Later, Pérez-Íñigo (1982) has also provided a replacement name *Scheloribates baloghi* which is itself a junior homonym of *Scheloribates baloghi* Kardar, 1977. As there is an available replacement name *Sch. caprai* Bernini, a new replacement for Pérez-Íñigo's homonym is not necessary.

**Scheloribates (Scheloribates) concentricus
Balogh, 1962**

Scheloribates concentricus Balogh, 1962d: 125, figs 73–74.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

***Scheloribates (Scheloribates) discifer* Balogh,
1959**

Scheloribates discifer Balogh, 1959b: 100, figs 23–24.
Scheloribates discifer: Ermilov & Rybalov 2019b: 238.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Scheloribates (Scheloribates) iteratus* Subías,
2004**

Scheloribates microclava Balogh, 1962d: 127, fig. 76.
Scheloribates (S.) iteratus Subías, 2004: 200. **nom. nov.**
pro *Scheloribates microclava* Balogh, 1962 non
Hammer, 1961.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal de l’Afrique Centrale à Tervuren,

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Scheloribates (Scheloribates) leleupi* Balogh,
1959**

Scheloribates leleupi Balogh, 1959b: 100, figs 19–22.
Scheloribates leleupi: Balogh 1962d: 96.
Scheloribates leleupi: Ermilov & Khaustov 2018: 153.
Scheloribates leleupi: Ermilov & Rybalov 2019b: 243,
fig. 13–24.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren and four paratypes, Musée de Dundo and ELTE.

Deposited in HNHM: Three paratypes (0+1106-68/Afr).

***Scheloribates (Scheloribates) maximus* Balogh,
1962**

Scheloribates maximus Balogh, 1962d: 124, figs 70–72.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal de l’Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Scheloribates (Scheloribates) microsetosus* Lee
& Pajak, 1990**

Megascheloribates microsetosus Lee & Pajak, 1990: 238, figs 25–27.

Megascheloribates pajaki J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 322. **nom. nov.** pro *Megascheloribates microsetosus* Lee & Pajak, 1990 nec. *Scheloribates microsetosus* Wallwork, 1977

Scheloribates (Scheloribates) pajaki: Subías 2023: 389.

Remarks. J. Balogh & P. Balogh (2002) provided a replacement name *Megascheloribates pajaki* **nom. nov.** for *Megascheloribates microsetosus* Lee & Pajak, 1990 which was a secondary homonym of *Scheloribates microsetosus* Wallwork, 1977 in the genus *Megascheloribates* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh 2002: 322). In the most recent list of oribatid mites (Subías 2023), the species of Lee & Pajak (1990) is listed in the genus *Scheloribates* and the species of Wallwork (1977) is listed in the genus *Topobates*, so the secondary homonymy no longer exists. According to ICZN Art. 59.4 “A species-group name rejected after 1960 on grounds of secondary homonymy is to be reinstated as valid by an author who considers that the two species-group taxa in question are not congeneric, unless it is invalid for some other reason.” Therefore the valid name now is *Scheloribates (Scheloribates) microsetosus*.

***Scheloribates (Scheloribates) ornatus* Balogh,
1959**

Scheloribates ornatus Balogh, 1959b: 100, figs 27–29.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren and five paratypes, Musée de Dundo and ELTE.

Deposited in HNHM: Five paratypes (0-1105-68/Afr).

***Scheloribates (Scheloribates) peractus* Balogh,
1962**

Scheloribates peractus Balogh, 1962d: 127, fig. 78.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.
Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Scheloribates (Scheloribates) polygonatus*
Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Scheloribates polygonatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1974a: 21, figs 15A–D.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences, Cuba.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Scheloribates (Scheloribates) pseudoprincipalis*
Balogh, 1962**

Scheloribates pseudoprincipalis Balogh, 1962d: 129, figs 79–80.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Scheloribates (Scheloribates) rugiceps* Balogh,
1962**

Scheloribates rugiceps Balogh, 1962d: 126, fig. 75.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Scheloribates (Scheloribates) striolatus* Balogh,
1961**

Scheloribates striolatus Balogh, 1961d: 27, figs 32–34.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Topobates Grandjean, 1958

***Topobates magnus* (Balogh, 1962)**

Setobates magnus Balogh, 1962d: 123, figs 67–69.
Topobates magnus: Subías 2004: 203.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes, Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1107-68/Afr) locality No. 18, an other one "sp. n." from No. 14, and three paratypes from No. 18. without type label.

***Topobates multisetosus* (Balogh, 1970)**

Tuberemaeus multisetosus Balogh, 1970a: 58, fig. 48.

Tuberemaeus multisetosus: P. Balogh 1988b: 172.

Topobates multisetosus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 883.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eighteen paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and seventeen paratypes.

Tuberemaeus Sellnick, 1930

***Tuberemaeus areolatus* Balogh & Mahunka,
1967**

Tuberemaeus areolatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1967b: 40, figs 9–10.

Hemileius (Tuberemaeus) areolatus: Subías 2004: 193.

Tuberemaeus aerolatus: Ermilov & Khaustov 2018: 153.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-124-67/Afr) and two paratypes (0-125/67/Afr).

***Tuberemaeus dispar* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Tuberemaeus dispar Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 256, figs 8A–D.

Hemileius (Tuberemaeus) dispar: Subías 2004: 193.

Tuberemaeus dispar: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 194.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and six paratypes.

***Tuberemaeus fissuratus* Balogh, 1970**

Tuberemaeus fissuratus Balogh, 1970b: 309, pl. IX, figs 52–53.

Hemileius (Tuberemaeus) fissuratus: Subías 2004: 193.
Tuberemaeus fissuratus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 194.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Tuberemaeus lineatus* Balogh, 1970**

Tuberemaeus lineatus Balogh, 1970b: 311, pl. VII. fig. 44.
Hemileius (Tuberemaeus) lineatus: Subías 2004: 193.
Tuberemaeus lineatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 194.
Tuberemaeus lineatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 168.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Tuberemaeus longisetosus* Balogh, 1970**

Tuberemaeus longisetosus Balogh, 1970b: 310, pl. VIII. figs 46–47.
Hemileius (Tuberemaeus) longisetosus: Subías 2004: 193.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

***Tuberemaeus propinquus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1974**

Tuberemaeus propinquus Balogh & Mahunka, 1974b: 255, figs 7A–D.
Hemileius (Tuberemaeus) propinquus: Subías 2004: 194.
Tuberemaeus propinquus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 195.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Tuberemaeus punctatus* Balogh, 1970**

Tuberemaeus punctatus Balogh, 1970b: 309, pl. VIII. fig. 50. "nom. praecoc." por Hammer, 1961
Hemileius (Tuberemaeus) neonominatus Subías 2004: 194. **nom. nov.** pro *Tuberemaeus punctatus* Balogh, 1970 non *Hemileius (Urubambates) punctatus* (Hammer, 1961).

Tuberemaeus neonominatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 195.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. The secondary homonymy no longer exists, therefore the original name must be considered valid (ICZN Art. 59.4).

***Tuberemaeus similis* Balogh, 1970**

Tuberemaeus similis Balogh, 1970a: 58, fig. 47.
Hemileius (Tuberemaeus) similis: Subías 2004: 186.
Tuberemaeus similis: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 883.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Tuberemaeus tuberculatus* Balogh, 1970**

Tuberemaeus tuberculatus Balogh, 1970a: 311, pl. VIII. fig. 45.
Hemileius (Tuberemaeus) tuberculatus: Subías 2004: 194.
Tuberemaeus tuberculatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 196.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype?

Remarks. The vial of the holotype seems to be empty.

***Tuberemaeus vermiculatus* Balogh, 1970**

Tuberemaeus vermiculatus Balogh, 1970a: 310, pl. VIII, figs 48–49.

Hemileius (Tuberemaeus) vermiculatus: Subías 2004: 194.

Tuberemaeus vermiculatus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 196.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Urubambates* Hammer, 1961**

***Urubambates paraguayensis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1981**

Urubambates paraguayensis Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 95, figs 130–135.

Hemileius (Urubambates) paraguayensis: Subías 2004: 194.

Urubambates paraguayensis: Fredes 2018: 135.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

TUBULOZETIDAE P. BALOGH, 1989

***Tubulozetes* P. Balogh, 1989**

***Tubulozetes rostratus* P. Balogh, 1989**

Tubulozetes rostratus P. Balogh, 1989: 24, figs 15–21.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Types.

Remarks. There are two specimens in one vial, the holotype and one of the paratypes. They were put into a common vial from a slide.

ZETOMOTRICHIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1954

***Rohria* Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

***Rohria pulchella* Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

Rohria pulchella Balogh & Mahunka, 1977b: 260, figs 9A–C.

Rohria pulchella: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 73.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

CERATOZETOIDEA JACOT, 1925

CERATOKALUMMIDAE BALOGH, 1970

***Achipterina* Berlese, 1916**

***Achipterina insignis* (Balogh, 1970)**

Ceratokalumma insignis Balogh, 1970b: 324, pl. XVI, figs 91–92.

Achipterina insignis: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 236.

Archipterina insignis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 197.

Archipterina insignis: Ermilov *et al.* 2021b: 2414.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Achipterina kaszabi* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1988)**

Ceratokalumma kaszabi J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1988a: 194, figs 3–6.

Achipterina kaszabi: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 236.

Achipterina kaszabi: Ermilov *et al.* 2021b: 2414.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Achipterina naisselinei* (J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1988)**

Ceratokalumma naisselinei J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1988a: 200, figs 7–11.

Achipterina naisselinei: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 236.

Archipterina naisselinei: Baert 2018: 8. species.

Archipterina naisselinei: Ermilov *et al.* 2021b: 2414.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Guaranozetes Balogh & Mahunka, 1981

Guaranozetes nudus Balogh & Mahunka, 1981

Guaranozetes nudus Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 100, figs 146–149.

Guaranozetes nudus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 73.

Guaranozetes nudus: Fredes 2018: 136.

Guaranozetes nudus: Ermilov *et al.* 2021b: 2414.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Types.

Remarks. There are two vials in HNHM with eight and one specimens and locality codes 47-3 and 47-1 respectively. According to the original description the holotype is from locality 47-3. Either the vials are mislabelled, or the holotype was not separated from the paratypes from the same locality.

CERATOZETIDAE JACOT, 1925

***Allozetes* Berlese, 1913**

***Allozetes africanus* Balogh, 1958**

Allozetes africanus Balogh, 1958: 26.

Allozetes africanus: Balogh 1960b: 98, figs 26–27.

Allozetes africanus: Tseng 1984: 43, figs 142–143.

Allozetes africanus: Mahunka 1988: 882, figs 124–125.

Allozetes africanus: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 172.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Twelve paratypes.

Remarks. As there is no information on the type material in the original description, all specimens should be considered as syntypes.

***Ceratozetes* Berlese, 1908**

***Ceratozetes insignis* Balogh, 1966**

Ceratozetes (?) insignis Balogh, 1966: 72, fig 6.

Farchacarus insignis: Subías 2004: 173.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Ceratozetes heterocuspis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1965**

Ceratozetes heterocuspis Balogh & Mahunka, 1965: 464, figs 22–23.

Ceratozetella heterocuspis: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1992: 236.

Ceratozetella (Ceratozetella) heterocuspis: Subías 2004: 173.

Ceratozetes heterocuspis: Bayartogtokh 2010: 62, figs 71A–F.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Geminozetes (Geminozetes) Balogh & Csiszár, 1963

***Geminozetes (Geminozetes) lamellatus* Balogh, 1966**

Geminozetes (?) lamellatus Balogh, 1966: 72, fig 7.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-107-68/Afr) and twenty seven paratypes (0-106-67/Afr).

Remarks. There is no data on the type series in the original description therefore, all specimens should be regarded as syntypes.

***Geminozetes (Geminozetes) lineatus* Balogh & Csiszár, 1963**

Geminozetes lineatus Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 483, figs 38–39.

Geminozetes lineatus: Fredes 2018: 140.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Leebates* Balogh & Mahunka, 1996**

***Leebates bornemisszai* Balogh & Mahunka
1996**

Leebates bornemisszai Balogh & Mahunka 1996: 158, figs 1–8.

Leebates bornemisszai: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 184.

Trichoribates (Viracochiella) bornemisszai: Subías 2004: 23.

Leebates bornemisszai: Behan-Pelletier & Ermilov 2019: 350.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Lepidozetes* Berlese, 1910**

***Lepidozetes dashidorzsi* Balogh & Mahunka,
1965**

Lepidozetes dashidorzsi Balogh & Mahunka, 1965: 462, figs 20–21.

Lepidozetes dashidorzsi: Bayartogtokh 2010: 70, figs 84Ě–И.

Lepidozetes dashidorzsi: Ryabinin, Liu, Gao & Wu 2018: 255.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

***Lophozetes* P. Balogh, 1985**

***Lophozetes truncatus* P. Balogh, 1985**

Lophozetes truncatus P. Balogh, 1985a: 89, figs 6A–E.

Lophozetes truncatus: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 180.

Macrogena (Macrogena) truncata: Subías 2020: 333.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes.

Remarks. There is no holotype designated in the original description, so all specimens should be considered as syntypes. There is another vial marked as "type material" containing seven specimens, but without an exact locality. In the original description the locality is the same as on the label of the "two paratypes".

***Patagonozetes* J. Balogh & P. Balogh**

***Patagonozetes exornatus* (Balogh & Csiszár,
1963)**

Sphaerozetes exornatus Balogh & Csiszár, 1963: 483, figs 40–41.

Patagonozetes exornatus: Balogh & Balogh 1990: 118.

Patagonozetes exornatus: Fredes 2018:141.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No deposition stated.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Pentazetes (Pentazetes) J. Balogh & P. Balogh,
1983***

***Pentazetes (Pentazetes) mandjeliae* J. Balogh &
P. Balogh, 1983**

Pentazetes mandjeliae J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983c: 325, fig. 17.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Balogh Collection.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

CHAMOBATIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1954

***Ceratobates* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

***Ceratobates pontiger* Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Ceratobates pontiger Balogh & Mahunka, 1969b: 64, fig. 63.

Ceratobates pontiger: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 74.

Ceratobates pontiger: Fredes 2018: 144.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajski and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Ceratobates spathulatus* Balogh & Mahunka,
1981**

Ceratobates spathulatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1981: 98, figs 142–145.

Ceratobates spathulatus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 74.

Ceratobates spathulatus: Fredes 2018: 144.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and five paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and six paratypes.

Chamobates (Chamobates) Hull, 1916

Chamobates (Chamobates) javensis (Hammer, 1979)

Sphaerozetes javensis Hammer, 1979: 62, fig. 109.

Unguizetes hammeri J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 302, pl. 408: 1. **nom nov.** pro *Sphaerozetes javensis* Hammer, 1979 nec. *Sphaerobates javensis* Willmann, 1932.

Chamobates (Chamobates) javensis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 171.

Remarks. J. Balogh & P. Balogh (2002) provided a replacement name *Unguizetes hammeri* nom. nov. for *Sphaerozetes javensis* Hammer, 1979 regarding congeneric with *Sphaerobates javensis* Willmann, 1932 in the genus *Unguizetes*. However, according to Subias (2023), the two species are no longer considered congeneric and Hammer's secondary homonym name should be reinstated. (ICZN Art. 59.4)

Hypozetes Balogh, 1959

Hypozetes imitator Balogh, 1959

Hypozetes imitator Balogh, 1959c: 16, figs 17–19.

Hypozetes imitator: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 172.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1175-68/Afr) and six other paratypes.

Remarks. There is no holotype designated in the original description, therefore, all specimens should be regarded as syntypes.

HUMEROBATIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1971

Africoribates Evans, 1953

Africoribates evansi Balogh, 1959

Africoribates evansi Balogh, 1959b: 104, figs 40–41.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren and one paratype Musée de Dundo and ELTE.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1176-68/Afr).

Africoribates macfarlanei Balogh, 1959

Africoribates macfarlanei Balogh, 1959b: 104, figs 42–44.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Afroleius Mahunka, 1984

Afroleius undulatus (Balogh, 1959)

Africoribates undulatus Balogh, 1959c: 16, figs 22–26.

Afroleius undulatus: Coetzee 2015: 395.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-117768/Afr).

Remarks. There is no holotype mentioned in the original description, therefore this specimen should be considered as one of the syntypes.

Humerobates Sellnick, 1928

Humerobates papuanus Balogh, 1970

Humerobates papuanus Balogh, 1970b: 317, pl. XII. fig. 70.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes.

PUNCTORIBATIDAE THOR, 1937

***Cryptobothria* Wallwork, 1963**

***Cryptobothria papuana* Balogh, 1970**

Cryptobothria papuana Balogh, 1970b: 314, pl. XI, figs 64–65.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and two paratypes.

Remarks. There is an other vial labeled as *C. papuana* holotype but it contains two specimens and its locality (BG.M.B.106.) does not match to the original description.

Lamellobates (Lamellobates) Hammer, 1958

***Lamellobates (Lamellobates) botari* Balogh & Mahunka, 1977**

Lamellobates botari Balogh & Mahunka, 1977b: 262, fig. 10.

Lamellobates gyoergyi Balogh & Mahunka, 1977b: 263, fig. 11.

Lamellobates (Lamellobates) botari: Subías 2023: 325.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype ZIL (*L. botari*). Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG (*L. gyoergyi*).

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes (*L. botari*). Holotype and one paratype (*L. gyoergyi*).

***Lamellobates (Lamellobates) molecula molecula* (Berlese, 1916)**

Lamellobates angolensis Balogh, 1958: 28.

Lamellobates angolensis: Balogh 1960b: 102, figs 32–33.

Lamellobates (Lamellobates) molecula molecula: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 74.

Type material in literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, á Tervuren (*L. angolensis*).

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Lamellobates (Lamellobates) orientalis* Csiszár, 1961**

Lamellobates orientalis Csiszár, 1961a: 354, fig. 24.

Lamellobates orientalis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 200.

Type material in the material. Holotype, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Paralamellobates Bhaduri & Raychaudhuri, 1968

***Paralamellobates misella* (Berlese, 1910)**

Oribatella schoutedeni Balogh, 1959b: 106, figs 50–51.

Paralamellobates misella: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 174.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, á Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Punctoribates (Minguezetes) Subías, Kahwash et Ruiz, 1990

***Punctoribates (Minguezetes) longiporosus* Balogh, 1963**

Punctoribates longiporosus Balogh, 1963: 41, figs 12–13.

Punctoribates (Minguezetes) longiporosus: Subías 2008: 346.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, á Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Sagittazetes* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

***Sagittazetes agressor* J. Balogh & P. Balogh,
1983**

Sagittazetes agressor J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a:
98, figs 16A–F.
Sagittazetes agressor: Colloff & Halliday 1989: 181.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and six paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Five paratypes.

Remarks. According to the documentation in HMHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1995 but Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it there.

Zachvatkinibates (Alpizetes) Mahunka, 2001

***Zachvatkinibates (Alpizetes) perlongus* (Balogh,
1959)**

Punctoribates (?) perlongus Balogh, 1959a: 29, figs 1–3.
Minguezetes perlongus: Bayartogtokh, Grobler & Cobanoglu 2000: 30.

Schweizerzetes perlongus: Mahunka 2001: 132, figs 1–9.
Schweizerzetes perlongus: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2004: 279.

Zachvatkinibates (Alpizetes) perlongus: Subías: 2011: 360.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and paratypes. No deposition data available.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

GALUMNOIDEA JACOT, 1925

GALUMNELLIDAE PIFFL, 1970

Galumnella (Galumnella) Berlese, 1916

***Galumnella (Galumnella) areolata* Balogh, 1960**

Galumnella areolata Balogh, 1960a: 38, figs 77–80.

Galumnella areolata: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren and two paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Galumnella (Galumnella) cellularis* Balogh &
Mahunka, 1967**

Galumnella cellularis Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 55,
pl. VIII. figs 46–47.

Galumnella cellularis: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 67.

Galumnella cellularis: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020:
175.

Type material in the literature. Holotype HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-59-67/As).

***Galumnella (Galumnella) pauliani* Balogh, 1961**

Galumnella pauliani Balogh, 1961d: 36, fig. 45.

Galumnella pauliani: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 67.

Galumnella pauliani: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020:
176.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Galumnella (Galumnella) punctipennis* Balogh,
1960**

Galumnella punctipennis Balogh, 1960a: 38, figs 81–84.

Galumnella punctipennis: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren and two paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes (0-1197-68/Afr).

***Galumnella (Galumnella) rugosa* Balogh, 1960**

Galumnella rugosa Balogh, 1960a: 39, figs 85–86.

Galumnella rugosa: Akrami 2015: 495.

Galumnella rugosa: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Galumnella (Galumnella) rugosula* Balogh,
1960**

Galumnella rugosula Balogh, 1960a: 39, figs 87–89.

Galumnella rugosula: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren and one paratype with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1189-68/Afr).

***Galumnella (Galumnella) woschitzi* Balogh,
1970**

Galumnella woschitzi Balogh, 1970b: 326, pl. XVII. figs 97–98.

Galumnella woschitzi: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Galumnopsis (Galumnopsis) Grandjean*, 1931**

***Galumnopsis (Galumnopsis) rostrata* Balogh,
1962**

Galumnopsis rostrata Balogh, 1962d: 122, fig. 66.

Galumnopsis rostrata: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal de l’Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

***Galumnopsis (Galumnopsis) ruginervis* Balogh,
1962**

Galumnopsis ruginervis Balogh, 1962d: 121, figs 64–65.

Galumnopsis (Galumnopsis) ruginervis: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 67: fig. 29.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Musée Royal de l’Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1195-68/Afr).

***Galumnopsis (Galumnopsis) sagitta* Balogh,
1970**

Galumnopsis sagitta Balogh, 1970b: 326, pl. XVII. fig. 99.

Galumnopsis sagitta: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum, Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

***Galumnopsis (Galumnopsis) sellnicki* Balogh,
1960**

Galumnopsis sellnicki Balogh, 1960a: 36, figs 72–76.

Galumnopsis sellnicki: Balogh 1962d: 96.

Galumnopsis sellnicki: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 67.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren and two paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Porogalumnella quadriporosa* Balogh, 1968**

Porogalumnella quadriporosa Balogh, 1968: 274, pl. XI. figs 62–63.

Porogalumnella quadriporosa: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 68.

Galumnopsis (Porogalumnella) quadriporosa: Subías 2018: 479.

Porogalumnella quadriporosa: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 202.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes. The holotype and a part of the paratypes are deposited in the Bernice P. Bishop Museum Honolulu (Hawaii), another part of the paratypes in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

GALUMNIDAE JACOT, 1925

***Allogalumna (Allogalumna) Grandjean*, 1936**

***Allogalumna (Allogalumna) borhidii* Balogh &
Mahunka, 1979**

Allogalumna borhidii Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 58, fig. 17.

Allogalumna borhidii: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 75.
Allogalumna (Allogalumna) borhidii: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 55.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and four paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and nine paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description there are only five paratypes mentioned.

***Allogalumna (Allogalumna) confluens* Balogh, 1960**

Allogalumna confluens Balogh, 1960a: 34, figs 59–63.
Allogalumna (Allogalumna) confluens: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 55.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren and *cca.* one hundred and twenty paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: One hundred and twenty nine (six are broken) paratypes (0-11911-68/Afr).

***Allogalumna (Allogalumna) cubana* Balogh & Mahunka, 1979**

Allogalumna cubana Balogh & Mahunka, 1979a: 59, fig. 18.
Acroalumna cubana: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 135.
Allogalumna (Allogalumna) cubana: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 55.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and five paratypes.

Remarks. In the original description there are only four paratypes mentioned.

***Allogalumna (Allogalumna) dilatata* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Allogalumna dilatata J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 104, figs 21A–D.
Allogalumna dilatata: Colloff & Bruce 1998: 190.

Allogalumna (Allogalumna) dilatata: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 55.

Allogalumna (Allogalumna) dilatata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2019: 203.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. According to the documentation in HNHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1995 but Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it there.

***Allogalumna (Allogalumna) leleupi* Balogh, 1962**

Allogalumna leleupi Balogh, 1962d: 120, figs 61–63.
Allogalumna (Allogalumna) leleupi: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 55.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes, Musée Royal de l’Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes (0-1198-68/Afr).

***Allogalumna (Allogalumna) longula* (Balogh, 1961)**

Xenogalumna longula Balogh, 1961d: 32, figs 39–41.
Allogalumna (Allogalumna) longula: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 55.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Allogalumna (Allogalumna) machadoi* (Balogh, 1960)**

Acroalumna machadoi Balogh, 1960a: 36, figs 68–71.
(?) *Acroalumna machadoi*: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 55.

Allogalumna (Allogalumna) machadoi: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 177.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Allogalumna (Allogalumna) madagascarensis*
(Balogh, 1961)**

Ctenogalumna madagascarensis Balogh, 1961d: 34, figs 42–44.
Allogalumna madagascarensis: Mahunka 1996b: 168, figs 11–12. comb. nov.
Allogalumna madagascarensis: Mahunka 2002b: 14.
Ctenogalumna madagascarensis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 380, pl. 495. fig. 10.
Allogalumna (Allogalumna) madagascarensis: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 55.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1187-68/Afr).

***Allogalumna (Allogalumna) margaritifera*
Balogh, 1960**

Allogalumna margaritifera Balogh, 1960a: 34, figs 64–67.
Allogalumna (Allogalumna) margaritifera: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 55.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren and two paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Eleven paratypes (0-1196-68/Afr).

Remarks. Only two paratypes were reported in the original description.

***Allogalumna (Allogalumna) plowmanae*
J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Allogalumna plowmanae J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 103, figs 20A–D.
Allogalumna (Allogalumna) plowmanae: Colloff & Bruce 1998: 190.
Allogalumna (Allogalumna) plowmanae: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 56.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

Remarks. According to the documentation in HNHM, the holotype was sent to CSIRO, Can-

berra in 1995. However, Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it there.

***Allogalumna (Globogalumna) globulifera*
Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Allogalumna globulifera Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 295, figs 22A–C.
Globogalumna globulifera: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 139.
Globogalumna globulifera: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 78.
Allogalumna (Globogalumna) globulifera: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 56.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and two paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Flagellozetes (Flagellozetes) Balogh, 1970

***Flagellozetes (Flagellozetes) porosus* Balogh,
1970**

Flagellozetes porosus Balogh, 1970a: 66, fig. 57.
Flagellozetes (Flagellozetes) porosus: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 56.
Flagellozetes porosus: Ermilov, Khaustov & Joharchi 2020: 883.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and twenty-two paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and eighteen paratypes.

Galumna (Indogalumna) Balakrishnan, 1985

***Galumna (Indogalumna) sanctaehelena*
J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002**

Galumna rugosa Wallwork, 1977: 229, figs 90c–d.
Galumna sanctaehelena J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 266, pl. 480: 8. **nom. nov.** pro *Galumnba rugosa* Wallwork, 1977 nec. Hammer, 1968.
Galumna (Indogalumna) sanctaehelena: Subías 2019: 412.

Galumna (Galumna) Heyden, 1826

***Galumna (Galumna) agueroi* P. Balogh, 1997**

Galumna agueroi P. Balogh, 1997: 26, figs 17–22.

Galumna agueroi: Schatz 2006: 277.

Galumna (Galumna) agueroi: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 57.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Galumna (Galumna) basilewskyi* Balogh, 1962**

Galumna basilewskyi Balogh, 1962d: 111, figs 38–40.

Galumna (Galumna) basilewskyi: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 57.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Musée Royal de l’Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1194-68/Afr).

***Galumna (Galumna) discifera* Balogh, 1960**

Galumna discifera Balogh, 1960a: 18, figs 5–8.

Galumna discifera: Engelbrecht 1969: 107, figs 22–29.

Galumna engelbrechti J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 364, pl. 478: 10. nom. nov. pro *Galumna discifera* Engelbrecht, 1969 nec. Balogh 1960. **Nomen nudum.**

Galumna (Galumna) discifera: Akrami 2015: 494.

Galumna (Galumna) discifera: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 58.

Galumna (Galumna) discifera: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 181.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren, tree paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: one Paratype (0-1181-68/Afr).

Remarks. J. Balogh & P. Balogh (2002) provided a replacement name for *Galumna discifera* Engelbrecht, 1969 non *Galumna discifera* Balogh, 1960. However, Engelbrecht (1969) only provided a redescription of *G. discifera* Balogh, 1960 therefore this is not a homonymy but at most a misidentification. Therefore the name *Galumna engelbrechti* Balogh & Balogh is an unavailable **nomen nudum**. If this name were available it

would be a primary homonym of *Galumna engelbrechti* Mahunka, 1997

***Galumna (Galumna) grandjeani* Balogh, 1962**

Galumna grandjeani Balogh, 1962d: 112, figs 41–44.

Galumna (Galumna) grandjeani: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 58.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Musée Royal de l’Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-11866-68/Afr).

***Galumna (Galumna) hammerae* P. Balogh, 1985**

Galumna hammerae P. Balogh, 1985a: 92, 8A–E.

Galumna (Galumna) hammerae: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 191.

Galumna (Galumna) hammerae: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 58.

Type material in the literature. One “paratype”. The holotypes of the new species, will be deposited in the National Insect Collection, CSIRO, Canberra, Australia.

Deposited in HNHM: One “type”.

Remarks. The species is described upon a single specimen called “paratype” which clearly a mistake and it should be the holotype.

***Galumna (Galumna) irazu* P. Balogh, 1997**

Galumna irazu P. Balogh, 1997: 25, figs 13–16.

Galumna irazu: Schatz 2006: 277.

Galumna (Galumna) irazu: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 59.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and ten paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Galumna (Galumna) laselvae* P. Balogh, 1997**

Galumna laselvae P. Balogh, 1997: 25, figs 9–12.

Galumna laselvae: Schatz 2006: 278.

Galumna laselvae: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 59.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and sixteen paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Galumna (Galumna) mariae* Balogh, 1961**

Galumna mariae Balogh, 1961b: 523, fig. 13.

Galumna (Galumna) mariae: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 59.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, HNHM, and six paratypes.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-1183-68/Afr).

***Galumna (Galumna) monteithi* Balogh & Mahunka, 1978**

Galumna monteithi Balogh & Mahunka, 1978a: 48, figs 45–46.

Galumna monteithi: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 192.

Galumna (Galumna) monteithi: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 59.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fourteen paratypes. The holotype and partly the paratypes are deposited in CSIRO, Canberra; another part of paratypes are deposited in HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Thirteen paratypes.

***Galumna (Galumna) nonoensis* P. Balogh, 1988**

Galumna nonoensis P. Balogh, 1988c: 336, figs 42–45.

Galumna nonoensis: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 59.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (broken).

***Galumna (Galumna) parviporosa* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Galumna parviporosa J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 102, figs 19A–E.

Galumna parviporosa: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 192.

Galumna (Galumna) parviporosa: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 60.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. According to the documentation in HMHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1995 but Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it there.

***Galumna (Galumna) scripta* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Galumna scripta Balogh & Mahunka, 1966b: 36, fig. 23.

Galumna (Galumna) scripta: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 60.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and forty paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-83-67/Afr) and ten paratypes.

***Galumna (Galumna) strinovichi* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Galumna strinovichi J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 99, figs 17A–E.

Galumna strinovichi: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 192.

Galumna (Galumna) strinovichi: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 60.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eight paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Four paratypes.

Remarks. According to the documentation in HMHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1995 but Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find it there.

***Galumna (Galumna) szentivanyorum* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983**

Galumna szentivanyorum J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1983a: 100, figs 18A–E.

Galumna szentivanyorum: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 192.

Galumna (Galumna) szentivanyorum: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 60.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. According to the documentation in HNHM the holotype was sent to CSIRO, Canberra in 1995 but Colloff & Holliday (1998) did not find it.

***Galumna (Galumna) triops* Balogh, 1960**

Galumna triops Balogh, 1960a: 20, figs 9–12.

Galumna (Galumna) triops: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 60.

Galumna (Galumna) triops: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 184.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren, and two paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1199-68/Afr).

***Heterogalumna* Balogh, 1960**

***Heterogalumna lineolata* Balogh, 1960**

Heterogalumna lineolata Balogh, 1960a: 20, figs 13–16.

Heterogalumna lineolata: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 61.

Heterogalumna lineolata: Ermilov & Rybalov 2019a: 16.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren, and two paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1185-68/Afr).

***Heterogalumna monticola* Balogh, 1962**

Heterogalumna monticola Balogh, 1962d: 113, fig. 45.

Heterogalumna monticola: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 61.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Heterogalumna pygmaea* (Balogh, 1958)**

Galumna pygmaea Balogh, 1958: 31.

Heterogalumna pygmaea: Balogh 1960a: 22, 17–20.

Heterogalumna pygmaea: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 61.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1188-68/Afr).

Remarks. In the original description there are no data on the type material, therefore all specimens in the type series should be considered as syntypes.

Leptogalumna (Leptogalumna) Balogh, 1960

***Leptogalumna (Leptogalumna) ciliata* Balogh, 1960**

Leptogalumna ciliata Balogh, 1960a: 32, figs 38–40.

Leptogalumna (Leptogalumna) ciliata: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 61, fig. 59.

Leptogalumna (Leptogalumna) ciliata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 186.

Leptogalumna ciliata: Ermilov *et al.* 2021a: 155.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren and one paratype with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1193-68/Afr).

***Neopilizetes* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 1990**

***Neopilizetes neotropicus* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1978)**

Pilizetes neotropicus Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 296, figs 23A–E.

Neopilizetes neotropicus: J. Balogh & P. Balogh 1990: 139.

Pilizetes (Neopilizetes) neotropicus: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 80.

Neopilizetes neotropicus: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 61, fig. 49.

Neopilizetes neotropicus: Amorim *et al.* 569: figs 1–4.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

Notogalumna Sellnick, 1959

Notogalumna hexagona (Balogh, 1960)

Galumna hexagona Balogh, 1960a: 18, figs 1–4.
Notogalumna hexagona: Ermilov, Martens & Tolstikov 2014: 43.
Notogalumna hexagona: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 61.

Type material in the literature. Holotype Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One "paratype" (0-1184-68/Afr).

Remarks. The species is described on a single holotype. The specimen labelled as paratype should be the holotype.

Orthogalumna Balogh, 1961

Orthogalumna saeva Balogh, 1961

Orthogalumna saeva Balogh, 1961d: 31, figs 36–38.
Orthogalumna saeva: Ermilov & Smit 2017: 798.
Orthogalumna saeva: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 61, fig. 34.
Orthogalumna saeva: Ermilov & Chi-Man 2020: 184 figs 5–7.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and three paratypes.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) Grandjean, 1936

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) complicata Balogh & Mahunka, 1978

Pergalumna complicata Balogh & Mahunka, 1978c: 297, figs 24A–B.
Pergalumna (Pergalumna) complicata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 79.
Pergalumna (Pergalumna) complicata: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 61.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) conspicua Balogh, 1962

Pergalumna conspicua Balogh, 1962d: 119, figs 59–60.
Pergalumna (Pergalumna) conspicua: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 62.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) decorata Balogh & Mahunka, 1977

Pergalumna decorata Balogh & Mahunka, 1977a: 26, fig. 20.
Pergalumna (Pergalumna) decorata: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 62.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype HNHM, one paratype MHNG, one paratype ZIL.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype and one paratype.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) frater Balogh, 1960

Pergalumna frater Balogh, 1960a: 32, figs 54–58.
Pergalumna (Pergalumna) frater: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 63.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren, and five paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1192-68/Afr).

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) granulata Balogh & Mahunka, 1967

Pergalumna granulatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 56, pl. IX, figs 48–49.
Pergalumna (Pergalumna) granulata: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 63.
Pergalumna granulata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 187.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and seven paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-69-67/As) and six paratypes (0-70-67/As).

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) horvathorum*
P. Balogh, 1997**

Pergalumna horvathorum P. Balogh, 1997: 28, figs 23–26.

Pergalumna horvathorum: Schatz 2006: 279.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) horvathorum: Ermilov & Smit 2017: 798.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) horvathorum: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 63.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) longisetosa*
Balogh, 1960**

Pergalumna longisetosa Balogh, 1960a: 30. *Pergalumna longisetosa:* Balogh 1962d: 96. *Pergalumna (Pergalumna) longisetosa:* Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 63.

Pergalumna longisetosa: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 189.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren, and five paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes.

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) nuda* Balogh, 1960**

Pergalumna nuda Balogh, 1960a: 30, figs 46–49.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) nuda: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 64.

Pergalumna nuda: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 190.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren, and two paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Fourty paratypes (0-1182-68/Afr).

Remarks. In the original description a holotype and only two paratypes were designated.

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) obvia obvia*
(Berlese, 1914)**

Dimidiogalumna wallworki J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 366, pl. 481: 4. nom. nov. **Nomen nudum.**

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) obvia obvia: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 64.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) obvia obvia: Subías 2018: 472.

Remarks. J. Balogh & P. Balogh provided a replacement name for *Galumna elimata* (Koch) in Wallwork 1977: 232 as if it were a homonym of *Galumna elimata* (Koch, 1841). However, this is only a possible misidentification of *G. elimata* therefore the proposed new replacement name is invalid and represents a **nomen nudum**. Moreover, Wallwork's specimen reported as *G. elimata* (Koch) are now identified as *Pergalumna (P.) obvia obvia* (Berlese) (Ermilov & Klimov 2017, Subías 2018).

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) passimpunctata*
Balogh & Mahunka, 1969**

Pergalumna passimpunctata Balogh & Mahunka, 1969a: 16, fig. 52.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) passimpunctata: Oliveira *et al.* 2017: 80.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) passimpunctata: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 64.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and nineteen paratypes. Holotype and the greater part of the paratypes are in HNHM. Some paratypes are deposited in the collections of J. Aoki, E. Piffel, A. Rajsiki and T. Woolleey.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-545-68/D-Am) and twelve paratypes (0-546-68/D-Am).

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) punctulata* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967**

Pergalumna punctulatus Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 56, pl. IX. figs 50–51.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) punctulata: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 64.

Pergalumna punctulata: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 191.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and fifteen paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-63-67/As) and twelve paratypes (0-64-67/As).

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) sura* P. Balogh, 1997**

Pergalumna sura P. Balogh, 1997: 28, figs 19–21.

Pergalumna sura: Schatz 2006: 280.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) sura: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 64.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and thirteen paratypes. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) tahitiensis* J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002**

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) tahitiensis J. Balogh & P. Balogh, 2002: 379, pl. 495: 7. **nom. nov.** pro *Pergalumna montana* Hammer, 1961 nec. *Pergalumna montana* Hammer, 1961.

Pergalumna montana Hammer, 1972: 42, fig. 47.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) tahitiensis: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 64.

Remarks. J. Balogh & P. Balogh 2002 provided replacement name for *Pergalumna montana* Hammer, 1972 the junior homonym of *Pergalumna montana* Hammer, 1961. However in the publication (J. Balogh & P. Balogh 2002) they erroneously cited Hammer 1961 for both names.

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) taprobanica* P. Balogh, 1988**

Pergalumna taprobanica P. Balogh, 1988b: 189, figs 46–49.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) taprobanica: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 64.

Pergalumna taprobanica: Ermilov, Khaustov & Johar-chi 2020: 883.

Type material in the literature. Holotype. No data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype.

Remarks. The vial labelled as holotype seems to be empty.

***Pilizetes (Pilizetes) Sellnick*, 1937**

***Pilizetes (Pilizetes) australis* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

Pilizetes australis Balogh & Mahunka, 1966a: 20, figs 35–36.

Pilizetes australis: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 65.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes NM, four paratypes HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-110-67/Afr).

***Pilizetes (Pilizetes) basilewskyi* Balogh, 1958**

Pilizetes basilewskyi Balogh, 1958: 31.

Pilizetes basilewskyi: Balogh 1962d: 96, figs 46–48.

Pilizetes basilewskyi: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 65.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Pilizetes (Pilizetes) curtipilus* Balogh, 1960**

Pilizetes curtipilus Balogh, 1960a: 24, figs 26–28.

Pilizetes curtipilus: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 65.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren and ten paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Sixteen paratypes (0-1180-68/Afr).

Remarks. In the original description only ten paratypes are mentioned!

***Pilizetes (Pilizetes) dudichi* Balogh, 1966**

Pilizetes dudichi Balogh, 1966: 76, fig 8.

Pilizetes dudichi: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 65.

Type material in the literature. No data available.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-128-67/Afr) and one paratype (0-129-67/Afr).

Remarks. There is no holotype designated in the original description, therefore all specimens should be considered as syntypes.

***Pilizetes (Pilizetes) sellnicki* Balogh, 1958**

Pilizetes sellnicki Balogh, 1958: 31.

Pilizetes sellnicki: Balogh 1960a: 24, figs 29–31.

Pilizetes sellnicki: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 65.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: Two paratypes (0-142-67/Afr).

Remarks. There is no holotype designated in the original description, therefore all specimens should be considered as syntypes.

***Pilizetes (Pilizetes) subglaber* Balogh, 1962**

Pilizetes subglaber Balogh, 1962d: 115, figs 49–50.

Pilizetes subglaber: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 65.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and three paratypes Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

***Setogalumna P.* Balogh, 1985**

***Setogalumna excellens P.* Balogh, 1985**

Setogalumna excellens P. Balogh, 1985a: 94, figs 9A–E.

Setogalumna excellens: Colloff & Halliday 1998: 193.

Setogalumna excellens: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 66.

Type material in the literature. Holotype CSIRO, Canberra and five paratypes with no on deposition data available.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

Remarks. Colloff & Halliday (1998) did not find the type material in CSIRO. It is probably lost.

***Sphaerogalumna* Balogh, 1961**

***Sphaerogalumna index* (Balogh, 1960)**

Pergalumna index Balogh, 1960a: 30, figs 41–45.

Sphaerogalumna index: Balogh 1961f: 305, pl. 25, fig. 8.

Sphaerogalumna index: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 66, fig. 58.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren, and four paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Twenty five paratypes (0-1201-68/Afr).

Remarks. In the original description there are only four paratypes reported.

***Stictozetes* Berlese, 1916**

***Stictozetes bisulcata* (Balogh, 1960)**

Trachygalumna bisulcata Balogh, 1960a: 26, figs 21–25.

Stictozetes bisulcatus: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 66.

Stictozetes bisulcatus: Ermilov *et al.* 2021a: 155.

Type material in the literature. Holotype one male, allotype one female, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren and six paratypes with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: Nine paratypes (0-1179-68/Afr).

Remarks. In the original description there are only six paratypes reported.

***Taeniogalumna* Balogh, 1962**

***Taeniogalumna sphaerula* Balogh, 1962**

Taeniogalumna sphaerula Balogh, 1962d: 116, figs 55–58.

Taeniogalumna sphaerula: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 66, fig. 60.

Taeniogalumna sphaerula: Ermilov & Rybalov 2019b: 238.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and one paratype, Musée Royal de l'Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype.

***Trichogalumna (Trichogalumna)* Balogh, 1960**

***Trichogalumna (Trichogalumna) lunai* (Balogh, 1958)**

Pilogalumna (?) lunai Balogh, 1958: 32.

Trichogalumna lunai: Balogh 1960a: 26, figs 32–34.

Trichogalumna (Trichogalumna) lunai: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 66.

Type material in the literature. Collections du Musée royal du Congo belge, à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Trichogalumna (Trichogalumna) montana* Balogh, 1962**

Trichogalumna montana Balogh, 1962d: 116, figs 51–54.

Trichogalumna (Trichogalumna) montana: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 66.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal de l’Afrique Centrale à Tervuren.

Deposited in HNHM: No material was found.

***Trichogalumna (Trichogalumna) seminuda* Balogh, 1960**

Trichogalumna seminuda Balogh, 1960a: 28, figs 35–37.

Trichogalumna (Trichogalumna) seminuda: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 66.

Type material in the literature. Holotype, Musée Royal du Congo Belge, à Tervuren, and one paratype with no data on deposition.

Deposited in HNHM: One paratype (0-1200-68/Afr).

***Trichogalumna (Trichogalumna) subnuda* Balogh & Mahunka, 1967**

Trichogalumna subnuda Balogh & Mahunka, 1967a: 57, pl. X, figs 52–53.

Trichogalumna (Trichogalumna) subnuda: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 66.

Trichogalumna (Trichogalumna) subnuda: Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020: 193.

Type material in the literature. Holotype and eleven paratypes, HNHM.

Deposited in HNHM: Holotype (0-65-67/As) and nine paratypes (0-66-67/As).

Acknowledgements – The authors would like to thank David Nicolson (ITIS) for discussing some of the nomenclatural issues.

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